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for a healthy future

Selection criteria and inventory of effect biomarkers for the 2nd set of substances

Deliverable Report

D14.5

WP14 - Biomarkers of Effect

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1 Abstract/Summary

Background: Biomarkers of effect are defined as measurable biochemical, physiologic, behavioral, or other alteration in an organism that, depending on the magnitude, can be recognised as associated with an established or possible health impairment or disease. In D14.2 we performed literature searches for identifying the most relevant effect biomarkers in relation to the 1st round of prioritised chemical substances. These searches were crucial for proposing effect biomarkers that will be implemented in the HBM4EU aligned studies and other European birth cohorts during 2020-2021.

Objective: Joint deliverable 14.5/14.6 aimed to carry out a wide literature survey in order to create an inventory of available biomarkers of effects for the 2nd set of prioritised chemical families: Acrylamide, arsenic, lead, mercury, mycotoxins, pesticides and UV-filters. Additionally, results from the search on hexavalent chromium (included in the 1st round of substances) are also presented here.

Methods: Different research teams participating in WP14 covered each of the 2nd round prioritised chemical families based on their previous expertise. Comprehensive literature searches with defined search terms for both the exposure of interest and the selected health endpoints were conducted in the PubMed/MEDLINE database (D14.5). Given the wide amount of information collected, the most relevant effect biomarkers used in epidemiological settings are summarised, prioritised and linked to the available experimental or AOP support (D14.6).

Results: The most relevant effect biomarkers for the 2nd set of prioritised substances have been gathered from the literature searches conducted. Biomarkers have been classified in classical vs. novel effect biomarkers. Then, the most interesting effect biomarkers have been highlighted and discussed in the context of available mechanistic knowledge.

Conclusions: A preliminary selection of effect biomarkers that could be of interest has been highlighted by each of the participating teams in this deliverable. However, as explored in AD14.3, a detailed and multidisciplinary procedure is needed to go from this initial list of biomarkers to the effect biomarkers that could be implemented in the HBM4EU aligned studies, taking into account many scientific and technical issues. Analogously to D14.2, the results of these literature searches should be published in peer-review journals during the coming years to create a corpus of knowledge that may help to approach the field of effect biomarkers in a more systematic way.

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2 Introduction

This deliverable continues the work carried out in deliverables D14.1, D14.2 and D14.3, which allowed the creation of an inventory of effect biomarkers related to the 1st list of prioritised compounds, which has been of great help to prioritise the implementation of effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies, as well as in other European birth cohorts.

The general strategy for the 2nd list of substances has been based on lessons learned from the 1st list. WP14 has learned from the literature searches on effect biomarkers for the 1st set of prioritised chemical compounds that each search is different and needs to be planned based on the specific chemical family under study, but some common points should be followed:

1. Summary of effect biomarkers that have been more frequently employed.
2. Novel biomarkers, including the omics field.
3. Identification of gaps in knowledge.
4. The need for experimental support of effect biomarkers based on mechanistic data and/or AOPs.

Since each chemical family needs a different search strategy, D14.5 presents the rationale, strategy and methods followed in each case, explaining the steps followed by each team in order to select the most relevant information, while managing many potential references. In addition, D14.6 presents, classifies and discusses the most relevant effect biomarkers found. D14.6 presents and summarises the most relevant data collected, then classifies it into classical or traditional effects biomarkers vs. more novel ones, and finally proposes some effect biomarkers of interest, together with available mechanistic or AOP information that can support the biological interest for a potential implementation in HBM studies.

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3 Methods

3.1 Acrylamide (BfR and UGR)

Background and Justification of health endpoint(s)

Carcinogenesis: Based on the evidence of acrylamide carcinogenicity in animals, the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) has classified acrylamide as a group 2A carcinogen for humans. Humans are exposed to acrylamide mainly through dietary intake, tobacco smoking, and special occupations (i.e. flocculants, grouting materials, textile manufacture). Acrylamide is metabolised in the body to form the epoxide glycidamide (GA), and both form adducts with DNA and with amino acids in hemoglobin. Several epidemiologic studies have explored its potential as a human carcinogen observing some positive associations between acrylamide intake and human carcinogenesis. A majority of these studies reported no statistically significant association between dietary acrylamide intake and various cancers, and only a study reported increased risk for renal, endometrial, and ovarian cancers.

Reproductive toxicity of acrylamide: Acrylamide is a low molecular weight compound that can easily dissolve in water, and pass through the placenta in animals and human organism. This compound was also found in breast milk of women. It was also estimated that about 50% of dietary acrylamide may be transferred through the placental blood into the embryo. Thus, it may have an influence on the normal prenatal and early postnatal development of infants. Nonetheless, the data on the risk of the harmful influence of acrylamide regarding early human development have not been properly assessed. The reproductive toxicity of acrylamide is also reflected by its influence on male infertility.

Specific search strategy, methodology and search terms

BfR performed the literature searches on acrylamide and neurotoxicity and cancer. Below the searches are listed:

- 1) "Acrylamide"[Mesh] AND "Neurotoxicity Syndromes"[Mesh] (46 articles).
- 2) "Acrylamide" AND ["Neurotox*" OR "Behavior" OR Cognit*"] (1399 articles).
- 3) "Acrylamide"[Mesh] AND "Carcinogenicity Tests"[Mesh] (17 articles).
- 4) "Acrylamide" AND ["Cancer*" OR "Carcinogen" OR "Tumor*" OR Mutagen*"] (1224 articles).

In total, they screened 626 titles and abstracts. Out of these, 87 papers were selected for more detailed review. The following PubMed searches were conducted:

- 1 "Acrylamide"[Mesh] AND "Neurotoxicity Syndromes"[Mesh] (46 articles).
- 2 "Acrylamide" AND ["Neurotox*" OR "Behavior" OR Cognit*"] (1399 articles).
- 3 "Acrylamide"[Mesh] AND "Carcinogenicity Tests"[Mesh] (17 articles).
- 4 "Acrylamide" AND ["Cancer*" OR "Carcinogen" OR "Tumor*" OR Mutagen*"] (1224 articles).

BfR searches Acrylamide (Jul 24 2019)							
Acrylamide + D14.6 Search (UGR, BfR)							
standard search criteria: full text, 10 years, human, animal; < 100 hits: no age filter							
		hits		possibly relev			
Searches	Health Endpoints	human	animal	prescreening	totally selecte		
1	Neurotoxicity MESH	8	26	34			
2	Neurotoxicity	160	207	160			
3	Cancer MESH	2	6	8			
4	Cancer	424	226	424			
				626		87	
1	"Acrylamide"[Mesh] AND "Neurotoxicity Syndromes"[Mesh]						
2	"Acrylamide" AND ["Neurotox*" OR "Behavior" OR "Cognit*"]						
3	"Acrylamide"[Mesh] AND "Carcinogenicity Tests"[Mesh]						
4	"Acrylamide" AND ["Cancer*" OR "Carcinogen" OR "Tumor*" OR "Mutagen*"]						

Figure 1: Searches with terms from selected health endpoints (BfR)

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In addition, UGR performed the literature searches on acrylamide and growth, development, reproductive and endocrine disruption effects (Date of search: July-August 2019). Despite the notable number of articles found with the proposed keywords, only those useful for the purpose of this search were selected. Below the searches are listed:

- 1) (acrylamide[Title]) AND ((reproductive health[Title] OR reproduction[Title] OR development[Title] OR developmental)[Title]) + filters: Free Full Text, English= 17 papers
- 2) (acrylamide[Title/Abstract]) AND ((reproductive health[Title/Abstract] OR reproduction[Title/Abstract] OR development[Title/Abstract] OR developmental)[Title/Abstract]) + filters: Free Full Text, English= 175 papers
- 3) "Acrylamide"[Mesh] AND "Reproduction"[Mesh] + filters: Free Full Text, English= 18 papers
- 4) "Reproduction"[Mesh] AND "acrylamide" + filters: Free Full Text, English= 41 papers
- 5) "Embryonic and Fetal Development"[Mesh] AND "Reproduction"[Mesh] AND "acrylamide" + filters: Free Full Text, English= 5 papers
- 6) "Growth and Development"[Mesh] AND "Reproduction"[Mesh] AND "acrylamide" + filters: Free Full Text, English= 17 papers

Figure 2: Searches with terms from selected health endpoints (UGR)

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3.2 Arsenic (VITO, UGR and NIPH)

Background

Arsenic (As) is widely present in air, soil, and water, drinking water being an important exposure route. Inorganic As (iAs) is more toxic than organic As, and trivalent iAs species are generally considered to be the most toxic (Carlin et al., 2016; Tchounwou et al., 2019). The primary metabolism of iAs in humans yields monomethylarsonic acid (MMA), which undergoes a secondary methylation to produce dimethylarsinic acid (DMA). As methylation may be a bioactivation process, the degree of methylation is assessed by determining the fractions of As/MMA and MMA/DMA and shows interindividual variability (Tchounwou et al., 2019).

Justification of health endpoint(s)

The International Agency for Research on Cancer has classified As as a class I human carcinogen. Wide range of other adverse health effects have been associated with acute and chronic As exposure as well. The National Research Council concluded in its 2013 review of the draft US EPA human health risk assessment of iAs that there is sufficient evidence for a causal association with lung, skin, and bladder cancer and ischemic heart disease (National Research Council, 2013). In its recent update of the iAs health risk assessment protocol, US EPA added hypertension, stroke, diabetes, skin lesions, and effects on pregnancy outcomes (fetal and infant morbidity, fetal loss, stillbirth, and neonatal mortality) to this. The strength of evidence for liver and kidney cancer, non-malignant respiratory disease, effects on the immune system, and neurodevelopment is less robust according to US EPA. Nevertheless, developmental neurotoxicity was, in spite of the small database, additionally identified as a particularly important endpoint for cost-benefit analysis (US EPA, 2019).

There is generally a lack of insight in the health impact of low level As exposure. Besides, the underlying mechanisms of iAs toxicity are poorly understood. Recognised molecular targets and modes of action are incomplete and often non-specific. In addition, it is likely that most health outcomes involve multiple interactive modes of action, which complicates the dose-response evaluation, especially in the low-dose region (Tchounwou et al., 2019; US EPA, 2019). This is also the case for cancer, metabolic syndrome and diabetes, cardiovascular effects, and neurobehavioural endpoints (Tchounwou et al., 2019). Therefore, these health outcomes were studied in this review to gain insight in their association with arsenic exposure in human and experimental studies and to identify effect biomarkers that may be used in future epidemiological research.

Specific search strategy, methodology and search terms

A comprehensive literature search was performed in the US National Library of Medicine (NCBI Pubmed) at June 7th 2019. The search terms, including MeSH® terms and MeSH Supplementary Concepts (<https://www.nlm.nih.gov/mesh>), are listed below. Search terms for As exposure were combined with search terms for health endpoints. Since MMA and DMA appeared to be widely used abbreviations, search results with an abstract not including 'arsenic' were omitted. Results published in the past ten years were then selected and reviews were removed. Human observational studies were separated from *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies focused on mechanisms of action by screening of the abstracts. Studies that did not evaluate biomarkers of effect or relevant health endpoints were omitted. Publications without abstract or not written in English and duplicates were also removed. Biomarkers of effect that were associated with arsenic exposure were listed from the abstracts of the remaining human observational studies. The abstracts of the experimental studies were explored to identify toxicity pathways and mechanisms of action of As related to the identified biomarkers of effect.

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Table 1: Literature search performed in the NCBI Pubmed at June 7th 2019

Arsenic exposure	("Arsenic"[Mesh] OR "Arsenates"[Mesh] OR "Arsenites"[Mesh] OR "arsenic acid"[Supplementary Concept] OR "arsenite"[Supplementary Concept] OR "arsenous acid"[Supplementary Concept] OR "monomethylarsonic acid"[Supplementary Concept] OR "dimethylarsinous acid"[Supplementary Concept] OR ("arsenite"[Supplementary Concept] OR "arsenite"[All Fields]) OR ("arsenic acid"[Supplementary Concept] OR "arsenic acid"[All Fields] OR "arsenate"[All Fields]) OR "Arsenious acid"[All Fields] OR iAs[All Fields] OR "Arsenic trioxide"[All Fields] OR AsIII[All Fields] OR "As(III)"[All Fields] OR AsV[All Fields] OR "As(V)"[All Fields] OR MMA[All Fields] OR "dimethylarsinic acid"[All Fields] OR "dimethylarsenic acid"[All Fields] OR "dimethylarsonic acid"[All Fields] OR DMA[All Fields])
Neurobehaviour	("Nervous System"[Mesh] OR "Nervous System Diseases"[Mesh] OR "Neurogenesis"[Mesh] OR "Child Development"[Mesh] OR "Cognitive Dysfunction"[Mesh] OR "Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Behavior and Behavior Mechanisms"[Mesh] OR "Reproductive Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Social Behavior Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Child Behavior Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Adolescent Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Antisocial Personality Disorder"[Mesh] OR "Infant Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Spatial Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Sucking Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Sexual Behavior, Animal"[Mesh] OR "Sexual Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Paternal Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Maternal Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Impulsive Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Feeding Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Exploratory Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Compulsive Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Child Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Behavior, Animal"[Mesh] OR "Mental Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Neurobehavior"[All Fields] OR "Neurodevelopment"[All Fields] OR "Neurology"[All Fields] OR "Autism"[All Fields] OR "Hyperactivity"[All Fields] OR "ASD"[All Fields] OR "ADHD"[All Fields] OR "mental retardation"[All Fields] OR "IQ"[All Fields])
Diabetes and metabolic syndrome	("Metabolic Syndrome"[Mesh] OR "Nutritional and Metabolic Diseases"[Mesh] OR "Metabolic Diseases"[Mesh] OR "Metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Glucose Metabolism Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Metabolome"[Mesh] OR "Metabolomics"[Mesh] OR "Receptor, Insulin"[Mesh] OR "Diabetes Mellitus"[Mesh] OR "Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2"[Mesh] OR "Insulin"[Mesh] OR "Insulin Resistance"[Mesh] OR "Hyperglycemia"[Mesh] OR "Glucose"[Mesh] OR "Blood Glucose"[Mesh] OR "Pancreas"[Mesh] OR "Metabolic disorder"[All Fields] OR "glucose homeostasis"[All Fields] OR "HOMA-IR"[All Fields])
Cardiovascular	("Cardiovascular System"[Mesh] OR "Cardiovascular Abnormalities"[Mesh] OR "Pregnancy Complications, Cardiovascular"[Mesh] OR "Diagnostic Techniques, Cardiovascular"[Mesh] OR "Cardiovascular Physiological Phenomena"[Mesh] OR "Cardiovascular Diseases"[Mesh] OR "Myocardial Infarction"[Mesh] OR "Myocardial Ischemia"[Mesh] OR "Ischemia"[Mesh] OR "Coronary Artery Disease"[Mesh] OR "Cardiology"[Mesh] OR "cardiovascular"[All Fields] OR "ischemic heart disease"[All Fields] OR "Hypertension"[All Fields])
Cancer	("Lung Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Urinary Bladder Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Skin Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Early Detection of Cancer"[Mesh] OR "Neoplasms, Second Primary"[Mesh] OR "Urologic Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Urogenital Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Biomarkers, Tumor"[Mesh])

To further substantiate the links between human effect biomarkers and the toxicity pathways of As, the AOP-Wiki v2.2 (OECD, 2018) was consulted. As search terms were entered as search term for stressors. Effect biomarkers from human observational studies and biological events involved in the toxicity pathways and mechanisms of action retrieved from the experimental studies were entered as search terms for KEs and KERs. AOPs were selected if three or more KEs (including MIEs) concerned effect biomarkers and/or elements of toxicity pathways identified in the literature search and AOs were related to relevant health endpoints.

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US EPA (2019). *Updated Problem Formulation and Protocol for the Inorganic Arsenic IRIS Assessment*.

3.3 Lead (NCRWE and MUW)

Background

EFSA concluded: "The CONTAM Panel identified developmental neurotoxicity in young children and cardiovascular effects and nephrotoxicity in adults as potential critical adverse effects of lead on which to base the risk assessment" and "In humans, the central nervous system is the main target organ for lead toxicity" (EFSA, 2010).

Justification of health endpoint(s)

Developmental neurotoxicity has been chosen as the focus of the literature search on Lead, because this endpoint is the most critical effect at low doses of exposure (EFSA, 2010).

Specific search strategy, methodology and search terms

NCRWE and MUW have performed an initial literature search in PubMed (27.03.2019) using the following search terms: (((("lead") OR "pb") OR lead[MeSH Terms]) OR "plumbum"[Title/Abstract]) OR "7439 92 1"[EC/RN Number]) and neurodevelopment. This resulted in 596 references in total. A sorting process followed this search to exclude the references in which the term "lead" was only used as a verb and not as metal. This reduced the number of references to approximately 160 articles. See the figure 3 below.

Figure 3: The search strategy reduced the number of references from 596 to approximately 160 articles

Overview of the results from the initial search: The 160 references were further sorted according to relevance. The inclusion criteria were that at least one effect biomarker were included in relation to

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a neurodevelopmental outcome associated to lead exposure. NCRWE and MUW also included *in vitro* data when information on candidate genes was indicated. As a result, we ended up with 24 eligible references that were grouped according to biomarker significance.

References

EFSA Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain (CONTAM). Scientific opinion on lead in food. EFSA Journal 2010;8(4).

3.4 Mercury (CNRS, UCY and ISCIII)

Background and justification of health endpoint(s)

The heavy metal mercury (Hg) is still considered as a major pollutant and health risk factor because less toxic inorganic mercury is transformed into toxic methylmercury (MeHg) in the environment itself and mercury accumulates across the aquatic food chain. Humans are primarily exposed to two species of Hg: methylmercury via fish consumption and inorganic Hg (as elemental Hg vapor) via dental amalgams. As such, exposures to Hg impact both the public and certain occupational groups (e.g., dentists, gold miners) worldwide. Exposure of the population to total mercury and methylmercury in particular is thus still a preoccupation of authorities and scientists (Basu et al., 2018). Major adverse effects of MeHg are neurological, but metabolic, reproductive, immune system effects are reported too. The brain and nervous system are the primary target tissues of MeHg in neonates, children, adolescents and adults (Al Osman et al., 2019; Sharma et al., 2019).

Exposure to Hg during pregnancy and early childhood can cause neurodevelopmental impairment and subclinical brain dysfunction because Hg can cross the placenta and the blood–brain-barrier, exposing the fetus during critical windows of development. In the brain, Hg can affect critical developmental processes, including cell proliferation, migration, differentiation, synaptogenesis, myelination, and apoptosis (Cariccio et al., 2019).

Mercury can cause immune, sensory, neurological, motor, and behavioral dysfunctions similar to traits defining/associated with autistic disorders, and these similarities extend to neuroanatomy, neurotransmitters, and biochemistry. Molecular mechanisms indicate that Hg exposure can induce death, disorganisation and/or damage to selected neurons in the brain similar to that seen in recent brain pathology studies of patients diagnosed with an ASD, and this alteration may likely produce the symptoms by which ASDs are diagnosed (Kern et al., 2016).

Specific search strategy, methodology and search terms

In order to identify biomarkers of effect for mercury, a pubmed search was performed by combining terms related to the compound of interest, i.e., “(mercury OR methylmercury or MeHg OR “CH₃-Hg”)” and terms which are specific for each health endpoint potentially capable of being effected by mercury, i.e., reproduction, neurodevelopment, metabolic & cardiovascular, immune/allergy, endocrine, and cancer health endpoints.

A preliminary search using this strategy retrieved an overwhelming amount of articles, albeit with overlaps between articles from one or another health endpoint.

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Table 2: Number of articles retrieved in both human and animals for each health endpoint after filtering by availability of full text and 10 years.

Neurobehavior	Cancer	Endocrine diseases	Immunology/ Allergy	Metabolic & Cardiovascular	Reproduction	TOTAL
Humans: 859	Human: 257	Humans:142	Human: 269	Humans: 1124	Humans: 643	Humans: 3294
Animals: 578	Animal: 85	Animals: 150	Animal: 205	Animals: 1466	Animals: 550	Animals: 3034

In order to focus the literature search on novel biomarkers and reduce the number of articles, search terms related to OMICs, epigenetics or biomarker as well as search terms related to unwanted articles were incorporated in the final search query. These terms were all identified by inputting epigenetic-, OMICs- and biomarker-related articles or typical articles to be omitted into Yale Mesh Analyser (<http://mesh.med.yale.edu/>) and consisted of the following:

Epigenetic terms: "DNA (Cytosine-5-)-Methyltransferase 1"[Mesh]; "DNA (Cytosine-5-)-Methyltransferases / genetics"[Mesh]; "DNA (Cytosine-5-)-Methyltransferases*"[Mesh]; "Epigenesis, Genetic*"[Mesh]; "DNA Modification Methylases*"[Mesh]; "Epigenetic*"[tiab]; "Epigenomics*"[Mesh]; "DNA Methylation*"[Mesh]; "Methylation"[Mesh]; "DNA Methylation / drug effects*"[Mesh]; "DNA Methylation / genetics*"[Mesh]; "Genomic Instability / genetics"[Mesh]; "CpG Islands / genetics"[Mesh]

OMICS terms: "Transcriptome / drug effects"[Mesh]; "Transcriptome / genetics*"[Mesh]; "Metabolomics"[Mesh]; "metabolome"[Mesh]; "Metabolomics"[Mesh]; "Metabolome / drug effects*"[Mesh]; "Metabolic Diseases / genetics"[Mesh]

Biomarker terms: "biomarkers"[tiab]; "Biomarkers / analysis"[Mesh]; "Biomarkers / urine"[Mesh]; "Biomarkers / blood"[Mesh]; "Fetal Blood / drug effects*"[Mesh]; "Blood Chemical Analysis"[Mesh]

Exclusion terms: "Rivers / chemistry"[Mesh], "Mercury / pharmacokinetics*"[Mesh], "Soil Pollutants / chemistry*"[Mesh]

Additionally, search terms specific to each health endpoint were regrouped using the operator "OR", to remove overlaps and generate a list of unique articles.

The final search terms used on the **9th of May 2019** is as follows:

mercury OR methylmercury or MeHg OR "CH3-Hg" AND ("DNA (Cytosine-5-)-Methyltransferase 1"[Mesh] OR "DNA (Cytosine-5-)-Methyltransferases / genetics"[Mesh] OR "DNA (Cytosine-5-)-Methyltransferases*"[Mesh] OR "Epigenesis, Genetic*"[Mesh] OR "DNA Modification Methylases*"[Mesh] OR "Epigenetic*"[tiab] OR "Epigenomics*"[Mesh] OR "DNA Methylation*"[Mesh] OR "Methylation"[Mesh] OR "DNA Methylation / drug effects*"[Mesh] OR "DNA Methylation / genetics*"[Mesh] OR "Genomic Instability / genetics"[Mesh] OR "CpG Islands / genetics"[Mesh] OR "Transcriptome / drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Transcriptome / genetics"[Mesh] OR "Metabolomics"[Mesh] OR "metabolome"[Mesh] OR "Metabolomics"[Mesh] OR "Metabolome / drug effects*"[Mesh] OR "Metabolic Diseases / genetics"[Mesh] OR "biomarkers"[tiab] OR "Biomarkers / analysis"[Mesh] OR "Biomarkers / urine"[Mesh] OR "Biomarkers / blood"[Mesh] OR "Fetal Blood / drug effects*"[Mesh] OR "Blood Chemical Analysis"[Mesh]) AND (((((((((((("Behavior"[Mesh]) OR ("Behavior and Behavior Mechanisms"[Mesh] OR "Reproductive Behavior"[Mesh])) OR "Social Behavior Disorders"[Mesh]) OR ("Child Behavior Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Adolescent Behavior"[Mesh])) OR "Antisocial Personality Disorder"[Mesh]) OR ("Infant Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Spatial Behavior"[Mesh])) OR "Sucking Behavior"[Mesh]) OR ("Sexual Behavior, Animal"[Mesh] OR "Sexual Behavior"[Mesh])) OR ("Paternal Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Maternal Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Impulsive Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Feeding Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Exploratory Behavior"[Mesh])) OR ("Compulsive Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Child Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Behavior, Animal"[Mesh])) OR "Mental Disorders"[Mesh])) OR (Behavior OR Neurobehavior OR Neurodevelopment OR Neurology OR Parkinson OR Alzheimer OR Autism OR Hyperactivity OR ASD OR ADHD OR mental retardation OR IQ loss OR internalizing OR externalizing OR depression OR cognition OR anxiety OR hearing loss OR visual acuity OR social skills)) OR (((((((("Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Uterine Cervical Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Urologic Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Liver Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Hereditary Breast and Ovarian Cancer Syndrome"[Mesh] OR "Early Detection of Cancer"[Mesh]) OR ("Urogenital Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Testicular Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Endometrial Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Vaginal

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Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Uterine Neoplasms"[Mesh])) OR ("Prostatic Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Ovarian Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Endocrine Gland Neoplasms"[Mesh])) OR ("Breast Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Neoplasms, Germ Cell and Embryonal"[Mesh] OR "Tumor Microenvironment"[Mesh])) OR ("Thyroid Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Pituitary Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Brain Neoplasms"[Mesh]))) OR (Cancer OR hormone-dependent cancer OR neoplasm OR malignant tumor OR Leukemia)) OR ("Endocrine System"[Mesh] OR "Endocrine Glands"[Mesh] OR "Endocrine System Diseases"[Mesh] OR "Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Gonadal Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Placental Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Pituitary Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Growth Hormone"[Mesh] OR "Thyroid Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Gastrointestinal Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Sex Hormone-Binding Globulin"[Mesh] OR "Adrenocorticotrophic Hormone"[Mesh] OR "Adrenal Cortex Hormones"[Mesh] OR Endocrine system OR hypothyroidism OR hyperthyroidism OR adrenal OR gonadal steroid hormones) OR ("Allergy and Immunology"[Mesh] OR "Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR "Rhinitis, Allergic, Seasonal"[Mesh] OR "Food Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR "Drug Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR "Shellfish Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR Allergy OR Hypersensitive OR respiratory allergy OR gastrointestinal allergy OR multiple chemical sensitivity OR allergic hypersensitivity disease OR contact allergy OR "Immune System"[Mesh] OR "Immune System Diseases"[Mesh] OR Immune system OR autoimmune disease OR cytokines OR white cells OR innate immune system OR adaptive immune system) OR ("Metabolic Syndrome"[Mesh] OR "Nutritional and Metabolic Diseases"[Mesh] OR "Metabolic Diseases"[Mesh] OR "Metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Glucose Metabolism Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Acidosis"[Mesh] OR "Metabolome"[Mesh] OR "Metabolomics"[Mesh] OR "Receptor, Insulin"[Mesh] OR "Lipolysis"[Mesh] OR "Gout"[Mesh] OR "Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2"[Mesh] OR "Acidosis, Renal Tubular"[Mesh] OR "Homocysteinemia" [Supplementary Concept] OR "Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptor Gamma Coactivator 1-alpha"[Mesh] OR "Obesity"[Mesh] OR "Pediatric Obesity"[Mesh] OR "Obesity, Abdominal"[Mesh] OR "Abdominal obesity metabolic syndrome" [Supplementary Concept] OR "Cardiovascular System"[Mesh] OR "Cardiovascular Abnormalities"[Mesh] OR "Pregnancy Complications, Cardiovascular"[Mesh] OR "Cardiovascular Diseases"[Mesh] OR adiposity OR body composition OR obesity OR abdominal obesity OR waist hip ratio OR adipose tissue OR adipokine OR visceral fat OR body fat OR overweight OR Metabolic OR Metabolic disorder OR Metabolic syndrome OR glucose homeostasis OR Hyperlipidemia OR Dyslipidemia OR hypertriglyceridemia OR HOMA-IR OR insulin resistance OR pancreas OR liver OR kidney) OR (reproductive OR puberty OR pregnancy OR infertility OR semen quality OR placenta OR anogenital distance OR hypospasia OR cryptorchidism OR "Reproductive Health"[Mesh] OR "Reproductive Medicine"[Mesh] OR "Reproduction"[Mesh] OR "Reproductive Techniques, Assisted"[Mesh] OR "Infertility"[Mesh])) **NOT** ("Rivers / chemistry"[Mesh] OR "Mercury / pharmacokinetics*"[Mesh] OR "Soil Pollutants / chemistry*"[Mesh]) -

In order to organize search results by search queries for each health endpoint, a group entitled “multiple endpoints” was created containing articles including two or more health endpoints. After filtering by articles published in the last 10 years and by full text availability, the following number of articles were retrieved using the final search query.

Table 3: Number of articles were retrieved using the final search query

	Neurodevelopment	Cancer	Endocrine	Immune	Metabolic & Cardiovascular	Reproduction	Multiple endpoints	Total
Human	38	9	0	10	75	30	102	264
Other animals	13	4	5	6	120	9	60	217

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3.5 Mycotoxins (INSA and MU)

Background

Mycotoxins are secondary fungal metabolites often found as natural contaminants in agricultural commodities all over the world and their occurrence pose a risk for human and animal health (Bennett and Klich, 2003; Wu et al., 2014). Ingestion of contaminated food, e.g., cereals and cereal-based food, dried fruits, coffee and fruit-based beverages, is the major route of mycotoxin exposure, while dermal and inhalation routes of mycotoxin exposure are less common (Zain 2011). Thus, widespread exposure of the general population to this substance group occurs, as well as co-exposure and aggregate exposure. Children are particularly vulnerable to mycotoxins effects due to the restricted diet with high consumption of cereal-based food and the immaturity of some defence systems. The impact of mycotoxins on human health depends on the toxin type, its conjugation forms and concentration, period of exposure, pharmacokinetics and accumulation of the mycotoxins as well as on factors related with the exposed person's physiology, e.g., age, gender, immune system and health state of the exposed person (Bennett and Klich 2003; Jonathan et al. 2004; Zain 2011). Within the mycotoxins group (2nd list of prioritised substances), deoxynivalenol (DON) and fumonisin B1 (FB1), were selected to be primarily addressed under the HBM4EU.

DON (also known as vomitoxin) exposure has been linked to acute animal and human gastroenteritis outbreaks (Pestka et al, 2010). It inhibits protein synthesis, stimulating the pro-inflammatory response, which results in the impairment of multiple physiological functions, such as the intestinal barrier, immune regulation and reproduction (Bensassi et al, 2009; Konigs et al, 2008; Wu et al, 2014). Fumonisin B₁ (FB₁) exposure has been associated with several human adverse health effects, particularly liver and kidney toxicity and oesophageal cancer (Group 2B, IARC 2002). The inhibition of ceramide synthesis and consequent disruption of sphingolipids metabolism as well as the induction of oxidative stress are the major mechanisms of FB₁-induced toxicity (Wangia et al, 2019).

Regarding the policy questions for mycotoxins, the ones that should be addressed by WP 14 in interaction with WP 13 are: i) which are the key events that determine the long-term health effects from low-dose continuous exposure to the target mycotoxins and ii) which are the most reliable and meaningful effect biomarkers for single and combined effects?

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Justification of the health endpoint(s) selected

To start addressing both questions, the most relevant health outcomes were selected for each mycotoxin, based on the effects reported in several epidemiological and animal studies. In addition, the mechanisms of action that are deemed to underlie their toxicity (in vitro/ex vivo and in vivo studies) were considered, in an attempt to link the identified health outcomes to central molecular, cellular or tissue/organ effects.

DON is suspected to be toxic for reproduction and it is able to cross the human placenta (Nielsen et al., 2011). DON exposure affects H295R cell viability, steroidogenesis and gene expression indicating their potential as endocrine disruptors (Ndossi et al., 2012). DON (and other trichothecenes), is immunotoxic, acting as a potent inhibitor of protein synthesis and stimulating the pro-inflammatory response (Sundheim et al., 2017).

FB1 is classified by IARC as possibly carcinogenic to humans (Group 2B, IARC, 2002). In vivo studies have shown that the repeated exposure to this toxin causes liver and kidney toxicity (EFSA, 2018) and may lead to liver and kidney tumorigenesis (IARC, 2002). FB1 is not mutagenic, being clastogenic to mammalian cells (EFSA, 2018); it also acts as a tumor promoter. FB1 adverse effects are mainly mediated by the inhibition of ceramide synthases, which are key enzymes in sphingolipid metabolism. Based on the results of animal studies, FB1 is considered as a potential immunotoxic substance (WHO, 2011).

In view of the above information, the literature searches for DON and FB1 were focused on the following topics/health endpoints:

- FB1 and hepatotoxicity, nephrotoxicity and carcinogenicity
- DON and immunotoxicity, reprotoxicity and endocrine disruption
- Population groups of high concern – general population and children
- Novel or specific effect biomarkers
- Key events (include mechanistic in vitro/in vivo studies)
- Co-exposure to several mycotoxins and combined effects

Specific search strategy, methodology and search terms

Concerning effect biomarkers, the keywords used for Fumonisin and DON for each selected endpoint are summarised in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. The Microsoft Excel based application Abstract Sifter (Baker et al., 2019) was applied to facilitate the finding of articles of interest in PubMed. In addition, the Text Mining tool CRAB 3.0 (<http://crab3.lionproject.net>) aimed at supporting literature review in chemical cancer risk assessment via PubMed, was applied to complete the literature survey.

Although the primary objective was to select human studies presenting data on each mycotoxin and effect biomarkers (1st analysis of the literature surveyed), in a second approach, the same articles were screened for *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies that provide mechanistic information related to the several target health endpoints (2nd analysis of the literature surveyed). This knowledge is relevant to try to establish the molecular initiation event and the key events in order to contribute to production of adverse outcome pathways (AOP) for FB1 and hepatotoxicity, nephrotoxicity or carcinogenicity and for DON and immunotoxicity, reprotoxicity or endocrine disruption. These will liaise with the work performed in WP13.

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Table 4: Methodology followed for Fumonisin, target endpoints and outputs generated

Mycotoxin and health endpoint	Search terms*	Filter: Last 10 years (>2008)	1st analysis - Exclusion criteria	2nd analysis (AOP-related studies) - Exclusion criteria
Fumonisin AND cancer	(Fumonisin B1 OR FB1 OR 116355-83-0 OR multiple mycotoxins) AND (((((((("Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Uterine Cervical Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Urologic Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Liver Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Hereditary Breast and Ovarian Cancer Syndrome"[Mesh] OR "Early Detection of Cancer"[Mesh]) OR ("Urogenital Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Testicular Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Endometrial Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Vaginal Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Uterine Neoplasms"[Mesh])) OR ("Prostatic Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Ovarian Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Endocrine Gland Neoplasms"[Mesh])) OR ("Breast Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Neoplasms, Germ Cell and Embryonal"[Mesh] OR "Tumor Microenvironment"[Mesh])) OR ("Thyroid Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Pituitary Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Brain Neoplasms"[Mesh]))) OR (Cancer OR hormone-dependent cancer OR neoplasm OR malignant tumor OR colon neoplasms OR tumor OR tumour))		Non-HBM studies Exposure-only studies; no use of effect biomarkers Reviews	No FB1, review, exposure- only, papers in plant or invertebrates
Fumonisin AND nephrotoxicity	(Fumonisin B1 OR FB1 OR 116355-83-0 OR multiple mycotoxins) AND ((Kidney OR renal) AND (failure OR disorder OR impairment OR toxicity) OR (Nephrotoxicity OR nephropathy OR nephrosis OR nephrotic OR nephritis))		Non-HBM studies Exposure-only studies; no use of effect biomarkers Reviews	No FB1, review, exposure- only, papers in plant or invertebrates
Fumonisin AND hepatotoxicity	(Fumonisin B1 OR FB1 OR 116355-83-0 OR multiple mycotoxins) AND ((Hepatotoxicity OR hepatic OR liver) AND (toxicity OR injury OR impairment OR damage))		Non-HBM studies Exposure-only studies; no use of effect biomarkers Reviews	No FB1, review, exposure- only, papers in plant or invertebrates
CRAB search	-human study/epidemiology -tumor-related -biomarkers			

* Search terms for health endpoint defined previously in word table: „HBM4EU. WP14-Final Search Terms (both MeSH and Synonyms) by Health Outcome“

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Table 5: Methodology followed for Deoxynivalenol, outputs generated and the target endpoints

Mycotoxin and health endpoint	Search terms*	Filter: Last 10 years (>2008)	1st and 2nd analysis (human studies and AOP-related studies). Exclusion criteria
Deoxynivalenol AND Immune System AND Allergy	(Deoxynivalenol OR 51481-10-8 OR multiple mycotoxins) AND ("Allergy and Immunology"[Mesh] OR "Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR "Rhinitis, Allergic, Seasonal"[Mesh] OR "Food Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR "Drug Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR "Shellfish Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR Allergy OR Hypersensitive OR respiratory allergy OR gastrointestinal allergy OR multiple chemical sensitivity OR allergic hypersensitivity disease OR contact allergy OR "Immune System"[Mesh] OR "Immune System Diseases"[Mesh] OR Immune system OR autoimmune disease OR cytokines OR white cells OR innate immune system OR adaptive immune system)		No DON, review, exposure only, synthesis only, papers in plant or invertebrates
Deoxynivalenol AND Reproductive	(Deoxynivalenol OR 51481-10-8) AND (reproductive OR puberty OR pregnancy OR infertility OR semen quality OR placenta OR anogenital distance OR hypospadias OR cryptorchidism OR "Reproductive Health"[Mesh] OR "Reproductive Medicine"[Mesh] OR "Reproduction"[Mesh] OR "Reproductive Techniques, Assisted"[Mesh] OR "Infertility"[Mesh])		No DON, review, exposure only, synthesis only, papers in plant or invertebrates
Deoxynivalenol AND Endocrine	(Deoxynivalenol OR 51481-10-8) AND ("Endocrine System"[Mesh] OR "Endocrine Glands"[Mesh] OR "Endocrine System Diseases"[Mesh] OR "Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Gonadal Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Placental Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Pituitary Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Growth Hormone"[Mesh] OR "Thyroid Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Gastrointestinal Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Sex Hormone-Binding Globulin"[Mesh] OR "Adrenocorticotropic Hormone"[Mesh] OR "Adrenal Cortex Hormones"[Mesh] OR Endocrine system OR hypothyroidism OR hyperthyroidism OR adrenal)		No DON, review, exposure only, synthesis only, papers in plant or invertebrates
CRAB search	-human study/epidemiology -tumor related -biomarkers		HBM, quantification in Food, review, risk assessment, DON synthesis

* Search terms for health endpoint defined previously in word table: „HBM4EU. WP14-Final Search Terms (both MeSH and Synonyms) by Health Outcome“

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3.6 Pesticides (excluding organophosphates) (INSERM/CNRS/VITO/UGR)

Background and Justification of health endpoint(s)

An extensive systematic review was conducted for pesticide literature focusing on chlorpyrifos, dimethoate, fipronil, pyrethroid pesticides and glyphosate, in order to identify biomarkers of effect associated with a wide spectrum of human target organs and systems. The purpose was also to identify knowledge gaps and to pinpoint research areas where epidemiological studies have raised concern for potential adverse health effects in humans at population-level exposures, such as developmental neurotoxicity (Fritsche et al. 2018) or childhood leukemia (EFSA Panel on Plant Protection Products and their residues (PPR) et al. 2017).

Specific search strategy, methodology and search terms

This pesticide literature focused on chlorpyrifos, dimethoate, fipronil, pyrethroid pesticides and glyphosate. We used search terms for diverse health endpoints suspected of being affected by pesticide exposure including cardiometabolic health, the immune system, pregnancy and reproductive outcomes, neurodevelopment and cancer (Kim et al., 2017).

Using the pesticide literature search methodology, developed by CNRS, it was possible to create a unique list for each pesticide with the overlaps removed (all the six health endpoints combined) by combining Boolean operators. Afterwards, the search terms were fine-tuned using Yale Mesh Analyser. This tool helps to identify non-relevant terms that are frequently associated with pesticide search (for example, mosquito control, malaria, etc). Once the fine-tuning was completed, the search was rerun by eliminating the non-specific terms that CNRS identified from Yale Mesh Analyser. 30% of the non-specific articles could be removed using this fine-tuning strategy. After the search in PubMed was rerun, it was downloaded as a XML file and converted into an excel spreadsheets using Pubmed2XL software. Finally, the PubMed search was renewed in order to identify articles for a single health endpoint for each pesticide (For example, Chlorpyrifos+ Neurodevelopment, Chlorpyrifos + Reproduction), and multiple health endpoints.

Here, there is a brief part as an example of the search terms for chlorpyrifos pesticide:

system OR adaptive immune system))) NOT (("Metabolic Syndrome"[Mesh] OR "Nutritional and Metabolic Diseases"[Mesh] OR "Metabolic Diseases"[Mesh] OR "Metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Glucose Metabolism Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Acidosis"[Mesh] OR "Metabolome"[Mesh] OR "Metabolomics"[Mesh] OR "Receptor, Insulin"[Mesh] OR "Lipolysis"[Mesh] OR "Gout"[Mesh] OR "Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2"[Mesh] OR "Acidosis, Renal Tubular"[Mesh] OR "Homocysteinemia" [Supplementary Concept] OR "Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptor Gamma Coactivator 1-alpha"[Mesh] OR "Obesity"[Mesh] OR "Pediatric Obesity"[Mesh] OR "Obesity, Abdominal"[Mesh] OR "Abdominal obesity metabolic syndrome" [Supplementary Concept] OR "Cardiovascular System"[Mesh] OR "Cardiovascular Abnormalities"[Mesh] OR "Pregnancy Complications, Cardiovascular"[Mesh] OR "Cardiovascular Diseases"[Mesh] OR adiposity OR body composition OR obesity **Unique articles (search 13.5.19)**

(Chlorpyrifos OR Chlorpyrifos-methyl) AND (((((((((((("Behavior"[Mesh]) OR ("Behavior and Behavior Mechanisms"[Mesh] OR "Reproductive Behavior"[Mesh])) OR "Social Behavior Disorders"[Mesh]) OR ("Child Behavior Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Adolescent Behavior"[Mesh])) OR "Antisocial Personality Disorder"[Mesh]) OR ("Infant Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Spatial Behavior"[Mesh])) OR "Sucking Behavior"[Mesh]) OR ("Sexual Behavior, Animal"[Mesh] OR "Sexual Behavior"[Mesh])) OR ("Paternal Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Maternal Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Impulsive Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Feeding Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Exploratory Behavior"[Mesh])) OR ("Compulsive Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Child Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Behavior, Animal"[Mesh])) OR "Mental Disorders"[Mesh])) OR (Behavior OR Neurobehavior OR Neurodevelopment OR Neurology OR Parkinson OR Alzheimer OR Autism OR Hyperactivity OR ASD OR ADHD OR mental retardation OR IQ loss OR internalizing OR externalizing OR depression OR cognition OR anxiety OR hearing loss OR visual acuity OR social skills)) OR (((((((("Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Uterine Cervical Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Urologic Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Liver Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Hereditary Breast and Ovarian

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Cancer Syndrome"[Mesh] OR "Early Detection of Cancer"[Mesh] OR ("Urogenital Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Testicular Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Endometrial Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Vaginal Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Uterine Neoplasms"[Mesh]) OR ("Prostatic Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Ovarian Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Endocrine Gland Neoplasms"[Mesh])) OR ("Breast Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Neoplasms, Germ Cell and Embryonal"[Mesh] OR "Tumor Microenvironment"[Mesh])) OR ("Thyroid Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Pituitary Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Brain Neoplasms"[Mesh])) OR (Cancer OR hormone-dependent cancer OR neoplasm OR malignant tumor OR Leukemia) OR ("Endocrine System"[Mesh] OR "Endocrine Glands"[Mesh] OR "Endocrine System Diseases"[Mesh] OR "Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Gonadal Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Placental Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Pituitary Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Growth Hormone"[Mesh] OR "Thyroid Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Gastrointestinal Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Sex Hormone-Binding Globulin"[Mesh] OR "Adrenocorticotrophic Hormone"[Mesh] OR "Adrenal Cortex Hormones"[Mesh] OR Endocrine system OR hypothyroidism OR hyperthyroidism OR adrenal OR gonadal steroid hormones) OR ("Allergy and Immunology"[Mesh] OR "Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR "Rhinitis, Allergic, Seasonal"[Mesh] OR "Food Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR "Drug Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR "Shellfish Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR Allergy OR Hypersensitive OR respiratory allergy OR gastrointestinal allergy OR multiple chemical sensitivity OR allergic hypersensitivity disease OR contact allergy OR "Immune System"[Mesh] OR "Immune System Diseases"[Mesh] OR Immune system OR autoimmune disease OR cytokines OR white cells OR innate immune system OR adaptive immune system) OR ("Metabolic Syndrome"[Mesh] OR "Nutritional and Metabolic Diseases"[Mesh] OR "Metabolic Diseases"[Mesh] OR "Metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Glucose Metabolism Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Acidosis"[Mesh] OR "Metabolome"[Mesh] OR "Metabolomics"[Mesh] OR "Receptor, Insulin"[Mesh] OR "Lipolysis"[Mesh] OR "Gout"[Mesh] OR "Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2"[Mesh] OR "Acidosis, Renal Tubular"[Mesh] OR "Homocysteinemia" [Supplementary Concept] OR "Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptor Gamma Coactivator 1-alpha"[Mesh] OR "Obesity"[Mesh] OR "Pediatric Obesity"[Mesh] OR "Obesity, Abdominal"[Mesh] OR "Abdominal obesity metabolic syndrome" [Supplementary Concept] OR "Cardiovascular System"[Mesh] OR "Cardiovascular Abnormalities"[Mesh] OR "Pregnancy Complications, Cardiovascular"[Mesh] OR "Cardiovascular Diseases"[Mesh] OR adiposity OR body composition OR obesity OR abdominal obesity OR waist hip ratio OR adipose tissue OR adipokine OR visceral fat OR body fat OR overweight OR Metabolic OR Metabolic disorder OR Metabolic syndrome OR glucose homeostasis OR Hyperlipidemia OR Dyslipidemia OR hypertriglyceridemia OR HOMA-IR OR insulin resistance OR pancreas OR liver OR kidney) OR (reproductive OR puberty OR pregnancy OR infertility OR semen quality OR placenta OR anogenital distance OR hypospadias OR cryptorchidism OR "Reproductive Health"[Mesh] OR "Reproductive Medicine"[Mesh] OR "Reproduction"[Mesh] OR "Reproductive Techniques, Assisted"[Mesh] OR "Infertility"[Mesh])) -> filter by 10 years & Full text availability -> 260 human & 660 other animals.

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EFSA Panel on Plant Protection Products and their residues (PPR), Ockleford C, Adriaanse P, Berny P, Brock T, Duquesne S, et al. 2017. Investigation into experimental toxicological properties of plant protection products having a potential link to parkinson's disease and childhood leukaemia. EFSA Journal 15:e04691.

Fritsche E, Grandjean P, Crofton KM, et al. Consensus statement on the need for innovation, transition and implementation of developmental neurotoxicity (DNT) testing for regulatory purposes. Toxicol Appl Pharmacol. 2018;354:3–6. doi:10.1016/j.taap.2018.02.004

3.7 Organophosphate Pesticides (EASP)

Background and Justification of health endpoint(s)

An extensive systematic review was conducted for organophosphate pesticides (OPs), with special focus on those authorized for agricultural use in the European Union, in order to identify biomarkers of effect associated with a wide spectrum of human target organs and systems. Pesticides covered included chlorpyrifos, dimethoate, malathion, fosphiazate, parathion, fosetyl, ethoprophos, fenamiphos, pyrimiphos and "organophosphate" pesticides in general.

Some concerns have been raised about human risks associated with organophosphate pesticides exposure, from short-term to chronic disease as as cancer, asthma, and diabetes Kim et al., (2017).

Specific search strategy, methodology and search terms

((((((((((("immune system"[MeSH Terms] OR "autoimmune diseases"[MeSH Terms] OR autoimmune[Text Word] OR "cytokines"[MeSH Terms] OR "cytokines"[MeSH Terms] OR "white cells"[MeSH Terms] AND "immune system"[MeSH

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Terms] OR immune[Text Word] OR "Allergy and Immunology"[Mesh] OR "Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR "Rhinitis, Allergic, Seasonal"[Mesh] OR "Food Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR "Drug Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR "Shellfish Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR "hypersensitivity"[MeSH Terms] OR "allergy and immunology"[MeSH Terms] OR allergy[Text Word] OR "allergy and immunology"[All Fields] OR "hypersensitivity"[MeSH Terms] OR hypersensitive[Text Word] OR "hypersensitivity"[MeSH Terms] OR hypersensitivity[Text Word] OR "allergy and immunology"[MeSH Terms] OR allergy[Text Word] OR "hypersensitivity"[MeSH Terms] OR "allergy and immunology"[MeSH Terms] OR "multiple chemical sensitivity"[MeSH Terms] OR allergic[Text Word] OR "hypersensitivity"[MeSH Terms] OR "dermatitis, allergic contact"[MeSH Terms] OR "allergic contact dermatitis"[All Fields] OR "contact"[All Fields] AND allergy[Text Word] OR "Immune System"[Mesh] OR "Immune System Diseases"[Mesh Terms] AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND (("chlorpyrifos"[MeSH Terms] OR chlorpyrifos[Text Word] OR "dimethoate"[MeSH Terms] OR Dimethoate[Text Word] OR "malathion"[MeSH Terms] OR Malathion[Text Word] OR fosthiazate[Text Word] OR "parathion"[MeSH Terms] OR parathion[Text Word] OR fosetyl[Text Word] OR ethoprophos[Text Word] OR "fenamiphos sulfoxide"[All Fields] OR fenamiphos sulfoxide[Text Word] OR "fenamiphos sulfone"[All Fields] OR fenamiphos sulfone[Text Word] OR fenamiphos[Text Word] OR pyrimiphos[Text Word] OR organophosphate[Text Word] OR "organophosphates"[MeSH Terms] OR organophosphates[Text Word] OR "phosmet"[MeSH Terms] OR phosmet[Text Word] AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("pesticides"[MeSH Terms] OR Pesticides[Text Word] AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) OR (("DNA (Cytosine-5-)-Methyltransferase 1"[Mesh] OR "DNA (Cytosine-5-)-Methyltransferases /genetics"[Mesh] OR "DNA (Cytosine-5-)-Methyltransferases*"[Mesh] OR "Epigenesis, Genetic*"[Mesh] OR "DNA Modification Methylases*"[Mesh] OR "Epigenetic*"[tiab] OR "Epigenomics*"[Mesh] OR "DNA Methylation*"[Mesh] OR "Methylation"[Mesh] OR "DNA Methylation /drug effects*"[Mesh] OR "DNA Methylation /genetics*"[Mesh] OR "Genomic Instability /genetics"[Mesh] OR "CpG Islands /genetics"[Mesh] AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND (("chlorpyrifos"[MeSH Terms] OR chlorpyrifos[Text Word] OR "dimethoate"[MeSH Terms] OR Dimethoate[Text Word] OR "malathion"[MeSH Terms] OR Malathion[Text Word] OR fosthiazate[Text Word] OR "parathion"[MeSH Terms] OR parathion[Text Word] OR fosetyl[Text Word] OR ethoprophos[Text Word] OR "fenamiphos sulfoxide"[All Fields] OR fenamiphos sulfoxide[Text Word] OR "fenamiphos sulfone"[All Fields] OR fenamiphos sulfone[Text Word] OR fenamiphos[Text Word] OR pyrimiphos[Text Word] OR organophosphate[Text Word] OR "organophosphates"[MeSH Terms] OR organophosphates[Text Word] OR "phosmet"[MeSH Terms] OR phosmet[Text Word] AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("pesticides"[MeSH Terms] OR Pesticides[Text Word] AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) OR (("Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Behavior and Behavior Mechanisms"[Mesh] OR "Reproductive Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Social Behavior Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Child Behavior Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Adolescent Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Antisocial Personality Disorder"[Mesh] OR "Infant Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Spatial Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Sucking Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Sexual Behavior, Animal"[Mesh] OR "Sexual Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Paternal Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Maternal Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Impulsive Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Feeding Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Exploratory Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Compulsive Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Child Behavior"[Mesh] OR "Behavior, Animal"[Mesh] OR "Mental Disorders"[Mesh] OR Behavior[Text Word] OR Neurobehavior[Text Word] OR Neurodevelopment[Text Word] OR Neurology[Text Word] OR Parkinson[Text Word] OR Alzheimer[Text Word] OR Autism[Text Word] OR Hyperactivity[Text Word] OR ASD[Text Word] OR ADHD[Text Word] OR internalizing[Text Word] OR externalizing[Text Word] OR depression[Text Word] OR cognition[Text Word] OR anxiety[Text Word] AND neuropsychological[Text Word] OR "mental retardation" OR "IQ loss" OR "hearing loss" OR "visual acuity" OR "social skills" AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("chlorpyrifos"[MeSH Terms] OR chlorpyrifos[Text Word] OR "dimethoate"[MeSH Terms] OR Dimethoate[Text Word] OR "malathion"[MeSH Terms] OR Malathion[Text Word] OR fosthiazate[Text Word] OR "parathion"[MeSH Terms] OR parathion[Text Word] OR fosetyl[Text Word] OR ethoprophos[Text Word] OR "fenamiphos sulfoxide"[All Fields] OR fenamiphos sulfoxide[Text Word] OR "fenamiphos sulfone"[All Fields] OR fenamiphos sulfone[Text Word] OR fenamiphos[Text Word] OR pyrimiphos[Text Word] OR organophosphate[Text Word] OR "organophosphates"[MeSH Terms] OR organophosphates[Text Word] OR "phosmet"[MeSH Terms] OR phosmet[Text Word] AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("pesticides"[MeSH Terms] OR Pesticides[Text Word] AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) OR (("Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR Cancer[Text Word] OR neoplasm[Text Word] OR Leukemia[Text Word] OR "hormone-dependent cancer" OR "malignant tumor" OR "malignant neoplasm" AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("chlorpyrifos"[MeSH Terms] OR chlorpyrifos[Text Word] OR "dimethoate"[MeSH Terms] OR Dimethoate[Text Word] OR "malathion"[MeSH Terms] OR Malathion[Text Word] OR fosthiazate[Text Word] OR "parathion"[MeSH Terms] OR parathion[Text Word] OR fosetyl[Text Word] OR ethoprophos[Text Word] OR "fenamiphos sulfoxide"[All Fields] OR fenamiphos sulfoxide[Text Word] OR "fenamiphos sulfone"[All Fields] OR fenamiphos sulfone[Text Word] OR fenamiphos[Text Word] OR pyrimiphos[Text Word] OR organophosphate[Text Word] OR "organophosphates"[MeSH Terms] OR organophosphates[Text Word] OR "phosmet"[MeSH Terms] OR phosmet[Text Word] AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) OR ((hypothyroidism[Text Word] OR hyperthyroidism[Text Word] OR adrenal[Text Word] OR "Endocrine system" OR "gonadal steroid hormones" OR "Endocrine System"[Mesh] OR "Endocrine Glands"[Mesh] OR "Endocrine System Diseases"[Mesh] OR "Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Gonadal Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Placental Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Pituitary Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Growth Hormone"[Mesh] OR "Thyroid Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Gastrointestinal Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Sex Hormone-Binding Globulin"[Mesh] OR "Adrenocorticotrophic Hormone"[Mesh] OR "Adrenal Cortex Hormones"[Mesh] AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("chlorpyrifos"[MeSH Terms] OR chlorpyrifos[Text Word] OR "dimethoate"[MeSH Terms] OR Dimethoate[Text Word] OR "malathion"[MeSH Terms] OR Malathion[Text Word] OR fosthiazate[Text Word] OR "parathion"[MeSH Terms] OR parathion[Text Word] OR fosetyl[Text Word] OR ethoprophos[Text Word] OR "fenamiphos sulfoxide"[All Fields] OR fenamiphos sulfoxide[Text Word] OR "fenamiphos sulfone"[All Fields] OR fenamiphos sulfone[Text Word] OR fenamiphos[Text Word] OR pyrimiphos[Text Word] OR organophosphate[Text Word] OR "organophosphates"[MeSH

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Terms] OR organophosphates[Text Word] OR "phosmet"[MeSH Terms] OR phosmet[Text Word] AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("pesticides"[MeSH Terms] OR Pesticides[Text Word] AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) OR (("Allergy and Immunology"[Mesh] OR "Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR "Rhinitis, Allergic, Seasonal"[Mesh] OR "Food Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR "Drug Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR "Shellfish Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR "Immune System"[Mesh] OR "Immune System Diseases"[Mesh] OR Allergy[Text Word] OR Hypersensitive[Text Word] OR cytokines[Text Word] OR "Immune system" OR "autoimmune disease" OR "white cells" OR "innate immune system" OR "adaptive immune system" OR "respiratory allergy" OR "gastrointestinal allergy" OR "multiple chemical sensitivity" OR "allergic hypersensitivity disease" OR "contact allergy" AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND (("chlorpyrifos"[MeSH Terms] OR chlorpyrifos[Text Word] OR "dimethoate"[MeSH Terms] OR Dimethoate[Text Word] OR "malathion"[MeSH Terms] OR Malathion[Text Word] OR fosthiazate[Text Word] OR "parathion"[MeSH Terms] OR parathion[Text Word] OR fosetyl[Text Word] OR ethoprophos[Text Word] OR "fenamiphos sulfoxide"[All Fields] OR fenamiphos sulfoxide[Text Word] OR "fenamiphos sulfone"[All Fields] OR fenamiphos sulfone[Text Word] OR fenamiphos[Text Word] OR pyrimiphos[Text Word] OR organophosphate[Text Word] OR "organophosphates"[MeSH Terms] OR organophosphates[Text Word] OR "phosmet"[MeSH Terms] OR phosmet[Text Word] AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("pesticides"[MeSH Terms] OR Pesticides[Text Word] AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND "last 10 years"[PDat])) OR (("Metabolic Syndrome"[Mesh] OR "Nutritional and Metabolic Diseases"[Mesh] OR "Metabolic Diseases"[Mesh] OR "Metabolism"[Mesh] OR "Glucose Metabolism Disorders"[Mesh] OR "Acidosis"[Mesh] OR "Metabolome"[Mesh] OR "Metabolomics"[Mesh] OR "Receptor, Insulin"[Mesh] OR "Lipolysis"[Mesh] OR "Gout"[Mesh] OR "Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2"[Mesh] OR "Acidosis, Renal Tubular"[Mesh] OR "Homocysteinemia"[Supplementary Concept] OR "Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptor Gamma Coactivator 1-alpha"[Mesh] OR "Obesity"[Mesh] OR "Pediatric Obesity"[Mesh] OR "Obesity, Abdominal"[Mesh] OR "Abdominal obesity metabolic syndrome"[Supplementary Concept] OR "Cardiovascular System"[Mesh] OR "Cardiovascular Abnormalities"[Mesh] OR "Pregnancy Complications, Cardiovascular"[Mesh] OR "Cardiovascular Diseases"[Mesh] OR adiposity[Text Word] OR obesity[Text Word] OR adypokine[Text Word] OR overweight[Text Word] OR Metabolic[Text Word] OR Hyperlipidemia[Text Word] OR Dyslipidemia[Text Word] OR hypertriglyceridemia[Text Word] OR HOMA-IR[Text Word] OR pancreas[Text Word] OR liver OR kidney[Text Word] OR "body composition" OR "abdominal obesity" OR "waist hip ratio" OR "adipose tissue" OR "visceral fat" OR "body fat" OR "Metabolic disorder" OR "Metabolic syndrome" OR "glucose homeostasis" OR "insulin resistance" AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND (("chlorpyrifos"[MeSH Terms] OR chlorpyrifos[Text Word] OR "dimethoate"[MeSH Terms] OR Dimethoate[Text Word] OR "malathion"[MeSH Terms] OR Malathion[Text Word] OR fosthiazate[Text Word] OR "parathion"[MeSH Terms] OR parathion[Text Word] OR fosetyl[Text Word] OR ethoprophos[Text Word] OR "fenamiphos sulfoxide"[All Fields] OR fenamiphos sulfoxide[Text Word] OR "fenamiphos sulfone"[All Fields] OR fenamiphos sulfone[Text Word] OR fenamiphos[Text Word] OR pyrimiphos[Text Word] OR organophosphate[Text Word] OR "organophosphates"[MeSH Terms] OR organophosphates[Text Word] OR "phosmet"[MeSH Terms] OR phosmet[Text Word] AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("pesticides"[MeSH Terms] OR Pesticides[Text Word] AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND "last 10 years"[PDat])) OR ((reproductive[Text Word] OR puberty[Text Word] OR pregnancy[Text Word] OR infertility[Text Word] OR placenta[Text Word] OR hypospadias[Text Word] OR cryptorchidism[Text Word] OR "semen quality" OR "anogenital distance" OR "Reproductive Health"[Mesh] OR "Reproductive Medicine"[Mesh] OR "Reproduction"[Mesh] OR "Reproductive Techniques, Assisted"[Mesh] OR "Infertility"[Mesh] AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND (("chlorpyrifos"[MeSH Terms] OR chlorpyrifos[Text Word] OR "dimethoate"[MeSH Terms] OR Dimethoate[Text Word] OR "malathion"[MeSH Terms] OR Malathion[Text Word] OR fosthiazate[Text Word] OR "parathion"[MeSH Terms] OR parathion[Text Word] OR fosetyl[Text Word] OR ethoprophos[Text Word] OR "fenamiphos sulfoxide"[All Fields] OR fenamiphos sulfoxide[Text Word] OR "fenamiphos sulfone"[All Fields] OR fenamiphos sulfone[Text Word] OR fenamiphos[Text Word] OR pyrimiphos[Text Word] OR organophosphate[Text Word] OR "organophosphates"[MeSH Terms] OR organophosphates[Text Word] OR "phosmet"[MeSH Terms] OR phosmet[Text Word] AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("pesticides"[MeSH Terms] OR Pesticides[Text Word] AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) AND "last 10 years"[PDat])) AND "last 10 years"[PDat])) AND "last 10 years"[PDat])) NOT (("Malaria /transmission"[Mesh] OR "Mosquito Control"[Mesh] OR "Insecticide Resistance"[Mesh] OR "Mosquito Vectors"[Mesh] OR "Insect Control /methods"[Mesh] OR "Copepoda /drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Coleoptera /drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Chironomidae /drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Oligochaeta /drug effects"[Mesh] OR "Spiders /drug effects"[Mesh]) AND "last 10 years"[PDat]) AND ("last 10 years"[PDat])) Filters: published in the last 10 years

References

Kim KH, Kabir E, Jahan SA. Exposure to pesticides and the associated human health effects. *Sci Total Environ.* 2017;575:525-535. doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.09.009.

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3.8 UV-Filters (UGR, DTU and RegionH)

Background and justification of health endpoint(s) selected

Benzophenone-3 (BP-3) is an organic ultraviolet (UV) filter widely used in sunscreens, body lotions and make-up, but also in many other applications including plastics and textiles (Morrison et al., 2017). The potential endocrine disrupting properties of BP-3, together with its ubiquitous exposure in human populations have led to an increasing concern about its use (Frederiksen et al., 2017). Therefore, we aimed to conduct a comprehensive review covering all the references related to: i) human sources of exposure; ii) human levels of BP-3 in pregnant women, children, adolescents and adults; iii) human exposure-health associations, including both health endpoints and the effect biomarkers that have been previously implemented. In addition, we also aimed to group all the in vitro and in vivo experimental references conducted in vertebrates (fish and rodents), in order to review the experimental support for specific outcomes, as well as to evaluate potential mechanisms of action and the xenometabolism and tissue disposition of BP-3.

Specific search strategy, methodology and search terms

To achieve our objective, we have used the search terms “Benzophenone-3 OR Benzophenone 3 OR oxybenzone OR 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzophenone”, which provided 784 initial references. After going through all the titles and abstracts, 595 references were excluded. The remaining 189 references were classified and inventoried in a database depending on the type of study as shown in the following flow-chart (Date of search: June 2019).

Figure 4: Classification and inventorisation in a database depending on the type of study

Out of the 38 studies that explored human exposure to benzophenone-3 and health associations, 18 references analysed effect biomarkers were selected.

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References

Frederiksen, H., Nielsen, O., Skakkebaek, N. E., Juul, A., & Andersson, A.-M. (2017). UV filters analyzed by isotope diluted TurboFlow-LC-MS/MS in urine from Danish children and adolescents. *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health*, 220(2 Pt A), 244–253. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2016.08.005>

Morrison, G. C., Bekö, G., Weschler, C. J., Schripp, T., Salthammer, T., Hill, J., ... Frederiksen, H. (2017). Dermal Uptake of Benzophenone-3 from Clothing. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 51(19), 11371–11379. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.7b02623>

3.9 Hexavalent Chromium (INSA, FIOH, INRS)

Clarification

Although hexavalent chromium belongs to the 1st list of prioritised compounds, it remained uncovered in D14.2 due to the lack of teams inside WP14 with previous expertise and interest. Later, INSA partner contacted WP14 leaders expressing their interest to conduct a literature search on this chemical. Therefore, the methods and results for hexavalent chromium are also included in this deliverable, together with the 2nd list of prioritised compounds.

Background

The general population is exposed to hexavalent chromium or Cr(VI) mainly through food ingestion, drinking water and tobacco smoke whereas occupational exposure occurs in several industries, e.g., metallurgic, chemical and aircraft maintenance industries. Although diverse biomonitoring studies have presented data on human exposure to this heavy metal, comparably fewer have reported effect biomarkers results. This section aims at presenting proven and novel effect biomarkers for Cr(VI) analysed in exposed populations, which may be quantitatively linked to adverse health outcomes in humans. These outcomes comprise mainly lung or gastrointestinal tumorigenesis for Cr(VI) exposure.

Description of health endpoint(s)

Once within the cells, Cr(VI) undergoes a process of reduction to Cr(III) [a more thermodynamically stable form of Cr], giving rise to genotoxic metabolites that can form DNA and protein adducts and other type of DNA damage. The most adverse health outcome of Cr(VI) exposure is pulmonary failure, including shortness of breath wheezing, phlegm, productive cough, asthma and ultimately lung cancer (Al Osman et al., 2019; Saha et al., 2011). At a lesser extent, Cr(VI) can cause stomach ulcers (Sasso and Schlosser, 2015), kidney (Kulathunga et al., 2019; Tsai et al., 2017) and liver damage (Patlolla et al., 2009; Yang et al., 2013). A recent systemic analysis and meta-analysis revealed that Cr(VI) does not increase stomach cancer incidence in an occupational context (Suh et al., 2019) but can do so upon oral exposure through contaminated water or food.

Specific search strategy, methodology and search terms

Search was conducted using the terms described in Table 6. The selection of the 50 references, which contained the most complete information on chromium effect biomarkers was first done. Searches were limited to studies with human data and they concentrated mostly on occupational exposures to Cr (VI), which is the form of chromium of concern in terms of health effects. Therefore, the literature searches were conducted focusing on the prioritised health endpoints.

The following table lists MeSH and No-MeSH terms, exclusions and filters used in the chromium literature search.

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Table 6: MeSH and No-MeSH terms, exclusions and filters used in the chromium literature search

Search results	Chromium AND (MeSH Terms OR synonym)	Exclusions	Filters
1st Search 242 references	"chromium"[MeSH Terms] OR "chromium"[All Fields]) AND ("environmental monitoring"[MeSH Terms] OR ("environmental"[All Fields] AND "monitoring"[All Fields]) OR "environmental monitoring"[All Fields] OR "biomonitoring"[All Fields])	"environmental-only studies" "non-human studies" "human exposure-only studies"	"full text"; "10 years"; "human"
2nd Search 196 references	("chromium"[MeSH Terms] OR "chromium"[All Fields]) AND ("biomarkers"[MeSH Terms] OR "biomarkers"[All Fields])		
3rd Search 603 references	("chromium"[MeSH Terms] OR "chromium"[All Fields]) AND ("toxicity"[Subheading] OR "toxicity"[All Fields])		

References

Al Osman, M., Yang, F., and Massey, I.Y. (2019). Exposure routes and health effects of heavy metals on children. *Biomaterials*.

Saha, R., Nandi, R., and Saha, B. (2011). Sources and toxicity of hexavalent chromium. *Journal of Coordination Chemistry* 64, 1782–1806.

Sasso, A.F., and Schlosser, P.M. (2015). An evaluation of in vivo models for toxicokinetics of hexavalent chromium in the stomach. *Toxicol. Appl. Pharmacol.* 287, 293–298.

Kulathunga, M.R.D.L., Ayanka Wijayawardena, M.A., Naidu, R., and Wijeratne, A.W. (2019). Chronic kidney disease of unknown aetiology in Sri Lanka and the exposure to environmental chemicals: a review of literature. *Environ Geochem Health*.

Tsai, T.-L., Kuo, C.-C., Pan, W.-H., Chung, Y.-T., Chen, C.-Y., Wu, T.-N., and Wang, S.-L. (2017). The decline in kidney function with chromium exposure is exacerbated with co-exposure to lead and cadmium. *Kidney International* 92, 710–720.

Patlolla, A.K., Barnes, C., Hackett, D., and Tchounwou, P.B. (2009). Potassium dichromate induced cytotoxicity, genotoxicity and oxidative stress in human liver carcinoma (HepG2) cells. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* 6, 643–653.

Yang, Y., Liu, H., Xiang, X., and Liu, F. (2013). Outline of occupational chromium poisoning in China. *Bull Environ Contam Toxicol* 90, 742–749.

Suh, M., Wikoff, D., Lipworth, L., Goodman, M., Fitch, S., Mittal, L., Ring, C., and Proctor, D. (2019). Hexavalent chromium and stomach cancer: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Crit. Rev. Toxicol.* 1–20.

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4 Results

4.1 Acrylamide (BfR and UGR)

4.1.1 Effect biomarkers for carcinogenesis

Carcinogenesis: 87 abstracts were obtained after a first preselection and removal of 8 duplicates. Two references were added, based on citations in two papers. There were no papers presenting effect markers, which can be recommended for HBM-settings, neither classical nor emerging ones.

Given the lack of available human data, effect biomarkers of DNA damage and oxidative stress related to acrylamide exposure could be tested in HBM studies based on the action mechanisms reported in the literature. Based on recent findings, N7-GAG levels could serve as a biomarker of AA-induced genotoxicity in epidemiological studies (Huang et al., 2015; 2019).

Table 7: References screened and tabulated

References assessed	Classification
1. Al-Lamki, R. S., Lu, W., Manalo, P., Wang, J., Warren, A. Y., Tolkovsky, A. M., Bradley, J. R. (2016). Tubular epithelial cells in renal clear cell carcinoma express high RIPK1/3 and show increased susceptibility to TNF receptor 1-induced necroptosis. <i>Cell Death Dis</i> , 7(6), e2287. doi:10.1038/cddis.2016.184	No association to AA or HBM
2. ANON. (1994). Acrylamide. <i>IARC Monogr Eval Carcinog Risks Hum</i> , 60, 389-433.	
3. ANON. (2004). ROC 14th edition, Acrylamide. <i>Rep Carcinog</i> , 11, lii4-6.	
4. ANON. (2005). NTP-CERHR monograph on the potential human reproductive and developmental effects of acrylamide. <i>Ntp cerhr mon</i> (14), v-I-2, II-xi-166, III-161-174.	No effects on hormonal levels reported, reference outdated
5. Attoff, K., Gliga, A., Lundqvist, J., Norinder, U., & Forsby, A. (2017). Whole genome microarray analysis of neural progenitor C17.2 cells during differentiation and validation of 30 neural mRNA biomarkers for estimation of developmental neurotoxicity. <i>PLoS One</i> , 12(12), e0190066. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0190066	Purpose: in vitro tool for screening of chemically induced neurotoxicity, not applicable for HBM demands
6. Bandarra, S., Fernandes, A. S., Magro, I., Guerreiro, P. S., Pingarilho, M., Churchwell, M. I., . . . Oliveira, N. G. (2013). Mechanistic insights into the cytotoxicity and genotoxicity induced by glycidamide in human mammary cells. <i>Mutagenesis</i> , 28(6), 721-729. doi:10.1093/mutage/get052	No data on effect marker reported
7. Barber, D. S., Stevens, S., & LoPachin, R. M. (2007). Proteomic analysis of rat striatal synaptosomes during acrylamide intoxication at a low dose rate. <i>Toxicol Sci</i> , 100(1), 156-167. doi:10.1093/toxsci/kfm210	Relation between accumulation of AA cysteine adducts and neurotoxicity demonstrated. Not applicable for HBM settings.
8. Bateman, L. A., Nguyen, T. B., Roberts, A. M., Miyamoto, D. K., Ku, W. M., Huffman, T. R., Nomura, D. K. (2017). Chemoproteomics-enabled covalent ligand screen reveals a cysteine hotspot in reticulon 4 that impairs ER morphology and	No association to AA or HBM

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cancer pathogenicity. <i>Chem Commun (Camb)</i> , 53(53), 7234-7237. doi:10.1039/c7cc01480e	
9. Beland, F. A., Olson, G. R., Mendoza, M. C., Marques, M. M., & Doerge, D. R. (2015). Carcinogenicity of glycidamide in B6C3F1 mice and F344/N rats from a two-year drinking water exposure. <i>Food Chem Toxicol</i> , 86, 104-115. doi:10.1016/j.fct.2015.09.017	Important findings in experimental studies (rodent studies). Not relevant for HBM-effect markers. Reference retrieved [Zhivagui, M., et al. (2019)]
10. Bongers, M. L., Hogervorst, J. G., Schouten, L. J., Goldbohm, R. A., Schouten, H. C., & van den Brandt, P. A. (2012). Dietary acrylamide intake and the risk of lymphatic malignancies: the Netherlands Cohort Study on diet and cancer. <i>PLoS One</i> , 7(6), e38016. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0038016	No effect marker reported
11. Brisson, B., Ayotte, P., Normandin, L., Gaudreau, E., Biévenu, J. F., Fennell, T. R., Bouchard, M. (2014). Relation between dietary acrylamide exposure and biomarkers of internal dose in Canadian teenagers. <i>J Expo Sci Environ Epidemiol</i> , 24(2), 215-221. doi:10.1038/jes.2013.34	No effect marker reported
12. Burley, V. J., Greenwood, D. C., Hepworth, S. J., Fraser, L. K., de Kok, T. M., van Breda, S. G., Cade, J. E. (2010). Dietary acrylamide intake and risk of breast cancer in the UK women's cohort. <i>Br J Cancer</i> , 103(11), 1749-1754. doi:10.1038/sj.bjc.6605956	no effect marker reported
13. Carlsson, H., von Stedingk, H., Nilsson, U., & Tornqvist, M. (2014). LC-MS/MS screening strategy for unknown adducts to N-terminal valine in hemoglobin applied to smokers and nonsmokers. <i>Chemical Research in Toxicology</i> , 27(12), 2062-2070. doi:10.1021/tx5002749	Biomarker of exposure
14. Cea, M., Cagnetta, A., Fulciniti, M., Tai, Y. T., Hideshima, T., Chauhan, D., Anderson, K. C. (2012). Targeting NAD+ salvage pathway induces autophagy in multiple myeloma cells via mTORC1 and extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK1/2) inhibition. <i>Blood</i> , 120(17), 3519-3529. doi:10.1182/blood-2012-03-416776	No association to AA or HBM
15. Chen, J. H., & Chou, C. C. (2015). Acrylamide inhibits cellular differentiation of human neuroblastoma and glioblastoma cells. <i>Food Chem Toxicol</i> , 82, 27-35. doi:10.1016/j.fct.2015.04.030	Human in vitro study
16. Chepelev, N. L., Gagne, R., Maynor, T., Kuo, B., Hobbs, C. A., Recio, L., & Yauk, C. L. (2017). Transcriptional profiling of male F344 rats suggests the involvement of calcium signaling in the mode of action of acrylamide-induced thyroid cancer. <i>Food Chem Toxicol</i> , 107(Pt A), 186-200. doi:10.1016/j.fct.2017.06.019	Targeted rat carcinogenicity study, mechanism potentially relevant for humans, no effect markers applicable to HBM
17. Dan, L., Klimenkova, O., Klimiankou, M., Klusman, J. H., van den Heuvel-Eibrink, M. M., Reinhardt, D., Skokowa, J. (2012). The role of sirtuin 2 activation by nicotinamide phosphoribosyltransferase in the aberrant proliferation and survival of myeloid leukemia cells. <i>Haematologica</i> , 97(4), 551-559. doi:10.3324/haematol.2011.055236	No association to AA or HBM
18. Delp, J., Gutbier, S., Klima, S., Hoelting, L., Pinto-Gil, K.,	No association to AA or HBM

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19. DeWoskin, R. S., Sweeney, L. M., Teeguarden, J. G., Sams, R., 2nd, & Vandenberg, J. (2013). Comparison of PBTK model and biomarker based estimates of the internal dosimetry of acrylamide. <i>Food Chem Toxicol</i> , 58, 506-521. doi:10.1016/j.fct.2013.05.008	No association to AA or HBM
20. Dourson, M., Hertzberg, R., Allen, B., Haber, L., Parker, A., Kroner, O., Kohrman, M. (2008). Evidence-based dose-response assessment for thyroid tumorigenesis from acrylamide. <i>Regul Toxicol Pharmacol</i> , 52(3), 264-289. doi:10.1016/j.yrtph.2008.08.004	Traditional biomarkers of effect (hormone levels)
21. Ehlers, A., Lenze, D., Broll, H., Zagon, J., Hummel, M., & Lampen, A. (2013). Dose dependent molecular effects of acrylamide and glycidamide in human cancer cell lines and human primary hepatocytes. <i>Toxicol Lett</i> , 217(2), 111-120. doi:10.1016/j.toxlet.2012.12.017	No relevance for HBM-related markers
22. El-Zakhem Naous, G., Merhi, A., Abboud, M. I., Mroueh, M., & Taleb, R. I. (2018). Carcinogenic and neurotoxic risks of acrylamide consumed through caffeinated beverages among the lebanese population. <i>Chemosphere</i> , 208, 352-357. doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2018.05.185	Study on external exposure, no effect marker reported
23. Erkekoglu, P., & Baydar, T. (2014). Acrylamide neurotoxicity. <i>Nutr Neurosci</i> , 17(2), 49-57. doi:10.1179/1476830513y.0000000065	Review on mechanisms of AA-neurotoxicity, no effect marker reported
24. Feng, C. H., & Lu, C. Y. (2011). Modification of major plasma proteins by acrylamide and glycidamide: Preliminary screening by nano liquid chromatography with tandem mass spectrometry. <i>Anal Chim Acta</i> , 684(1-2), 80-86. doi:10.1016/j.aca.2010.10.042	Exposure markers only
25. Hochstenbach, K., van Leeuwen, D. M., Gmuender, H., Gottschalk, R. W., Lovik, M., Granum, B., van Delft, J. H. (2012). Global gene expression analysis in cord blood reveals gender-specific differences in response to carcinogenic exposure in utero. <i>Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev</i> , 21(10), 1756-1767. doi:10.1158/1055-9965.Epi-12-0304	Mixture Tox approach, no effect marker can be derived from this study
26. Hogervorst, J. G., Baars, B. J., Schouten, L. J., Konings, E. J., Goldbohm, R. A., & van den Brandt, P. A. (2010). The carcinogenicity of dietary acrylamide intake: a comparative discussion of epidemiological and experimental animal research. <i>Crit Rev Toxicol</i> , 40(6), 485-512. doi:10.3109/10408440903524254	No effect marker can be derived from this study
27. Hogervorst, J. G. F., van den Brandt, P. A., Godschalk, R. W. L., van Schooten, F. J., & Schouten, L. J. (2017). Interactions between dietary acrylamide intake and genes for ovarian cancer risk. <i>Eur J Epidemiol</i> , 32(5), 431-441. doi:10.1007/s10654-017-0244-0	Comparison of rat and human data, no effect marker can be derived
28. Huang, C. C., Wu, C. F., Shih, W. C., Luo, Y. S., Chen, M. F., Li, C. M., Wu, K. Y. (2015). Potential Association of Urinary N7-(2-Carbamoyl-2-hydroxyethyl) Guanine with Dietary Acrylamide Intake of Smokers and Nonsmokers. <i>Chemical</i>	Exploratory study, urinary N7-(2-carbamoyl-2-hydroxyethyl) guanine (N7-GAG) as marker of exposure and effect (risk-associated marker), small

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<i>Research in Toxicology</i> , 28(1), 43-50. doi:10.1021/tx500265p	sample size, has to be validated
29. Huang, Y. F., Huang, C. J., Lu, C. A., Chen, M. L., Liou, S. H., Chiang, S. Y., & Wu, K. Y. (2018). Feasibility of using urinary N7-(2-carbamoyl-2-hydroxyethyl) Guanine as a biomarker for acrylamide exposed workers. <i>J Expo Sci Environ Epidemiol</i> , 28(6), 589-598. doi:10.1038/s41370-018-0018-0	Urinary exposure markers
30. Huang, Y. F., Wu, K. Y., Liou, S. H., Uang, S. N., Chen, C. C., Shih, W. C., Chen, M. L. (2011). Biological monitoring for occupational acrylamide exposure from acrylamide production workers. <i>Int Arch Occup Environ Health</i> , 84(3), 303-313. doi:10.1007/s00420-010-0558-7	Urinary exposure markers
31. Jakobsen, L. S., Granby, K., Knudsen, V. K., Nauta, M., Pires, S. M., & Poulsen, M. (2016). Burden of disease of dietary exposure to acrylamide in Denmark. <i>Food Chem Toxicol</i> , 90, 151-159. doi:10.1016/j.fct.2016.01.021	RA, no effect marker
32. Je, Y. (2015). Dietary acrylamide intake and risk of endometrial cancer in prospective cohort studies. <i>Arch Gynecol Obstet</i> , 291(6), 1395-1401. doi:10.1007/s00404-014-3595-8	No association between AA-exposure and endometrial cancer, no effect marker
33. Kim, S. M., Baek, J. M., Lim, S. M., Kim, J. Y., Kim, J., Choi, I., & Cho, K. H. (2015). Modified Lipoproteins by Acrylamide Showed More Atherogenic Properties and Exposure of Acrylamide Induces Acute Hyperlipidemia and Fatty Liver Changes in Zebrafish. <i>Cardiovasc Toxicol</i> , 15(4), 300-308. doi:10.1007/s12012-014-9294-7	Exploratory zebrafish study, MoA to be verified in mammals and humans
34. Komoike, Y., & Matsuoka, M. (2016). Endoplasmic reticulum stress-mediated neuronal apoptosis by acrylamide exposure. <i>Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology</i> , 310, 68-77. doi:10.1016/j.taap.2016.09.005	Mechanistical findings for neurotox in vitro
35. Konings, E. J., Hogervorst, J. G., van Rooij, L., Schouten, L. J., Sizoo, E. A., van Egmond, H. P., . . . van den Brandt, P. A. (2010). Validation of a database on acrylamide for use in epidemiological studies. <i>Eur J Clin Nutr</i> , 64(5), 534-540. doi:10.1038/ejcn.2010.17	AA exposure data
36. Kopanska, M., Muchacka, R., Czech, J., Batoryna, M., & Formicki, G. (2018). Acrylamide toxicity and cholinergic nervous system. <i>J Physiol Pharmacol</i> , 69(6). doi:10.26402/jpp.2018.6.03	MoA based on animal data suggested, cholinergic synapse function and ROS-mediated effects. No effect marker can be concluded.
37. Kotemori, A., Ishihara, J., Zha, L., Liu, R., Sawada, N., Iwasaki, M., Tsugane, S. (2018). Dietary acrylamide intake and risk of breast cancer: The Japan Public Health Center-based Prospective Study. <i>Cancer Sci</i> , 109(3), 843-853. doi:10.1111/cas.13496	No effect markers addressed
38. Kotemori, A., Ishihara, J., Zha, L., Liu, R., Sawada, N., Iwasaki, M., Tsugane, S. (2018). Dietary acrylamide intake and the risk of endometrial or ovarian cancers in Japanese women. <i>Cancer Sci</i> , 109(10), 3316-3325. doi:10.1111/cas.13757	No effect markers addressed
39. Lee, H. R., Cho, S. J., Park, H. J., Kim, K. H., Rhee, D. K., & Pyo, S. (2010). The inhibitory effect of acrylamide on NCAM expression in human neuroblastoma cells: involvement of CK2/Ikaros signaling pathway. <i>Toxicol In Vitro</i> , 24(7), 1946-1952. doi:10.1016/j.tiv.2010.08.004	In vitro study
40. Lee, J. G., Wang, Y. S., & Chou, C. C. (2014). Acrylamide-	In vitro, high concentrations AA,

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induced apoptosis in rat primary astrocytes and human astrocytoma cell lines. <i>Toxicol In Vitro</i> , 28(4), 562-570. doi:10.1016/j.tiv.2014.01.005	
41. Li, D., Wang, P., Liu, Y., Hu, X., & Chen, F. (2016). Metabolism of Acrylamide: Interindividual and Interspecies Differences as Well as the Application as Biomarkers. <i>Curr Drug Metab</i> , 17(4), 317-326.	No effect markers, no relevance for HBM
42. Lin, C. Y., Lin, Y. C., Kuo, H. K., Hwang, J. J., Lin, J. L., Chen, P. C., & Lin, L. Y. (2009). Association among acrylamide, blood insulin, and insulin resistance in adults. <i>Diabetes Care</i> , 32(12), 2206-2211. doi:10.2337/dc09-0309	Initial study (traditional biomarkers-hormonal levels), warrants confirmation.
43. Lin, Y., Lagergren, J., & Lu, Y. (2011). Dietary acrylamide intake and risk of esophageal cancer in a population-based case-control study in Sweden. <i>Int J Cancer</i> , 128(3), 676-681. doi:10.1002/ijc.25608	No effect marker addressed
44. Lineback, D. R., Coughlin, J. R., & Stadler, R. H. (2012). Acrylamide in foods: a review of the science and future considerations. <i>Annu Rev Food Sci Technol</i> , 3, 15-35. doi:10.1146/annurev-food-022811-101114	No effect marker addressed
45. Lipworth, L., Sonderman, J. S., Tarone, R. E., & McLaughlin, J. K. (2012). Review of epidemiologic studies of dietary acrylamide intake and the risk of cancer. <i>Eur J Cancer Prev</i> , 21(4), 375-386. doi:10.1097/CEJ.0b013e3283529b64	No effect marker addressed
46. Lipworth, L., Sonderman, J. S., Tarone, R. E., & McLaughlin, J. K. (2013). Acrylamide: a human cancer risk? <i>Eur J Cancer Prev</i> , 22(2), 193-194. doi:10.1097/CEJ.0b013e328358194d	Letter to the editor
47. Liu, Z. M., Tse, L. A., Chen, B., Wu, S., Chan, D., Kowk, T., Wong, S. Y. (2017). Dietary acrylamide exposure was associated with mild cognition decline among non-smoking Chinese elderly men. <i>Sci Rep</i> , 7(1), 6395. doi:10.1038/s41598-017-06813-9	No effect marker addressed
48. LoPachin, R. M. (2004). The changing view of acrylamide neurotoxicity. <i>Neurotoxicology</i> , 25(4), 617-630. doi:10.1016/j.neuro.2004.01.004	MoA for neurotoxicity, no effect marker applicable to HBM identified, outdated
49. LoPachin, R. M. (2005). Acrylamide neurotoxicity: neurological, morphological and molecular endpoints in animal models. <i>Adv Exp Med Biol</i> , 561, 21-37. doi:10.1007/0-387-24980-x_2	Outdated (molecular markers in experimental studies)
50. Lopachin, R. M., & Decaprio, A. P. (2005). Protein adduct formation as a molecular mechanism in neurotoxicity. <i>Toxicol Sci</i> , 86(2), 214-225. doi:10.1093/toxsci/kfi197	Outdated, for envisaged proteomics results, see Barber et al. (2007)
51. LoPachin, R. M., & Gavin, T. (2012). Molecular mechanism of acrylamide neurotoxicity: lessons learned from organic chemistry. <i>Environ Health Perspect</i> , 120(12), 1650-1657. doi:10.1289/ehp.1205432	Mixture Tox, additivity; Molecular Mechanism of ACR Synaptotoxicity. No HBM-effect markers to be concluded.
52. LoPachin, R. M., & Gavin, T. (2015). Toxic neuropathies: Mechanistic insights based on a chemical perspective. <i>Neurosci Lett</i> , 596, 78-83. doi:10.1016/j.neulet.2014.08.054	No HBM-effect markers addressed
53. Lujan-Barroso, L., Gonzalez, C. A., Slimani, N., Obon-Santacana, M., Ferrari, P., Freisling, H., Duell, E. J. (2014). Dietary intake of acrylamide and esophageal cancer risk in the	RA, No effect markers addressed

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54. Luo, Y. S., Long, T. Y., Shen, L. C., Huang, S. L., Chiang, S. Y., & Wu, K. Y. (2015). Synthesis, characterization and analysis of the acrylamide- and glycidamide-glutathione conjugates. <i>Chem Biol Interact</i> , 237, 38-46. doi:10.1016/j.cbi.2015.05.002	GSH conjugates in rat serum, marker of exposure
55. Lyn-Cook, L. E., Jr., Tareke, E., Word, B., Starlard-Davenport, A., Lyn-Cook, B. D., & Hammons, G. J. (2011). Food contaminant acrylamide increases expression of Cox-2 and nitric oxide synthase in breast epithelial cells. <i>Toxicol Ind Health</i> , 27(1), 11-18. doi:10.1177/0748233710380217	In vitro study, human breast epithelial cells.
56. Motwani, H. V., Frostne, C., & Tornqvist, M. (2017). Parallelogram based approach for in vivo dose estimation of genotoxic metabolites in humans with relevance to reduction of animal experiments. <i>Sci Rep</i> , 7(1), 17560. doi:10.1038/s41598-017-17692-5	Hb adduct levels, marker of exposure
57. Nagata, C., Konishi, K., Tamura, T., Wada, K., Tsuji, M., Hayashi, M., Yasuda, K. (2015). Associations of acrylamide intake with circulating levels of sex hormones and prolactin in premenopausal Japanese women. <i>Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev</i> , 24(1), 249-254. doi:10.1158/1055-9965.Epi-14-0935	No effect marker addressed
58. Obon-Santacana, M., Freisling, H., Peeters, P. H., Lujan-Barroso, L., Ferrari, P., Boutron-Ruault, M. C., Duell, E. J. (2016). Acrylamide and glycidamide hemoglobin adduct levels and endometrial cancer risk: A nested case-control study in nonsmoking postmenopausal women from the EPIC cohort. <i>Int J Cancer</i> , 138(5), 1129-1138. doi:10.1002/ijc.29853	Hb adduct levels, negative findings
59. Obon-Santacana, M., Lujan-Barroso, L., Freisling, H., Cadeau, C., Fagherazzi, G., Boutron-Ruault, M. C., Duell, E. J. (2017). Dietary and lifestyle determinants of acrylamide and glycidamide hemoglobin adducts in non-smoking postmenopausal women from the EPIC cohort. <i>Eur J Nutr</i> , 56(3), 1157-1168. doi:10.1007/s00394-016-1165-5	No effect marker addressed
60. Pan, X., Guo, X., Xiong, F., Cheng, G., Lu, Q., & Yan, H. (2015). Acrylamide increases dopamine levels by affecting dopamine transport and metabolism related genes in the striatal dopaminergic system. <i>Toxicol Lett</i> , 236(1), 60-68. doi:10.1016/j.toxlet.2015.04.017	Mechanism of AA-neurotoxicity in rats, dopamine levels increased bei AA relevance to HBM to be proven
61. Pedersen, G. S., Hogervorst, J. G., Schouten, L. J., Konings, E. J., Goldbohm, R. A., & van den Brandt, P. A. (2010). Dietary acrylamide intake and estrogen and progesterone receptor-defined postmenopausal breast cancer risk. <i>Breast Cancer Res Treat</i> , 122(1), 199-210. doi:10.1007/s10549-009-0642-4	No effect marker addressed
62. Pedreschi, F., Mariotti, M. S., & Granby, K. (2014). Current issues in dietary acrylamide: formation, mitigation and risk assessment. <i>J Sci Food Agric</i> , 94(1), 9-20. doi:10.1002/jsfa.6349	No relevance for HBM-related markers
63. Pelucchi, C., Galeone, C., Negri, E., Bosetti, C., Serraino, D., Montella, M., La Vecchia, C. (2016). Dietary Acrylamide and the Risk of Endometrial Cancer: An Italian Case-Control. <i>Nutr</i>	No effect marker addressed

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64. Pelucchi, C., Rosato, V., Bracci, P. M., Li, D., Neale, R. E., Lucenteforte, E., La Vecchia, C. (2017). Dietary acrylamide and the risk of pancreatic cancer in the International Pancreatic Cancer Case-Control Consortium (PanC4). <i>Ann Oncol</i> , 28(2), 408-414. doi:10.1093/annonc/mdw618	No effect marker addressed
65. Pennisi, M., Malaguarrera, G., Puglisi, V., Vinciguerra, L., Vacante, M., & Malaguarrera, M. (2013). Neurotoxicity of acrylamide in exposed workers. <i>Int J Environ Res Public Health</i> , 10(9), 3843-3854. doi:10.3390/ijerph10093843	No relevance for HBM-related markers
66. Poersch, A., Grassi, M. L., Carvalho, V. P., Lanfredi, G. P., Palma, C. S., Greene, L. J., Faca, V. M. (2016). A proteomic signature of ovarian cancer tumor fluid identified by highthroughput and verified by targeted proteomics. <i>Journal of Proteomics</i> , 145, 226-236. doi:10.1016/j.jprot.2016.05.005	Proteomic analysis of ovarian tumor fluid, tumor diagnosis, no AA-HBM relevance
67. Pruser, K. N., & Flynn, N. E. (2011). Acrylamide in health and disease. <i>Front Biosci (Schol Ed)</i> , 3, 41-51.	No relevance for HBM-related markers
68. Riboldi, B. P., Vinhas, A. M., & Moreira, J. D. (2014). Risks of dietary acrylamide exposure: a systematic review. <i>Food Chem</i> , 157, 310-322. doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2014.02.046	Exposure markers only
69. Rietjens, I., Dussort, P., Gunther, H., Hanlon, P., Honda, H., Mally, A., Eisenbrand, G. (2018). Exposure assessment of process-related contaminants in food by biomarker monitoring. <i>Archives of Toxicology</i> , 92(1), 15-40. doi:10.1007/s00204-017-2143-2	Biomarkers of internal exposure
70. Sams, C., Jones, K., Warren, N., Cocker, J., Bell, S., Bull, P., & Cain, M. (2015). Towards a biological monitoring guidance value for acrylamide. <i>Toxicol Lett</i> , 237(1), 30-37. doi:10.1016/j.toxlet.2015.05.018	Biomarkers of internal exposure
71. Semla, M., Goc, Z., Martiniakova, M., Omelka, R., & Formicki, G. (2017). Acrylamide: a common food toxin related to physiological functions and health. <i>Physiol Res</i> , 66(2), 205-217.	AO's, oxidative stress, Genotoxicity and cytotoxicity, lipid peroxidation and DNA lesions in long term animal studies.
72. Shipp, A., Lawrence, G., Gentry, R., McDonald, T., Bartow, H., Bounds, J., Van Landingham, C. (2006). Acrylamide: review of toxicity data and dose-response analyses for cancer and noncancer effects. <i>Crit Rev Toxicol</i> , 36(6-7), 481-608. doi:10.1080/10408440600851377	Outdated, no effect marker
73. Sisnaiske, J., Hausherr, V., Krug, A. K., Zimmer, B., Hengstler, J. G., Leist, M., & van Thriel, C. (2014). Acrylamide alters neurotransmitter induced calcium responses in murine ESC-derived and primary neurons. <i>Neurotoxicology</i> , 43, 117-126. doi:10.1016/j.neuro.2014.03.010	Reduction of ACh+ glutamate and induction of calcium responses in murine ESCN at high concentrations, not relevant for HBM effect markers
74. Sun, Q., Xu, L., Ma, Y., Qiao, X., & Xu, Z. (2014). Study on a biomimetic enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay method for rapid determination of trace acrylamide in French fries and cracker samples. <i>J Sci Food Agric</i> , 94(1), 102-108. doi:10.1002/jsfa.6204	AA analytics
75. Takahashi, M., Inoue, K., Koyama, N., Yoshida, M., Irie, K., Morikawa, T., Nishikawa, A. (2011). Life stage-related differences in susceptibility to acrylamide-induced neural and testicular toxicity. <i>Archives of Toxicology</i> , 85(9), 1109-1120.	Traditional animal study, no molecular or other effect markers

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76. Tardiff, R. G., Gargas, M. L., Kirman, C. R., Carson, M. L., & Sweeney, L. M. (2010). Estimation of safe dietary intake levels of acrylamide for humans. <i>Food Chem Toxicol</i> , 48(2), 658-667. doi:10.1016/j.fct.2009.11.048	RA based on animal studies and PBTK
77. Tran, N. L., Barraj, L. M., Murphy, M. M., & Bi, X. (2010). Dietary acrylamide exposure and hemoglobin adducts--National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (2003-04). <i>Food Chem Toxicol</i> , 48(11), 3098-3108. doi:10.1016/j.fct.2010.08.003	Hb adducts
78. Vesper, H. W., Sternberg, M. R., Frame, T., & Pfeiffer, C. M. (2013). Among 10 sociodemographic and lifestyle variables, smoking is strongly associated with biomarkers of acrylamide exposure in a representative sample of the U.S. Population. <i>J Nutr</i> , 143(6), 995s-1000s. doi:10.3945/jn.112.173013	Smoking as most relevant factor of biomarker association of AA-exposure
79. Virk-Baker, M. K., Nagy, T. R., Barnes, S., & Groopman, J. (2014). Dietary acrylamide and human cancer: a systematic review of literature. <i>Nutr Cancer</i> , 66(5), 774-790. doi:10.1080/01635581.2014.916323	No effect marker addressed
80. Von Tungeln, L. S., Doerge, D. R., Gamboa da Costa, G., Matilde Marques, M., Witt, W. M., Koturbash, I., Beland, F. A. (2012). Tumorigenicity of acrylamide and its metabolite glycidamide in the neonatal mouse bioassay. <i>Int J Cancer</i> , 131(9), 2008-2015. doi:10.1002/ijc.27493	Murine study, not relevant for HBM-markers
81. Wang, Q., Chen, X., Ren, Y., Chen, Q., Meng, Z., Cheng, J., Zhang, Y. (2017). Toxicokinetics and internal exposure of acrylamide: new insight into comprehensively profiling mercapturic acid metabolites as short-term biomarkers in rats and Chinese adolescents. <i>Archives of Toxicology</i> , 91(5), 2107-2118. doi:10.1007/s00204-016-1869-6	Not relevant to AA-toxicity
82. Wang, Q., Zhang, X., Han, Y., Wang, X., & Gao, G. (2016). M2BP inhibits HIV-1 virion production in a vimentin filaments-dependent manner. <i>Sci Rep</i> , 6, 32736. doi:10.1038/srep32736	Exposure markers only
83. Woehrling, E. K., Hill, E. J., Torr, E. E., & Coleman, M. D. (2011). Single-cell ELISA and flow cytometry as methods for highlighting potential neuronal and astrocytic toxicant specificity. <i>Neurotox Res</i> , 19(3), 472-483. doi:10.1007/s12640-010-9202-2	In vitro study, markers not applicable for HBM settings
84. Xie, J., Terry, K. L., Poole, E. M., Wilson, K. M., Rosner, B. A., Willett, W. C., Tworoger, S. S. (2013). Acrylamide hemoglobin adduct levels and ovarian cancer risk: a nested case-control study. <i>Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev</i> , 22(4), 653-660. doi:10.1158/1055-9965.Epi-12-1387	Hb adducts as exposure markers
85. Yi, C., Xie, K., Song, F., Yu, L., Zhao, X., Li, G., & Yu, S. (2006). The changes of cytoskeletal proteins in plasma of acrylamide-induced rats. <i>Neurochem Res</i> , 31(6), 751-757. doi:10.1007/s11064-006-9079-x	Rat study, findings not relevant for HBM-settings and demands
86. Yu, S. F., Song, F. Y., Yi, C., Yang, X. W., Li, G. Z., Zhang, C. L., Xie, K. Q. (2013). Acrylamide alters cytoskeletal protein level in rat serum. <i>Biomed Environ Sci</i> , 26(11), 926-929. doi:10.3967/bes2013.023	Rat study, findings not relevant for HBM-settings and demands
87. Zhang, L., Gavin, T., Barber, D. S., & LoPachin, R. M. (2011). Role of the Nrf2-ARE pathway in acrylamide neurotoxicity. <i>Toxicol Lett</i> , 205(1), 1-7.	High-dose rat study, potential MIEs, mechanism of neurotox, negative findings

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88. Zhao, M., Wang, F. S. L., Hu, X. S., Chen, F., & Chan, H. M. (2017). Effect of acrylamide-induced neurotoxicity in a primary astrocytes/microglial co-culture model. <i>Toxicol In Vitro</i> , 39, 119-125. doi:10.1016/j.tiv.2016.11.007	Murine in vitro study, results compared to preceeding paper partly opposing
89. Zhivagui, M., Ng, A. W. T., Ardin, M., Churchwell, M. I., Pandey, M., Renard, C., . . . Zavadil, J. (2019). Experimental and pan-cancer genome analyses reveal widespread contribution of acrylamide exposure to carcinogenesis in humans. <i>Genome Res</i> , 29(4), 521-531. doi:10.1101/gr.242453.118	Interesting paper, relevance of results to be proven, no effect markers applicable to HBM-settings can be concluded yet

References included above.

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4.1.2 Effect biomarkers for Reproductive and Developmental adverse effects

Despite the notable number of articles found with the proposed keywords, the majority of them were not selected because they were not useful for the purpose of this search. Below, we summarise some possible biomarkers associated with acrylamide exposure and reproductive and/or developmental adverse effects, based on the final 17 articles selected from the initial search.

- Duan et al., Sci Rep. 2015;5:11562 (doi: 10.1038/srep11562): In this study authors investigated possible acrylamide reproductive toxic effects **in female mice**. Mice were fed an acrylamide-containing diet for 6 weeks. Results showed the following effects of an acrylamide-containing diet. (1) **Ovary weights were reduced** in acrylamide-treated mice and **oocyte developmental competence was also reduced**, as shown by reduced GVBD and polar body extrusion rates. (2) Acrylamide feeding resulted in **aberrant oocyte cytoskeletons**, as shown by an increased abnormal spindle rate and confirmed by disrupted γ -tubulin and p-MAPK localisation. (3) Acrylamide feeding resulted in **oxidative stress and oocyte early stage apoptosis**, as shown by increased ROS levels and p-MAPK expression. (4) Fluorescence intensity analysis showed that **DNA methylation levels were reduced** in acrylamide-treated **oocytes** and **histone methylation** levels were also **altered**, as H3K9me₂, H3K9me₃, H3K4me₂, and H3K27me₃ levels were reduced after acrylamide treatment. (5) After acrylamide feeding, the **litter sizes** of acrylamide-treated **mice** were significantly smaller compared to those of control mice. Thus, these results indicated that acrylamide might affect **oocyte quality** through its effects on cytoskeletal integrity, ROS generation, apoptosis induction, and epigenetic modifications.
- Hogervorst et al., Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev. 2013;22(11):2024-36 (doi: 10.1158/1055-9965.EPI-13-0509): Some epidemiologic studies have observed positive associations between acrylamide intake and sex-hormonal effects. Authors cross-sectionally investigated the relationship between acrylamide intake and **plasma levels of sex hormones and sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG)** among 687 postmenopausal and 1,300 premenopausal controls in nested case-control studies within the Nurses' Health Studies. They did not find associations between acrylamide and sex hormones or SHBG among premenopausal women overall or among never-smokers. Among normal-weight premenopausal women, acrylamide intake was statistically significantly positively associated with luteal total and free estradiol levels. Among postmenopausal women overall and among never-smokers, acrylamide was borderline statistically significantly associated with lower estrone sulfate levels but not with other estrogens, androgens, prolactin, or SHBG. Among normal-weight women, (borderline) statistically significant inverse associations were noted for estrone, free estradiol, estrone sulfate, DHEA, and prolactin, whereas statistically significant positive associations for testosterone and androstenedione were observed among overweight women. Overall, this study did not show conclusive associations between acrylamide intake and sex hormones that would lend unequivocal biologic plausibility to the observed increased risks of endometrial, ovarian, and breast cancer. The association between acrylamide and sex hormones may differ by menopausal and overweight status.
- National Toxicology Program. NTP-CERHR monograph. **2005**; (14):v-I-2, II-xi-166, III-1-74: Occupational exposure to acrylamide can occur through the dermal and inhalation routes. The objectives of this study were to evaluate the metabolism of acrylamide in humans following oral administration, to **compare hemoglobin adduct formation on oral and dermal administration**, to **measure hormone levels**, and to monitor the safety of acrylamide in people exposed under controlled conditions. The primary objectives of this study were to evaluate the conversion of acrylamide to glycidamide in people exposed to acrylamide, and to

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evaluate the extent of uptake following dermal administration. Male volunteers were exposed by administering a low dose of ^{13}C labeled acrylamide orally or dermally, and measuring urinary metabolites or hemoglobin adducts derived from the glycidamide pathway and comparing them to metabolites and hemoglobin adducts derived from acrylamide directly. More specifically, authors intended to evaluate urinary metabolites and hemoglobin adducts, and to measure hormone levels after exposure to a known dose of acrylamide. As a secondary and no less important objective, we intended to monitor the safety of acrylamide in people exposed under controlled conditions. 1,2,3- $^{13}\text{C}_3$ Acrylamide (AM) was administered in an aqueous solution orally (single dose of 0.5, 1.0, or 3.0 mg/kg) or dermally (3 daily doses of 3.0 mg/kg) to sterile **male volunteers**. **Urine samples** (3 mg/kg oral dose) were analysed for **AM metabolites** using **^{13}C NMR spectroscopy**. Approximately 86 % of the urinary metabolites were derived from GSH conjugation, and excreted as N-acetyl-S-(3-amino-3-oxopropyl)cysteine and its S-oxide. Glycidamide, glyceramide, and low levels of N-acetyl-S-(3-amino-2-hydroxy-3-oxopropyl) cysteine were detected in urine. On oral administration, a linear dose response was observed for N-(2-carbamoyl)valine (AAVal) and N-(2-carbamoyl-2-hydroxyethyl)valine (GAVal) in hemoglobin. Dermal administration resulted in lower levels of AAVal and GAVal. Data showed that humans metabolise acrylamide via glycidamide to a lesser extent than rodents, and dermal uptake was approximately 5% of that observed with oral uptake.

- Pedersen et al., Environ Health Perspect. 2012;120(12):1739-45 (doi: 10.1289/ehp.1205327): Authors examined the associations between prenatal exposure to acrylamide and birth outcomes in a prospective European mother-child study. **Hemoglobin (Hb) adducts of acrylamide and its metabolite glycidamide were measured in cord blood** (reflecting cumulated exposure in the last months of pregnancy) from 1,101 singleton pregnant women (Denmark, England, Greece, Norway, Spain during 2006-2010). Maternal diet was estimated through food-frequency questionnaires. Both acrylamide and glycidamide Hb adducts were associated with a statistically significant **reduction in birth weight and head circumference**. The estimated difference in birth weight for infants in the highest versus lowest quartile of acrylamide Hb adduct levels after adjusting for gestational age and country was -132 g (95% CI: -207, -56); the corresponding difference for head circumference was -0.33 cm (95% CI: -0.61, -0.06). Findings were similar in infants of nonsmokers, were consistent across countries, and remained after adjustment for factors associated with reduced birth weight. Maternal consumption of foods rich in acrylamide, such as fried potatoes, was associated with cord blood acrylamide adduct levels and with reduced birth weight. Dietary exposure to acrylamide was associated with reduced birth weight and head circumference. Consumption of specific foods during pregnancy was associated with higher acrylamide exposure in utero.
- Semla et al., Physiol Res. 2017;66(2):205-217: As a low molecular weight compound, acrylamide passes through the placenta in animals and human organism. It was also found in breast milk of women. Thus, it may have the influence on the normal prenatal and early postnatal development of infants. Nonetheless, the data on the risk of the harmful influence of acrylamide on the early development of human has been poorly assessed so far. Interesting studies over acrylamide influence on **embryonic and early postnatal development** of rats were performed by El-Sayyad et al. (2011). Pregnant females rats were orally exposed to high acrylamide doses of 30 mg/kg b.w. from day 6 of gestation until parturition and throughout lactation. The young pups derived from acrylamide-exposed females had **lower body size and weight and lower brain size** in comparison to control animals. They also suffered from muscular dystrophy and ultrastructural changes in cerebral cortex. The reproductive toxicity of acrylamide is also manifested by its influence on **animal male infertility**. According to Scientific Committee on Food (SCF 2002), the impaired fertility may involve affected **sperm**

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count and sperm motility parameters. The increased number of **glycidamide-DNA adducts** and **fragmentation of DNA in germ cells** of male mice exposed chronically to low AA doses was proved by Nixon et al. (2012). This suggests increased risk of DNA lesions in male reproductive material and their possible introduction into zygote. Indeed, it was found that exposure of male rats to acrylamide doses of 19 mg/kg for eight days and next mated to unexposed females led to reduced fertility rates and increased frequency of resorption of embryos (Sakamoto and Hashimoto 1986). Moreover, exposure of rats to acrylamide (dose of 100 ppm) resulted in disrupted mating performance, ejaculatory processes and subsequent transport of sperm (Zenick et al. 1986)".

- De Long et al., Diabetes Metab Syndr Obes. 2017;10:101-109 (doi: 10.2147/DMSO.S95296): This narrative review explores the evidence linking early-life exposure to a suite of chemicals that are common contaminants associated with food production (pesticides; imidacloprid, chlorpyrifos, and glyphosate) and processing (acrylamide), in addition to chemicals ubiquitously found in our household goods (brominated flame retardants) and drinking water (heavy metals) and changes in key pathways important for the development of MetS and obesity. Rodent models have demonstrated that prenatal and perinatal acrylamide exposures result in low birth weight offspring that develop signs of **liver toxicity and lipid accumulation** in postnatal life. Meanwhile, administration of acrylamide to adult rodents has been shown to increase glycogen content and increase hepatocyte size in addition to causing dysglycemia and elevated serum lipid levels. To date, *only three studies have investigated the relationship between prenatal acrylamide exposure and fetal growth outcomes in human populations* but have, for the most part, shown consistent associations between acrylamide exposure and **reduced fetal growth**. The MoBa study found that an increased consumption of acrylamide was associated with **lower birth weight infants**. Similarly, the NewGeneris study found that maternal and cord blood levels of acrylamide and its metabolite glycidamide correlated with a **reduced birth weight and head circumference**. An additional study found that maternal dietary acrylamide and birth weight showed a significant negative correlation and that dietary intake of acrylamide was significantly higher in **small for gestational age (SGA; <10th percentile)** newborns. Taken together, these results suggest that increased **maternal acrylamide consumption during pregnancy may have the potential to impair fetal growth**.
- Nixon et al., PLoS One. 2014;9(5):e94904 (doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0094904): Metabolism of xenobiotics by cytochrome P450s (encoded by the CYP genes) often leads to bio-activation, producing reactive metabolites that interfere with cellular processes and cause DNA damage. In the testes, DNA damage induced by xenobiotics has been associated with impaired spermatogenesis and adverse effects on reproductive health. These authors previously reported that chronic exposure to the reproductive toxicant, acrylamide, produced **high levels of DNA damage in spermatocytes** of Swiss mice. CYP2E1 metabolises acrylamide to glycidamide, which, unlike acrylamide, readily forms adducts with DNA. Thus, they investigated the mechanisms of acrylamide toxicity in mouse male germ cells, examining the **expression of the CYP, CYP2E1**, which metabolises acrylamide. Using Q-PCR and immunohistochemistry, they establish that CYP2E1 is expressed in germ cells, in particular in spermatocytes. Additionally, CYP2E1 gene expression was upregulated in these cells following in vitro acrylamide exposure (1 µM, 18 h). Spermatocytes were isolated and treated with 1 µM acrylamide or 0.5 µM glycidamide for 18 hours and the presence of DNA-adducts was investigated using the comet assay, modified to detect DNA-adducts. Both compounds produced significant levels of DNA damage in spermatocytes, with a greater response observed following glycidamide exposure. A modified comet assay indicated that direct adduction of DNA by glycidamide was a major source of DNA damage. Oxidative stress

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played a small role in eliciting this damage, as a relatively modest effect was found in a comet assay modified to detect oxidative adducts following glycidamide exposure, and glutathione levels remained unchanged following treatment with either compound. Overall results indicate that the male germ line has the capacity to respond to xenobiotic exposure by inducing detoxifying enzymes, and the DNA damage elicited by acrylamide in male germ cells is likely due to the formation of glycidamide adducts.

- Duarte-Salles et al., *Environ Health Perspect.* 2013;121(3):374-9 (doi: 10.1289/ehp.1205396): Author assess associations of prenatal exposure to dietary acrylamide with small for gestational age (SGA) and birth weight. This study included 50,651 women in the Norwegian Mother and Child Cohort Study (MoBa). Acrylamide exposure assessment was based on intake estimates obtained from a food frequency questionnaire (FFQ), which were compared **with hemoglobin (Hb) adduct measurements reflecting acrylamide exposure** in a subset of samples (n = 79). Data on infant birth weight and gestational age were obtained from the Medical Birth Registry of Norway. Multivariable regression was used to estimate associations between prenatal acrylamide and birth outcomes. **Acrylamide intake** during pregnancy was **negatively associated with fetal growth**. When women in the highest quartile of acrylamide intake were compared with women in the lowest quartile, the multivariable-adjusted OR for SGA was 1.11 (95% CI: 1.02, 1.21) and the coefficient for birth weight was -25.7 g (95% CI: -35.9, -15.4). Results were similar after excluding mothers who smoked during pregnancy. Maternal acrylamide- and glycidamide-Hb adduct levels were correlated with estimated dietary acrylamide intakes (Spearman correlations = 0.24; 95% CI: 0.02, 0.44; and 0.48; 95% CI: 0.29, 0.63, respectively).
- Kadawathagedara et al., *Environ Int.* 2018;113:325-334 (doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2018.01.004) (*Follow-up of previous study*): Authors studied the association between prenatal acrylamide exposure and child postnatal growth up to 8 years in the Norwegian Mother and Child Cohort Study (MoBa). In 51,952 mother-child pairs from MoBa, acrylamide intake during pregnancy was estimated by combining maternal food intake with food concentrations of acrylamide. Mothers reported their child's weight and length/height up to 11 times between 6 weeks and 8 years. Weight and height growth trajectories were modelled using Jenss-Bayley's growth model. Logistic regression models were used to study the association with overweight/obese status at 3, 5 and 8 years, as identified using the International Obesity Task Force cut-offs. Linear mixed-effect models were used to explore associations with overall growth. At 3 years, the adjusted odds ratios (95% Confidence Intervals (CI)) of being overweight/obese were 1.10 (1.02, 1.20), 1.12 (1.04, 1.22) and 1.21 (1.11, 1.31) by increasing prenatal acrylamide exposure quartile. Similar dose-response associations were found at 5 and 8 years. Acrylamide intake during pregnancy was associated with higher weight growth velocity in childhood. Children exposed at the highest level had 22 g (95% CI: 8, 37), 57 g (95% CI: 32, 81), and 194 g (95% CI: 110, 278) higher weight at 0.5, 2, and 8 years, respectively, compared to their low exposed peers. Children prenatally exposed to acrylamide in the highest quartile experienced a moderate increase in weight growth velocity during early childhood that resulted in a moderately increased prevalence of overweight/obesity compared to peers in the lowest quartile.
- Gutzkow et al., *Andrology.* 2016;4(6):1102-1114.(doi: 10.1111/andr.12233): Diet-induced obesity is known to impair male reproduction and may aggravate the male reproductive toxicity of the food contaminant acrylamide. Exposure of male mice to acrylamide induces paternally mediated pre- and post-implantation losses because of **spermatozoal toxicity and these effects are potentiated in mice fed a high-fat diet**. Glycidamide - an acrylamide metabolite - is the primary mediator of reproductive effects in males. The mechanisms causing the

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interaction between diet and acrylamide are not clear. However, diet-induced obesity is associated with oxidative stress in male reproductive tissues which might contribute to increased germ cell susceptibility. In this study, authors investigated whether a moderate diet-induced obesity regimen could interfere with glycidamide-induced spermatozoal toxicity and increase oxidative stress. For this purpose, **sperm chromatin integrity, oxidised DNA and protein levels, transcript levels of oxidative stress responsive genes and glycidamide-induced DNA and haemoglobin adducts were analysed in samples from male mice**

exposed to a high-fat diet for 6 weeks in combination with a single glycidamide exposure 7 days prior to sacrifice. They found that glycidamide-induced sperm DNA fragmentation was markedly higher in obese than in lean mice. However, the levels of oxidised DNA and/or protein in blood, liver and testicular tissue was lower in obese than in lean mice.

Accompanying the reduced level of oxidised macromolecules, the transcript levels of several oxidative stress-related genes were altered in the liver and testis from obese mice suggesting induction of an antioxidant response in these animals. The haemoglobin-glycidamide adduct levels were higher in obese than in lean animals, whereas obesity did not seem to increase the level of glycidamide-induced DNA adducts. These findings show that a moderate diet-induced obesity regimen may potentiate glycidamide-induced sperm cells toxicity and suggest that the increase in glycidamide-induced sperm toxicity observed in obese mice does not depend on overt oxidative stress.

- Marchetti et al., *Toxicol Sci.* 2009;107(1):194-205. (doi: 10.1093/toxsci/kfn209): Chromosomal mosaicism in human preimplantation embryos is a common cause of spontaneous abortions, however, our knowledge of its etiology is limited. Authors used multicolor fluorescence in situ hybridisation painting to investigate whether paternally transmitted **chromosomal aberrations** result in mosaicism in mouse two-cell embryos. Paternal exposure to acrylamide produced significant increases in chromosomally defective two-cell embryos, however, the effects were transient primarily affecting the postmeiotic stages of spermatogenesis. Comparisons with previous studies of zygotes demonstrated similar frequencies of chromosomally abnormal zygotes and two-cell embryos suggesting that there was no apparent selection against numerical or structural chromosomal aberrations. However, the majority of affected two-cell embryos were mosaics showing different chromosomal abnormalities in the two blastomeric metaphases. **Analyses of chromosomal aberrations in zygotes and two-cell embryos** showed a tendency for loss of acentric fragments during the first mitotic division of embryogenesis, whereas both dicentrics and translocations apparently underwent proper segregation. These results suggest that embryonic development can proceed up to the end of the second cell cycle of development in the presence of abnormal paternal chromosomes and that even dicentrics can persist through cell division. The high incidence of chromosomally mosaic two-cell embryos suggests that the first mitotic division of embryogenesis is prone to missegregation errors and that paternally transmitted chromosomal abnormalities increase the risk of missegregation leading to embryonic mosaicism.
- Ghanayem et al., *Biol Reprod.* 2010;82(1):96-104. (doi: 10.1095/biolreprod.109.078915): The objective of this study work was to examine the effect of diet-induced obesity on male fertility and the effect of obesity on susceptibility to chemical-induced reproductive toxicity. From 5 to 30 wk of age, genetically intact male C57Bl/6J mice were fed a normal diet or one in which 60% of the kilocalories were from lard. Obese mice exhibited significant differences in the mRNA of several genes within the testes in comparison to lean males. The fertility of male mice was compared through mating with control females. Acrylamide (AA)-induced reproductive toxicity was assessed in obese or lean males treated with water or 25 mg AA kg(-1) day(-1) via gavage for 5 days and then mated to control females. Percent body fat and weight were significantly increased in mice fed a high-fat vs. a normal diet. Obesity resulted in

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significant reduction in plugs and pregnancies of control females partnered with obese vs. lean males. Serum leptin and insulin levels were each approximately 5-fold higher in obese vs. age-matched lean mice. Sperm from obese males exhibited decreased motility and reduced hyperactivated progression vs. lean mice. **Treatment with AA exacerbated male infertility of obese and lean mice; however, this effect was more pronounced in obese mice.** Further, females partnered with AA-treated obese mice exhibited a further decrease in the percentage of live fetuses, whereas the percentage of resorptions increased. This work demonstrated that diet-induced obesity in mice caused a significant reduction in male fertility and exacerbated AA-induced reproductive toxicity and germ cell mutagenicity.

- Myöhänen et al., Basic Clin Pharmacol Toxicol. 2012;110(2):101-12.(doi: 10.1111/j.1742-7843.2011.00761.x): This review deals with the foetal exposure to food and environmental carcinogens in human beings. In particular, human transplacental transfer of the food carcinogens such as acrylamide, glycidamide and nitrosodimethylamine are in focus. Because these carcinogens are genotoxic, the **functional capacity of human placenta to induce DNA adduct formation or metabolise these above mentioned CYP2E1 substrates is of interest in this context.** In this **placental perfusion studies**, it was found that the genotoxic carcinogens acrylamide, its metabolite glycidamide and NDMA (nitrosodimethylamine) were transferred readily through the human placenta in perfusions lasting 4–6hr. The equilibrium in concentrations between the maternal and foetal sides was achieved within 2–3hr. The fast transfer of these compounds was comparable to the transfer of the passively diffusing reference compound, antipyrine. The transfer mechanism of these compounds is thus most probably through the cells by passive diffusion. Human placenta does not protect the foetus from transplacental exposure to NDMA, acrylamide or its more genotoxic metabolite, glycidamide. Results show that there are equal levels of acrylamide or NDMA in maternal and foetal circulation, indicating that fetuses can be exposed to these compounds in levels equal to those of their mother. Results also showed that both acrylamide and NDMA are metabolically activated into genotoxic metabolites by CYP2E. Data demonstrated that CYP2E1 activity necessary for acrylamide activation is very low or non-existent in human placentas. Thus, the perfusion studies and microsomal incubations confirmed that neither acrylamide nor NDMA were metabolised into the reactive glycidamide or methyl diazonium ion in human placentas from non-smoking, non-drinking mothers. **DNA adducts in the placenta may be a biomarker for reproductive toxic effects in pregnancy outcome.** Additionally, **haemoglobin adducts of acrylamide can also be assess in umbilical cord of neonates.** According to these findings, it feasible that risk assessment should involve the assessment of human foetal exposure and placental effects of chemicals.

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In summary, after the literature search, it is possible to consider that there are a few emergent effect markers for acrylamide exposure related with reproductive and developmental adverse effects.

Table 8: Possible biomarkers associated with acrylamide exposure and reproductive and/or developmental adverse effects

References	Possible biomarkers for reproductive and developmental adverse effects
1. Duan X, Wang QC, Chen KL, Zhu CC, Liu J, Sun SC. Acrylamide toxic effects on mouse oocyte quality and fertility in vivo. <i>Sci Rep.</i> 2015;5:11562. doi: 10.1038/srep11562.	Analysis of oocytes to detect ROS levels and p-MAPK expression, DNA methylation levels and histone methylation levels Oocytes from donor to investigate the toxic effects of women exposed to acrylamide (effect on pregnant women and their offspring)
2. Hogervorst JG, Fortner RT, Mucci LA, Tworoger SS, Eliassen AH, Hankinson SE, Wilson KM. Associations between dietary acrylamide intake and plasma sex hormone levels. <i>Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev.</i> 2013;22(11):2024-36. doi: 10.1158/1055-9965.EPI-13-0509.	Hormonal regulation: Sex hormones (luteal total, estrone sulfate, estrone, free estradiol, DHEA, prolactin, testosterone and androstenedione) and sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG) levels. Possible traditional effect biomarkers
3. National Toxicology Program. NTP-CERHR monograph on the potential human reproductive and developmental effects of acrylamide. NTP CERHR MON. 2005;(14):v-I-2, II-xi-166, III-1-74.	Some novel effect biomarkers found: acrylamide and glycidamide react with hemoglobin producing stable adducts: N-(2-carbamoyl-ethyl)valine (AAVal) and N-(2-carbamoyl-2-hydroxyethyl)valine (GAVal) in blood. Also variation in hormone levels after oral versus dermal acrylamide exposure
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5. Semla M, Goc Z, Martiniaková M, Omelka R, Formicki G. Acrylamide: a common food toxin related to physiological functions and health. <i>Physiol Res.</i> 2017;66(2):205-217. Review	Genetic damage in male germ cell: Sperm count and motility parameters. Acrylamide and glycidamide-DNA adducts and fragmentation of DNA in male germ cells.
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15. Ghanayem BI, Bai R, Kissling GE, Travlos G, Hoffler U. Diet-induced obesity in male mice is associated with reduced fertility and potentiation of acrylamide-induced reproductive toxicity. Biol Reprod. 2010;82(1):96-104. doi: 10.1095/biolreprod.109.078915.	Obesity may exacerbate acrylamide induced reproductive toxicity and germ cell mutagenicity (animal study). Emergent biomarkers of effect: Expression of some genes related with obesity (PPARg, Crem, Sh2b1, Dhh, Igf1, and Lepr) in cord blood, in addition to some traditional markers: glucose, cholesterol, triglycerides, insulin, leptin, and hormone levels in blood.
16. Boyle EB, Viet SM, Wright DJ, Merrill LS, Alwis KU, Blount BC, Mortensen ME, Moyer J Jr, Dellarco M. Assessment of Exposure to VOCs among Pregnant	Exposure descriptive study, without any biomarker of effect

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17. Myöhänen K1, Vähäkangas K. Foetal exposure to food and environmental carcinogens in human beings. Basic Clin Pharmacol Toxicol. 2012;110(2):101-12. doi: 10.1111/j.1742-7843.2011.00761.x. Review	DNA adducts as biomarkers of exposure and effect

4.2 Arsenic (VITO, UGR and NIPH)

Classic effect biomarkers

Cancer

Classic molecular or biochemical effect biomarkers were not reported in publications of epidemiological studies.

Metabolic syndrome and diabetes

Some epidemiological evidence for all characteristics of the metabolic syndrome (blood glucose level, dyslipidemia, abdominal obesity, hypertension) was found, as demonstrated by evaluation of classical biomarkers such as fasting blood glucose, blood lipid profile (VDL, HDL, triglycerides), and blood pressure. Both epidemiological and experimental studies found increased as well as decreased adipogenesis (as for instance evaluated by adiponectin and perilipin expression) after As exposure. Oxidative stress (increased reactive oxygen species (ROS) production and decreased antioxidant response) and NO signaling were reported to be involved in effects of As on increased blood pressure.

Regular indicators of insulin resistance and diabetes mellitus such as glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c), oral glucose tolerance testing, and homeostatic model assessment - insulin resistance (HOMA-IR) were used to demonstrate effects of As on (gestational) diabetes in epidemiological studies. Several experimental studies suggest that diabetogenic effects of As are mediated by oxidative stress. Both epidemiological and experimental studies reported either reduction of insulin secretion (caused by disrupted pancreatic β -cell function due to oxidative stress, cytotoxicity, dysfunction of mitochondria and/or insulin transport vesicles, apoptosis, autophagy, inflammation, or pyroptosis) or reduction of insulin sensitivity as primary effect of As. A number of studies that did not find associations between As exposure and diabetes were however also identified (Chen et al., 2010; Munoz et al., 2018; Nizam et al., 2013; Peng, Harlow, & Park, 2015; Steinmaus, Yuan, Liaw, & Smith, 2009; A. Yang et al., 2017; Yuan et al., 2018).

Sex-specific effects of As on lipid profiles, blood glucose, and insulin resistance were identified in *in vivo* studies.

Cardiovascular

Cardiovascular disease is characterised in epidemiological and experimental studies by classical biomarkers such as blood pressure (systolic, diastolic, and pulse pressure), 1st-, 2nd- and 3rd-min Heart Rate Recovery (HRR), carotid intima media thickness (cIMT), and ECG measures (QT interval, JT interval, PR interval, QRS duration, and QT dispersion).

The majority of these studies showed increased blood pressure and cIMT at higher As concentrations obtained in urine, nails and blood. HRR is lower when exposed to As, showing cardiac autonomic dysregulation. Regarding ECG measures, Q-Tc interval prolongation is the most cited effect of As exposure while the influence on other parameters remains unclear.

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Cystatin C, fasting blood glucose, lipid profile (LDLc, HDLc, APOB/A, and triglyceride levels), plasma oxidised LDL (oxLDL) and 8-isoprostane levels are also classical biomarkers related to cardiovascular diseases.

Neurobehaviour

Arsenic has the potential to pass through the placenta barrier and into the developing brain, and cause neurodevelopmental effects. Furthermore, indirect effects e.g. through thyroid hormone disruption are also reported in a few studies.

Classical biomarkers of oxidative stress are associated with As exposure and have been included in one human purely mechanistic study (Ma 2016) and in several of the animal experiments where oxidative stress is associated with neurological toxicity is most (Monaco 2018; Du 2018; Hallauer 2016; Chandravanshi 2014a, 2014b, 2018; Dhar 2018; Zhao 2017; Sun 2015; Liu 2013; Herrera 2013; Han 2011; Rodriguez 2010; Xi 2010), but not all studies (Htway 2019). An association between As exposure and markers of thyroid hormone disruption has been reported in one epidemiological study (Ciarrocca 2012) and in two animal studies report on thyroid markers (Guan 2016; Sun 2015). These studies are in adults, but are included here because of potential relevance to neurodevelopment due to the established association of maternal hyper- and hypo-thyroidism with neurodevelopment.

In addition to these classical biomarkers, markers of susceptibility are also included in a few epidemiological studies examining neurodevelopmental endpoints. These are markers influencing the rate of metabolism and elimination of As, like AS3MT and GSTO polymorphisms (Hsieh 2017), and levels of methyl donors, like folate status and polymorphisms in folate metabolism genes (Mazumdar 2015).

Epidemiological evidence for pathological or functional endpoints exists after developmental exposure to arsenic. However, no studies were identified reporting effects biomarkers in whole blood, plasma or serum combined with adverse neurobehavioral effects in children. On the other hand, a few studies do report blood biomarkers or neurobehavioral effects caused by arsenic exposure (i.e, exposure biomarkers or tests for neurobehavior function and not molecular effect biomarkers).

More specifically, changes in plasma cholinesterase activity (Ali 2010, no neurobehavioral endpoint evaluated), neural tube defects (Amitai 2018), neuropathy (Chakraborti 2016; 2017), birth defects (Wu 2014), hearing loss in children and mice (rLi 2018; 2019; Saunders 2013), and impaired somatosensory evoked potentials in patients (Mochizuki 2016) are reported. In addition, serum pigment epithelium-derived factor (PEDF) is proposed to mitigate arsenic apoptosis in nerve cells in adults (Zhang 2019), since an independent positive correlation between serum PEDF levels and arsenic exposure levels in drinking water was observed.

Further epidemiological evidence for neurobehavioral/neuropsychological and/or fine motor function effects are published: Increased risk for autism spectrum disorders (ASD) (Dickerson 2016; Li 2018), lowered IQ (Hamadani 2012; Kang 2010; Nahar 2015; Wasserman 2014) (some studies indicate more pronounced effects on IQ in girls than in boys), lower IQ and social competence in adolescents (Nahar 2014), lower intellectual test scores (Liu 2016), decreased working memory score (Wassermann 2017), developmental delay and health status in children associated to arsenic methylation capacity (Hsieh 2015; Hsueh 2018), mental retardation and developmental disability (Liu 2010; Parajuli 2013), intellectual disability (McDermott; 2011; 2013; Onicescu 2015), intellectual function (WISC-IV subscale scores, Wasserman 2012), impaired motor function (Parvez 2012), neurotoxicity (immediate recall test, Rocha-Amador 2010), inattention and disturbed impulsivity (Simple Reaction Time Test, Rodriguez-Barranco 2017), decreased cognitive score (Rodrigues 2016), severe intellectual disability (McDermott 2014),

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reduced effectiveness of folic acid supplementation in preventing myelomeningocele (Mazumdar 2016), oppositional, -cognitive problems, -ADHD index and ADHD sub-scales (Roy 2011), lower neonatal behavioral neurological assessment (NBNA) score (Wang 2019), and lower intellectual function in adolescents (modified WISC-IV, e.g. verbal comprehension score) (Wasserman 2019).

Epidemiological evidence for thyroid hormone disruption was found in adults, as evident by changes in urine levels of TH and TSH (Ciarrocca 2012, no neurobehavioral endpoints evaluated).

Global histone modifications in peripheral lymphocytes of adults (altered global levels of H3K18ac, H3K9me2, and H3K36me3) were shown to correlate with both urinary and hair-arsenic levels of the subject; here no neurobehavioral/neurodevelopmental endpoints were evaluated. In addition, modifications of H3K18ac and H3K36me3 were enriched in the promoters of oxidative stress response (OSR) genes in human embryonic kidney (HEK) cells and HaCaT cells (Ma 2017). Arsenic exposure was associated with lower total H3 concentrations in plasma, but only among women with folate deficiency, suggesting that %H3K27me3 in maternal plasma differs between mothers of infants with myelomeningocele and mothers of infants without myelomeningocele, and may be a marker for myelomeningocele risk (Tauheed 2017).

In animal studies, neurobehavioral effects were shown to correlate with effects biomarkers in different brain regions in mice, rats and zebrafish. However, surprisingly, only one study was found measuring a blood biomarker combined with neurobehavioral endpoints, i.e. serum corticosterone combined with behavioral effects in rats (Sobolewski 2019).

Mouse studies report both neurobehavioral effects combined with effect biomarkers in brain regions, and a few studies report neurobehavioral effects without suggesting any MoA or effect biomarkers.

In a recent mouse study, poor sociability and poor social novelty preference was followed by decreased gene expression of serotonin receptor 5B and BDNF in prefrontal cortex (Htway 2019). Protein expression of both PSD-95 and SYP decreased, subsequently causing alteration in synaptic structures, which contributed to arsenite-induced deficits in spatial learning and memory ability in mouse offspring (Zhao 2018). Increased GSH synthesis in hippocampus and increased extracellular glutamate levels, AMPA subunits downregulation, deficient LTP induction, and learning and memory deficits (Morris water maze) were reported in mice offspring by (Nelson-Mora 2019). In adult mice, a deficit in learning and memory was found, abnormal morphologic changes of Purkinje cells were observed in cerebellum, and cerebellar expressions of calmodulin-dependent protein kinase IV (CaMK IV) protein and the thyroid hormone receptor (TR) gene, and TR1 protein were significantly lower. Subchronic exposure to As impaired learning and memory and down-regulating expression of TR1 as well as down-stream CaMK IV. It was also suggested that increased As may be responsible for down-regulation of TR1 and CaMK IV in cerebellum and that the down-regulated TR1 may be involved in As-induced impairment of learning and memory via inhibiting CaMK IV and its down-stream pathway (Guan 2016). In young male offspring mice, arsenic caused changes in perseverative/impulsive behavior (autism-like behavior) (Hill 2016).

As embryonic exposure caused global hypo-acetylation at H3K9 and changes in functional annotation with highly significant representation of Krppel associated box (KRAB) transcription factors in brain samples from exposed pups, and exposure of adult mice impaired spatial and episodic memory, as well as fear conditioning performance (Cronican 2013).

Arsenic produced behavioral impairments in male and female offspring where the most striking effects were on development of gait and other motor responses including acoustic startle, righting reflexes, and forelimb grip (Markowski 2012).

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In adolescent mice exposed to arsenic during gestation, decreased *in vivo* GR binding coincided with significantly decreased mRNA levels and slight reductions of protein of both H-Ras and Raf-1. ERK, a downstream target of Ras and Raf, was decreased in the hippocampus, proposed to be the cause of learning deficiencies (Martinez-Finley, 2012). Perinatal exposure to sodium arsenate on corticosterone receptor (CR)s in C57BL/6J mouse revealed significantly lower levels of these receptors in the nucleus of offspring and showed longer latency to approach a novel object than controls in an object recognition task. In the 8-way radial arm maze, arsenic offspring had a significant increase in the number of entry errors compared to controls (Martinez-Finley 2010).

In adult mice, chronic arsenic exposure led to impaired learning and memory, and upregulation of miRNA-219 expression in hippocampus, and decreased CaMKII; inhibition of miRNA-219 resulted in upregulation of NR2, c-Fos and C-Jun (Wang 2018).

Unknown species (i.e not reported in abstract): As combined with prenatal stress induced reductions in locomotor activity in females and reduced learning deficits in males. As-exposed males showed increased time in the open arms of an elevated plus maze and decreased novel object recognition whereas females did not (Sobolewski 2019). In a fluoxetine intervention animal study, perinatal As exposure induced depressive-like symptoms in a mild learned helplessness task and in the forced swim task (Tyler 2015).

Decrease in mRNA-expression levels of tight junction (TJ) proteins (occludin, claudin, ZO-1, and ZO-2), PI3K, Akt, mTOR, and p62, with concomitant increases in Beclin1, LC3I, LC3II, Atg5, and Atg12 were found. In addition, As significantly downregulated occludin and mTOR protein-expression levels with concomitant upregulation of Beclin1, LC3, and Atg12. Histopathological analysis revealed the irregular arrangement of the Purkinje cell layer, and occurrence of autophagosomes and vacuolated axons in the cerebella. The authors conclude that developmental As exposure significantly alters TJ proteins, resulting an increase in BBB permeability, facilitating the ability of As to cross the BBB and induce autophagy, which might be partly the result of inhibition of the PI3K-Akt-mTOR signaling pathway (Manthari 2018).

In adult male and female mice, developmental arsenic exposure influenced histone 3K4 trimethylation with increased levels in the male dentate gyrus (DG) and frontal cortex (FC) and decreased levels in the female DG. The histone methyltransferase MLL exhibited a similar sex- and region-specific expression profile as H3K4me3 levels, while histone demethylase KDM5B expression trended in the opposite direction. As increased histone 3K9 acetylation levels in the male DG along with histone acetyltransferase (HAT) expression of GCN5 and decreased H3K9ac levels in the male FC along with decreased HAT expression of GCN5 and PCAF. As decreased expression of histone deacetylase enzymes HDAC1 and HDAC2, which were concurrent with increased H3K9ac levels but only in the female DG. Arsenic during development leads to long-lasting changes in histone methylation and acetylation in the adult brain due to aberrant expression of epigenetic machinery (Tyler 2015).

In mice offspring of As treated dams, expression of vesicular glutamate transporter 2 (VGLUT2) and metabotropic glutamate receptors mGluR2 were significantly lower in the striatum indicating that altered glutamatergic neurotransmission may contribute to As-induced developmental neurotoxic effects (Sung 2019). At E14, arsenic mouse exposure significantly decreased expression of both protein and mRNA in brain of glucocorticoid receptor (GR), while hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase enzymes (HSD1) mRNA and proteins decreased, and HSD2 enzyme protein levels were increased but mRNA levels were decreased in the brain. GR placental protein levels were decreased at E18 in the arsenic exposed condition (Caldwell 2015).

In perinatal As exposed mice, differentiated cells was decreased in hippocampus, and altered hippocampal morphology and gene expression (Tyler 2014). Arsenic-exposed litters showed

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neuron necrosis in cerebellum, and the mitosis of granule cells decreased in arsenic-exposed mice. 8-OxodG was formed in neurons of all the layers, especially in the granular layer in cerebellum of arsenic-exposed mice (Ding 2014).

Perinatal exposure to sodium arsenate increased hypothalamic corticotrophin-releasing factor (CRF), altered corticosterone (CORT), decreased hippocampal 11-hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase Type 1 (11-HSD 1), and altered subcellular glucocorticoid receptor (GR) distribution in the hypothalamus. These data indicate HPA axis impairment resulting from perinatal exposure to sodium arsenate (Goggin 2013).

In rats, neurobehavioral effects combined with biomarkers of effects in brain regions were also reported, and in some studies biomarkers of As exposure or neurobehavior effects only after developmental arsenic exposure were reported. Synaptosomal epinephrine, dopamine, and norepinephrine increased levels, and decreased mitochondrial monoamine oxidase activity in cortex, cerebellum, hippocampus, accompanied by offspring behavioral deficits (open field, locomotor activity, explorative behavior, and grip strength) were reported by (Saritha 2019). In a postnatal exposure study, positive correlations between arsenic concentration and deficits in learning and social skills (autism-like behavior) were found, and increases in anxiety-like behavior. Abnormal morphologic changes in the external granular layer and external pyramidal layer were positively correlated with the water arsenic concentration, and higher levels of doublecortin (DCX) expression in the external granular and external pyramidal layers, also evident five weeks after exposure (Zhou 2018). Long-term memory deficits were found, followed by decreased 7-nAChR expression, increased glutamate levels that may produce excitotoxicity, and decreased CAT activity (indicating oxidative stress) in hippocampus (Monaco 2019).

Escape latencies increased at PND42, and short-term and long-term spatial memory ability declined, and additionally CREB protein expression in the cerebral cortex decreased in pups. There were negative correlation between the proteins expression and escape latency periods in pups (Zhu 2017).

Developmental As exposure decreased adult serum corticosterone in both rat genders, and males showed neurobehavioral deficits (increased time in the open arms of elevated plus maze and decreased novel object recognition) (Sobolewski 2019). This is the only study identified measuring serum markers combined with neurobehavioral deficits.

Impaired cognitive abilities combined with altered expression of genes, i.e. reduction of 5-methylcytosine, 5-hydroxymethylcytosine, DNA-methyltransferases, ten-eleven translocations showed that DNA methylation/demethylation were reported by (Du 2018) to be suppressed in brain tissues. The authors conclude that As affects oxidative/anti-oxidative balance, further inhibit ten-eleven translocations (TETs) expression through TCA cycle and alpha-ketoglutarate pathway, and consequently cause DNA methylation/demethylation disruption (Du 2018).

Developmental exposure resulted in behavioral deficits (contextual fear conditioning), increased amyloid precursor protein clearance through higher levels of soluble receptor for advanced glycation products (RAGE), and increased beta-secretase activity, suggesting effects of arsenic exposure on the production of beta-amyloid (1-42) and cerebral amyloid clearance through RAGE that displays behavioral alterations (Nino 2018).

Chronic exposure of As resulted in hippocampal neuronal apoptosis through an up-regulated BMP2/Smad-dependent attenuation of BDNF/TrkB pathway, inducing cognitive deficits (Pandey 2018).

Arsenic exposure affects short-term memory more dramatically in adult animals rather than of young ones, whereas difficulties in long-term memory were detected among young animals

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(Bikashvili 2017). Developmental As exposure showed delay in the development of sensory-motor reflexes, and decreased locomotor activity in adult rats (Gumilar 2016).

Early life As exposure resulted in increased motor activity, linked with increase in the binding of dopamine (D2) receptors, mRNA expression of DAR-D2 receptor gene and expression of tyrosine hydroxylase protein in the corpus striatum. Moreover, arsenic enhanced generation of ROS, and was associated with decrease in the mitochondrial membrane potential, activity of mitochondrial complexes and increased oxidative stress. Disruption in the expression of pro-apoptotic, anti-apoptotic and stress marker proteins was also distinct in the corpus striatum of arsenic exposed rats (Chandravanshi 2015).

Following early life exposure to As, learning and memory ability declined, glutamate levels decreased in cortex, metabotropic glutamate receptors (mGluR5) mRNA and protein expressions in the hippocampus and mGluR5 protein expression in the cortex decreased (Jiang 2015).

Decreased binding of muscarinic-cholinergic receptors in frontal cortex and hippocampus associated with reduced CHRM2 mRNA levels, acetylcholinesterase activity and expression of ChAT and PKC -1. Spatial learning and memory associated with arsenic induced cholinergic alterations (Chandravanshi 2014).

Arsenite exposure significantly prolonged the time of completing reflex response of surface righting, negative geotaxis and cliff avoidance of rat offspring. Neurons and capillaries presented pathological changes and the expression of neural cell adhesion molecules (NCAMs), polysialylation of NCAM (PSA-NCAM), and two polysialyltransferases (STX and PST) were up-regulated in hippocampus of rat offspring (Luo 2013).

In a perinatal As rat exposure study, increase of acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity was noted, in addition to increase in lipid peroxidation (TBARS), where antioxidant administration reversed it. Catalase (CAT) activity in arsenic groups was increased (Herrera 2013).

Chronic arsenite exposure showed that the performance was significantly impaired in the Morris water maze and Y maze tasks. Exposure resulted in abnormal structural changes in the myelin sheaths of nerve fibers and decreases in the terminals of mossy fibers indicating that chronic exposure results in detrimental changes in the neuronal synapses, which may contribute to the arsenite-induced impairment of spatial memory (Jing 2013).

Early life exposure to As showed that 5 methyl-cytosine was significantly higher in the cortex and hippocampus of exposed animals, and DNA hypomethylation was observed the following months in the cortex at high arsenic exposure. Also an increase in the non-methylated form of protein phosphatase 1 (PP1) gene promoter at 2 and 3 months of age in cortex and hippocampus. Additionally, progressive and dose-dependent deficits of fear memory was reported (Martinez 2012).

In adult rats exposed to As for one year, hypoactivity and increases in the striatal dopamine content in addition to up-regulation of mRNA for Mn-SOD and Trx-1 and a down-regulation of DAR-D mRNA levels in the nucleus accumbens were observed. Trx-1 mRNA levels were up-regulated in the cortex, while DAR-D mRNA expression was increased in striatum (Rodriguez 2011).

In offspring, As exposure reduced glutathione (GSH) levels in cortex and hippocampus on PND 42, activity of acetylcholinesterase was significantly higher in hippocampus, also mRNA expression of glutamate decarboxylase (GAD(65) and GAD(67)) in pup's cortex or hippocampus were higher. The level of malondialdehyde in pup's brain on PND 0 and cortex on PND 28 and 42 were significantly higher than in the control group (Xi 2011).

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Developmental neurotoxicity was reported as enhanced generation of ROS associated with decrease in the mitochondrial membrane potential, activity of mitochondrial complexes and increased oxidative stress. Disruption in the expression of pro-apoptotic, anti-apoptotic and stress marker proteins was also distinct in the corpus striatum (Chandravanshi 2018).

In a postnatal As exposure rat study, the multilayered pattern of Calbindin (D28k-CB) +ve cells along with their downregulated expression and low packing density was evident (Dhar 2019), suggesting disturbed cerebellar calcium homeostasis.

In adult rats, Rac1 and Cdc42 expressions increased in cerebellum and in cerebrum, and NaAsO₂ decreased cell viability in primary cultured rat astrocytes, whereas low concentrations (1 µM) NaAsO₂ increased the cell viability. Taken together, the in vivo and in vitro studies indicate that activations of Rac1 and Cdc42 play an important role in arsenic neurotoxicity (apoptosis) in rat cerebellum. No functional endpoints investigated (An 2016).

Developmental exposure resulted in apoptosis in hippocampus neurons including cell shrinkage and nuclear condensation. Nissl bodies were decreased especially in CA1 area in exposed animals. Expression of NGF and GAP-43 mRNA were reduced with increasing As doses (Fan 2015).

The NMDA receptor and the postsynaptic signaling proteins CaMKII, postsynaptic density protein 95 (PSD-95), synaptic Ras GTPase-activating protein (SynGAP) and nuclear activated extracellular-signal regulated kinase (ERK1/2) play important roles in synaptic plasticity, learning and memory. In a 3 months As exposure rat study, decreased protein expression of NR2A, PSD-95 and p-CaMKII in the hippocampus of arsenite-exposed rats was observed. Expression of SynGAP, a negative regulator of Ras-MAPK activity, was increased, decreased p-ERK1/2 activity was found in the hippocampus of arsenite-exposed rats, suggesting that altered expression of NMDA receptor complex and postsynaptic signaling proteins may explain arsenic-induced neurotoxicity (Luo 2012).

Myelin alterations in rat brain and changes in levels of methylated arginines in brain and serum were observed in adult female Wistar rats, accompanied by significant lower levels of dimethyl arginine (Zarazua 2010).

Zebrafish/zebrafish larvae studies show reduced locomotor activity, oxidative stress (H₂O₂), oxidative damage with MDA being augmented. AsIII exposure increased thyroxine levels and modulated gene transcription in HPT axis. In ZF embryos, photomotor response (PMR) hypoactivity and developmental effects (Sun 2016).

In vitro or combined in vitro-animal studies. In rat cerebellar granule neurons (CGN), apoptosis was induced, and intracellular ROS generation increased and the apoptotic effects could be partially reversed by antioxidant N-acetyl-L-cysteine. Neuroglobin (Ngb) protein and mRNA expression were downregulated shortly after NaAsO₂ exposure and then upregulated after a longer time of exposure. Neuroglobin is a vertebrate heme protein regarded as playing neuroprotective role in hypoxia or oxidative stress. Higher Ngb expression was also detected in rat cerebellum, but not in other parts (cerebrum, hippocampus, and midbrain) of the brain exposed to NaAsO₂ for 16 weeks (Liu 2014).

Primary cultured cerebral cortex neurons of mouse embryos were exposed to sodium arsenite exhibited decreased cell survival, and total neurite length was suppressed. The protein level of GluA1, a specific subunit of the AMPA receptor, was significantly decreased, GluA1 expression in neuropeptide Y neurons was found to be up or downregulated dependent of concentrations. GluA1/2 overexpression protected against the deleterious effects of NaAsO₂ on neurite outgrowth (Maekawa 2014).

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In primary cultures of chick cerebellar Bergmann glial cells exposed to As, decrease in glutamate (GLU) transport was observed, and protein kinase A, protein kinase C, and p38 mitogen-activated protein kinase-dependent decreases in K(M) and V(max) concomitant with diminished GLU/aspartate transporter (GLAST) transcription, and increase in nuclear factor (erythroid-derived 2)-like 2 DNA-binding activity correlated with a rise in total glutathione levels (Castro-Coronel 2011).

In chicken, levels of inflammatory-related factor NF- κ B and pro-inflammatory cytokines in brain tissues increased (Sun 2017). Histology changes were revealed in the brain tissues exposure to arsenic, activities of Glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px) and CAT were decreased, whereas the malondialdehyde (MDA) content was increased gradually along with increase in diet-arsenic. The mRNA levels of Hsps and protein expressions of Hsp60 and Hsp70 were up-regulated, altogether indicating oxidative stress (Zhao 2017). In another study, chick embryos exposed to sodium arsenite showed reduction in embryo viability, embryo body weight and extraembryonic vascular area, accompanied by a significantly increased incidence of the failed closure of the caudal end of the neural tube. Choline reversed the decrease in embryo viability and the increase in the failed closure of the caudal end of the neural tube, and also the global DNA methylation by increasing the expressions of DNMT1 and DNMT3a (Song 2013). In chick embryos, neural tube defects (NTDs) were associated with oxidative stress; increased intracellular oxidative species and DNA methylation changes were observed following arsenic exposure, accompanied by a decrease in manganese SOD activity. Furthermore, a significant decrease in DNA methyltransferase (DNMT) 1 and 3a expression was observed in addition to a decrease in S-adenosylmethionine (SAM) and increase in S-adenosylhomocysteine (SAH). This effect resulted in a significant reduction of the SAM/SAH ratio, which may also contribute to DNA hypomethylation (Han 2012).

Table 9: Biomarkers of neurobehavioral effects and of arsenic exposure reported in human, animal and in vitro studies

Biomarker	Tissue/matrix	Neurobehavioral effect	Exposure period	Species	Reference
Cholinesterase activity	Plasma	Not evaluated	Adults	Human	Ali 2010
Pigment epithelium-derived factor (PEDF)	Serum	Not evaluated (only apoptosis)	Adults	Human	Zhang 2019
Arsenic methylation capacity		Developmental delay	Children	Human	Hsieh 2015; Hsueh 2018
TH, TSH	Urine	Not evaluated	Adults (occupational)	Human	Ciarrocca 2012
H3K18ac, H3K9me2, H3K36me3	Lymphocytes	Not evaluated	Adults	Human	Ma 2017
BDNF, serotonin receptor 5B gene expression	Prefrontal cortex	Poor sociability and poor social novelty preference	Developmental exposure	Mice	Htway 2019
Protein expression PSD-95, SYP	Hippocampus	Spatial learning and memory deficits	Developmental exposure	Mice	Zhao 2018
GSH synthesis, extracellular glutamate, AMPA subunits regulation	Hippocampus	LTP, learning and memory deficits	Developmental exposure	Mice	Nelson-Mora 2019
CaMK IV protein, Thyroid hormone receptor (TR) gene and protein	Cerebellum	Learning and memory deficits	Adults	Mice	Guan 2016
Global hypo-acetylation	Brain	Spatial and	Pups (adults)	Mice	Cronican 2013

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Biomarker	Tissue/matrix	Neurobehavioral effect	Exposure period	Species	Reference
at H3K9		episodic memory deficits, fear conditioning performance	behavioral effects)		
Glucocorticoid receptor (GR) mRNA, H-Ras protein, Raf-1 protein, ERK expression.	Hippocampus	Not evaluated	Developmental exposure	Mice	Martinez-Finley 2012
Corticosterone receptor (CR)	Brain	Object recognition task and 8-way radial arm maze performance	Developmental exposure	Mice	Martinez-Finley 2010
miRNA-219, CaMKII	Hippocampus	Learning and memory deficits	Adults	Mice	Wang 2018
Epinephrine, dopamine, norepinephrine, mitochondrial monoamine oxidase	Brain synaptosomes	Open field, locomotor activity, explorative behavior, and grip strength deficits	Developmental exposure	Rat	Saritha 2019
Doublecortin (DCX)	External granular and external pyramidal layers	Learning and social skill deficits (autism-like behavior)	Developmental exposure	Rat	Zhou 2018
7-nAChR expression, Glutamate levels, CAT activity	Hippocampus	Long-term memory deficits	Developmental exposure	Rat	Monaco 2019
CREB protein expression	Cerebral cortex	Escape latency, short-term and long-term spatial memory deficits	Developmental exposure	Rat	Zhu 2017
Corticosterone	Serum	Increased time in the open arms of elevated plus maze and decreased novel object recognition	Developmental exposure	Rat, both genders	Sobolewski 2019
DNA methylation/demethylation (5-methylcytosine, 5-hydroxymethylcytosine, DNA-methyltransferases, ten-eleven translocation genes)	Brain	Impaired cognitive abilities	Developmental exposure	Rat	Du 2018
Soluble receptor for advanced glycation products (RAGE), beta-secretase activity	Brain	Contextual fear conditioning deficits	Developmental exposure	Rat	Nino 2018
BMP2/Smad, BDNF/TrkB	Hippocampus	Cognitive deficits	Developmental exposure	Rat	Pandey 2018
DAR-D2 gene and tyrosine hydroxylase protein, ROS, oxidative stress, pro-apoptotic,	Corpus striatum	Increased motor activity	Developmental exposure	Rat	Chandravanshi 2015

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Biomarker	Tissue/ matrix	Neurobehavioral effect	Exposure period	Species	Reference
anti-apoptotic and stress marker protein expression					
Glutamate levels, metabotropic glutamate receptors (mGluR5) mRNA and protein expressions	Cortex	Learning and memory deficits	Developmental exposure	Rat	Jiang 2015
CHRM2 mRNA levels, acetylcholinesterase activity, expression of ChAT and PKC-1	Frontal cortex, hippocampus	Spatial learning and memory deficits	Developmental exposure	Rat	Chandravanshi 2014
Neural cell adhesion molecules (NCAMs), Polysialylation of NCAM (PSA-NCAM), polysialyltransferases (STX and PST)	Hippocampus	Prolonged time of completing reflex response of surface righting, negative geotaxis and cliff avoidance	Developmental exposure	Rat	Luo 2013
Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity, lipid peroxidation (TBARS), Catalase (CAT) activity	Brain	Not evaluated	Developmental exposure	Rat	Herrera 2013
5 methyl-cytosine, DNA hypomethylation, non-methylated form of protein phosphatase 1 (PP1) gene promoter	Cortex, hippocampus	Fear memory deficits	Developmental exposure	Rat	Martinez 2012
Dopamine content, mRNA for Mn-SOD, Trx-1, DAR-D	Several brain regions	Hypoactivity	Adult	Rat	Rodriguez 2011
Acetylcholinesterase activity, mRNA expression of glutamate decarboxylase (GAD(65) and GAD(67)), malondialdehyde	Hippocampus or cortex	Not evaluated	Developmental exposure		Xi 2011
ROS, mitochondrial membrane potential, activity of mitochondrial complexes, oxidative stress, expression of pro-apoptotic, anti-apoptotic and stress marker proteins	Corpus striatum	Not evaluated	Developmental exposure	Rat	Chandravanshi 2018
Calbindin (D28k-CB)	Brain	Not evaluated	Developmental exposure	Rat	Dhar 2019
Rac1, Cdc42 expression	Cerebellum, cerebrum	Not evaluated	Adult	Rat	An 2016
NGF, GAP-43 mRNA	Hippocampus	Not evaluated	Developmental exposure	Rat	Fan 2015
NR2A, PSD-95, p-CaMKII, SynGAP, p-ERK1/2 activity	Hippocampus	Not evaluated	Developmental exposure	Rat	Luo 2012
Methylated arginines, dimethyl arginine	Serum, brain	Not evaluated	Adult	Rat	Zarazua 2010

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Biomarker	Tissue/matrix	Neurobehavioral effect	Exposure period	Species	Reference
mRNA tight junction (TJ) proteins, PI3K-Akt-mTOR signaling pathway	Cerebellum	Not evaluated	Developmental exposure	Mice	Manthari 2018
H3K4me3, H3K9ac	Dendate gyrus, frontal cortex	Not evaluated	Adult	Mice	Tyler 2015
Vesicular glutamate transporter 2 (VGLUT2), metabotropic glutamate receptors mGluR2, glucocorticoid receptor (GR), hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase enzymes (HSD1) mRNA and proteins, and HSD2 enzyme protein	Striatum	Not evaluated	Developmental exposure	Mice	Caldwell 2015
Morphology, gene expression	Hippocampus	Not evaluated	Developmental exposure	Mice	Tyler 2014
8-OxodG, necrosis	Cerebellum	Not evaluated	Developmental exposure	Mice	Ding 2014
Hypothalamic corticotrophin-releasing factor (CRF), corticosterone (CORT), decreased hippocampal 11-hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase Type 1 (11-HSD 1), subcellular glucocorticoid receptor (GR).	Hypothalamus	Not evaluated	Developmental exposure	Mice	Goggin 2013
Oxidative stress (H2O2), oxidative damage with MDA, thyroxine levels, gene transcription in HPT axis	Brain	Reduced locomotor activity, photomotor response (PMR) hypoactivity	Adult and developmental exposure	Zebrafish/zebrafish larvae studies	Sun 2016
Apoptosis, ROS neuroglobin (Ngb) protein and mRNA	In vitro			In vitro rat cerebellar granule neurons (CGN)	Liu 2014
Neuroglobin (Ngb) protein and mRNA	Cerebellum	Not evaluated		Rat	Liu 2014
Total neurite length, protein level of GluA1	In vitro			Mice primary cultured cerebral cortex neurons	Maekawa 2014
Protein kinase A, protein kinase C, GLU/aspartate transporter (GLAST) transcription, nuclear factor (erythroid-derived 2)-like 2 DNA-binding activity, GSH levels	In vitro			Primary cultures of chick cerebellar Bergmann glial cells	Castro-Coronel 2011
H3K36me3 enriched in promoters of oxidative stress	In vitro				Ma 2017
NF-κB, pro-inflammatory cytokines	Brain	Not evaluated	Developmental exposure	Chicken	Sun 2017

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Biomarker	Tissue/matrix	Neurobehavioral effect	Exposure period	Species	Reference
Histology changes, Glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px), CAT, malondialdehyde (MDA) content, mRNA levels of Hsps and protein expressions of Hsp60 and Hsp70, oxidative stress	Brain	Not evaluated	Developmental exposure	Chicken	Zhao 2017
Embryo viability, closure of the caudal end of the neural tube, global DNA methylation by increasing the expressions of DNMT1 and DNMT3a	Brain	Not evaluated	Developmental exposure	Chick embryos	Song 2013
Neural tube defects, oxidative stress, ROS, DNA methylation, manganese SOD activity, DNA methyltransferase (DNMT) 1 and 3a expression, S-adenosylmethionine (SAM), S-adenosylhomocysteine (SAH)	Brain	Not evaluated	Developmental exposure	Chick embryos	Han 2012

Novel effect biomarkers

Cancer

Experimental studies showed the following novel effect biomarkers:

- High level of As increases oxidative stress which increases the formation of Malondialdehyde (MDA) that lead to carcinogenesis such as cervix cancer.
- β -catenin expression is associated with urothelial carcinoma in arsenic contaminated areas through β -catenin-based signaling pathway.
- As exposure enhances placental growth factor (PIGF) expression through via MTF-1 degradation promoting skin cancer.
- Chronic As exposure negatively correlates with the expression of multidrug resistance-associated protein-1 (MRP1) in lung cancer whose modification in its expression is due probably to depletion of intracellular GSH concentrations.
- Epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) is over-expressed liver cancer exposed to arsenic via EGFR-Ras-Raf-ERK1/2 pathway.

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Several genetic biomarkers for effects of As exposure on cancer were reported:

- miRNAs as miR-425-5p and miR-433 are induced in squamous cell carcinoma (SCC), basal cell carcinoma (BCC) associated with high levels of As. Overexpression of miR-184 might play an oncogenic role in the antiapoptotic and proliferative processes and Knock-down of miR-576-3p promote the proliferation of bladder cancer cells due to increase the expression of cyclin D1. miR-205 development may play a role in tumor progression.
- 8-Hydroxydeoxyguanosine (8-OHdG) is an indicator of oxidative DNA damage and high levels might be indicative of arsenic-induced renal cell carcinoma.
- The un-methylation at -56 and -54 bp CpG sites was significantly associated with the development of invasive As-induced cancer.
- MALAT1 is a non-coding RNA is over-expressed in exposition to As and in hepatocellular carcinomas. HIF-2 α transcriptionally regulates MALAT1, which are involved in malignant transformation of the cells.
- Methylation level of CTNNA2, KLK7, NPY2R, ZNF132, KCNK17 and As exposure were found in urothelial carcinoma through the hypermethylation in genes involved in cell adhesion, proteolysis, transcription regulation, neuronal pathways and ion transport.

Metabolic syndrome and diabetes

Novel molecular or biochemical effect biomarkers were not reported in publications of epidemiological studies. Experimental studies showed the following:

- As causes expression and secretion of C-reactive protein (CRP) *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Elevated CRP levels are produced in response to inflammatory cytokines and are associated with atherosclerosis, hypertension, cardiovascular disease, and insulin resistance.
- Impaired expression and/or function of glucose transporter type 4 (GLUT4), a major mediator of glucose removal from the circulation and a key regulator of glucose homeostasis, was related to elevated fasting blood glucose.
- Some biomarkers for lipid metabolism were found in cultured human hepatocytes and rat liver, such as decreased liver X receptor (LXR) activity (which also regulates GLUT4 activity) and increased cholesteryl ester transfer protein (CETP), lecithin-cholesterol acyltransferase (LCAT), and carnitine O-octanoyltransferase (CROT) levels.
- Induction of C/EBP homologous protein (CHOP10), an endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress response protein, by As and subsequent reduced DNA-binding activity of CCAAT/enhancer-binding protein β (C/EBP β), which regulates the transcription of peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor γ (PPAR γ) and C/EBP α , may be involved in reduction of adipogenesis.
- Activation of RhoA GTPase in rat aorta is related to contractility and may mediate effects of As on blood pressure.
- Nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2 (Nrf2, mediating glucose-triggered insulin signaling involving ROS), insulin promoter factor 1 (PDX1), nuclear factor erythroid 2 like 1 (Nfe2l1), PPAR γ , PTEN-induced kinase 1 (PINK1) signaling, thioredoxin (Trx) system, phospho-PERK (p-PERK), and tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α) may play a role in disrupted β -cell functioning.
- Reduced insulin sensitivity was explained by selenoprotein P (SelPB) release, oxidative stress (disrupted mitochondrial respiration and NAD-dependent deacetylase sirtuin-3 (SirT3) enzyme, forkhead box O3 (FOXO3a), MnSOD, and peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor-gamma coactivator (PGC-1 α) activity which deregulates ROS

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metabolism) and/or disrupted insulin signaling (insulin receptor substrate 1 and 2 (IRS-1, IRS-2), phosphoinositide 3-kinases (PI3K), and protein kinase B (AKT) expression and enhanced adaptive oxidative stress response), or disrupted adipocyte differentiation.

- DNA methylation profiles have been reported to be affected by As exposure both prenatally and later in life. Differential DNA methylation was associated with high LDL in humans, long interspersed nuclear element-1 (LINE-1) hypomethylation, which is involved in many types of disorders, in blood leukocyte DNA was related to elevated blood pressure, and altered methylation patterns of genes with known associations with diabetes, eg. transforming growth factor beta (TGF- β) signaling, centromere protein E (CENPE), proto-oncogene tyrosine-protein kinase Fyn (FYN, an important regulator of whole body metabolism and is known to be associated with insulin sensitivity in mice), ADP-ribosyl cyclase 2 (BST1, a glycosyl-phosphatidylinositol expressed abundantly in pancreatic islet cells), islet cell autoantigen-related protein (PTPRN2, a known autoantigen in insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus) and partitioning defective 3 homolog (PAR3) were found to be associated with As exposure.

In addition, diabetic individuals showed a distinct metabolomic profile associated to iAs metabolites in urine.

Several genetic susceptibility markers for effects of As exposure on metabolic syndrome and diabetes were reported:

- An epidemiological study showed that manganese superoxide dismutase (MnSOD), a scavenger of reactive oxygen species, and 8-oxoguanine DNA glycosylase (OGG1), which is involved in repair of DNA damage resulting from exposure to reactive oxygen, genotypes may be associated with an increased risk of hypertension associated with As exposure. Experimental studies showed increased expression and activity of NADPH oxidase (p22Phox and Nox-4), indicative of increased ROS production in rat aorta.
- Polymorphisms of the endothelin-1 type B receptor (EDNRB) gene were associated with reduced obesity risk in humans. The endothelin system can regulate adiposity by modulating adiponectin activity. A role for EDNRB in aberrant lipid storage and metabolism due to As exposure was confirmed in cultured adipocytes.
- Potential associations between neurogenic locus notch homolog protein 2 (NOTCH2), a disintegrin and metalloproteinase with thrombospondin motifs 9 (ADAMTS9), interleukin 8 receptor, alpha (IL8RA), thioredoxin (TXN), mineralocorticoid receptor or nuclear receptor subfamily 3, group C, member 2 (NR3C2), cytochrome c oxidase subunit 5a (COX5A) and glutamate-cysteine ligase catalytic subunit (GCLC) polymorphism with susceptibility to As effects on type 2 diabetes were reported in epidemiological studies.
- Polymorphisms in creatine kinase (CK) and tumor suppressor candidate 1 (TUSC1) were related to insulin resistance in humans and a polymorphism in calpain-10 gene (CAPN-10), which encodes a protein involved in the secretion and action of insulin, enhanced reduction of insulin secretion by As.
- Arsenite methyltransferase (AS3MT), which is involved in methylation of As to MMA and DMA, genotype was associated with diabetes and insulin resistance in epidemiological studies, dyslipidemia in an epidemiological and experimental study, and higher fat percentage in an experimental study. A glutathione S-transferase omega-1 (GSTO1, responsible for the reduction of As metabolites) polymorphism was associated with susceptibility towards occurrence of metabolic syndrome after As exposure. A polymorphism in methionine synthase (MTR) was associated with insulin resistance. Low MMA% was associated with metabolic syndrome, diabetes and insulin resistance, high

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MMA% and low DMA% with hypertension and insulin resistance, and high DMA% with dyslipidemia and diabetes.

Cardiovascular

Experimental studies reported the novel effect biomarkers associated with the exposure to As listed below:

- 11 CpGs related to cardiovascular disease (CVD), among them 5 specifically related to Low Density Lipoprotein (LDL).
- AS3MT gene single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) A35991G (rs10748835), linked both to low level As exposure and CVD.
- Big endothelin-1 (Big ET-1), an accurate indicator of the degree of activation of the endothelial system, which is higher in hypertensive individuals living in As endemic areas.
- Monocyte chemoattractant protein 1 (MCP1), soluble plasma vascular and cellular adhesion molecules (VCAM-1 and ICAM-1), circulating inflammatory and endothelial function markers.
- Heme oxygenase (HO)-1, which may play a protective role in blood pressure regulation and cardiovascular mortality risk in hypertensive individuals exposed to environmental stressors such as As.
- MicroRNA (miRNA) (miR-126, miR-155, and miR-145), which levels are altered in individuals with CVD, adults and children, via angiogenesis.
- Plasma Asymmetric Dimethylarginine (ADMA), Atherogenic Index of Plasma (AIP) , and Adipocyte Fatty Acid-Binding Protein (FABP4), strongly associated with As exposure.
- Soluble thrombomodulin (sTM) in serum. It is thought to be a specific and stable marker for endothelial damage or dysfunction, which could be an early event of arsenic-related CVD.

Neurobehaviour

Epidemiological studies: No novel molecular biomarker of effect was identified in this literature search.

Experimental studies: Some potential novel biomarkers of effects are studied, but these were generally identified in brain tissue and not in a matrix that is readily accessible in epidemiological studies. A few markers are still mentioned below in relation to AOPs.

Selected biomarker(s) and experimental support

Cancer

Based on epidemiological and experimental studies, the following biomarkers may be of interest:

- miRNAs (miR-425-5p, miR-433, miR-184, miR-576-3p, miR-205): associated with squamous cell carcinoma, basal cell carcinoma, tumors capable of metastasis, poor progression, antiapoptotic and proliferative processes (*epidemiological and experimental evidence*)
- 8-Hydroxydeoxyguanosine (8-OHdG): associated with oxidative DNA damage and renal cell carcinoma (*only epidemiological evidence*)
- Un-methylation at -56 and -54 bp CpG sites: associated with development of invasive As-induced cancer (*only epidemiological evidence*)
- MALAT1 and HIF-2 α : involved in malignant transformation of the cells and hepatocellular carcinomas (*epidemiological and experimental evidence*)
- Malondialdehyde (MDA): associated with oxidative damage and carcinogenesis (*only epidemiological evidence*)

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- β -catenin: associated with tumor site and urothelial carcinoma (*only epidemiological evidence*)
- CTNNA2, KLK7, NPY2R, ZNF132 and KCNK17 methylation: associated with smoking-unrelated urothelial carcinoma (*only epidemiological evidence*)
- Placental growth factor (PIGF): associated with skin cancer (*epidemiological and experimental evidence*)
- MRP1: associated with GSH concentrations and lung cancer (*only epidemiological evidence*)
- Epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR): associated with liver cancer (*epidemiological and experimental evidence*)

Metabolic syndrome and diabetes

No AOPs associated with As as stressor or containing multiple effect biomarkers as KEs and related to the studied health outcomes were identified. Based on epidemiological and experimental studies, the following biomarkers may be of interest:

- CRP levels: associated with atherosclerosis, hypertension, cardiovascular disease and insulin resistance (*only experimental evidence*)
- GLUT4 expression or functioning: associated with blood glucose levels (*only experimental evidence*)
- LXR expression or activity: associated with lipid metabolism and GLUT4 activity (*only experimental evidence*)
- CHOP10, C/EBP β , PPAR γ , and C/EBP α expression or activity (*only experimental evidence*), adiponectin and perilipin expression or secretion (*only experimental evidence*), and EDNRB polymorphisms and activation (*epidemiological and experimental evidence*): associated with adipogenesis and obesity risk
- MnSOD and OGG1 genotypes and activity: associated with oxidative stress, hypertension, and insulin sensitivity (*experimental and/or epidemiological evidence*)
- Disrupted β -cell functioning (PDX1, L-Nfe2l1, PPAR γ , PINK1, Trx system, p-PERK, TNF- α): associated with reduced insulin secretion (*only experimental evidence*)
- Insulin signaling (SelPB, IRS-1, IRS-2, PI3K, AKT, Nrf2, SirT3, PGC-1 α expression or activity): associated with antioxidant response and insulin resistance (*only experimental evidence*)
- Various polymorphisms: associated with insulin secretion, insulin resistance, and diabetes (*only epidemiological evidence*)
- DNA methylome: associated with LDL levels, blood pressure, insulin secretion, insulin resistance, and diabetes (*only epidemiological evidence*)
- Metabolome: associated with diabetes (*only epidemiological evidence*)
- As metabolism (AS3MT, GSTO1, and MTR genotype, MMA% and DMA%): associated with dyslipidemia, fat percentage, hypertension, metabolic syndrome, insulin resistance, and diabetes (*experimental and/or epidemiological evidence*)

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Cardiovascular

According to the experimental and epidemiological evidence, the following biomarkers could be of interest:

- CpGs related to cardiovascular disease (CVD), specifically those related to Low Density Lipoprotein (LDL) (*epidemiological and experimental evidence*).
- AS3MT gene single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) A35991G (rs10748835) (*epidemiological evidence*).
- Big endothelin-1 (Big ET-1), an accurate indicator of the degree of activation of the endothelial system, which is higher in hypertensive individuals living in As endemic areas (*epidemiological evidence*).
- Monocyte chemoattractant protein 1 (MCP1), soluble plasma vascular and cellular adhesion molecules (VCAM-1 and ICAM-1), circulating inflammatory and endothelial function markers (*epidemiological evidence*).
- Heme oxygenase (HO)-1, which may play a protective role in blood pressure regulation and cardiovascular mortality risk in hypertensive individuals exposed to environmental stressors such as As (*epidemiological and experimental evidence*).
- MicroRNA (miRNA) (miR-126, miR-155, and miR-145), which levels are altered in individuals with CVD, adults and children, via angiogenesis (*epidemiological and experimental evidence*).
- Plasma Asymmetric Dimethylarginine (ADMA), Atherogenic Index of Plasma (AIP) , and Adipocyte Fatty Acid-Binding Protein (FABP4), strongly associated with As exposure (*epidemiological and experimental evidence*).
- Soluble thrombomodulin (sTM) in serum. It is thought to be a specific and stable marker for endothelial damage or dysfunction, which could be an early event of arsenic-related CVD (*epidemiological evidence*).

Neurobehaviour

As is identified in AOPwiki as stressors 430 (Arsenite) and 458 (sodium arsenite). The stressors do not appear to be connected to specific AOPs for neurological disease, but to the key events inhibition of IKK complex and oxidative DNA damage, respectively.

Eight AOPs relevant to developmental neurotoxicity have been developed (or outlined only) and seven of them have the similar adverse outcome described as cognitive impairment or learning and memory deficits in children triggered by an exposure to environmental chemicals (Bal-Price and Meek, 2017). The AOPs relevant for developmental neurotoxicity are:

AOP 13: Chronic binding of antagonist to N-methyl-D-aspartate receptors (NMDARs) during brain development induces impairment of learning and memory abilities (endorsed OECD).

AOP 54: Inhibition of Na⁺/I⁻ symporter (NIS) leads to learning and memory impairment (endorsed OECD).

AOP 42: Xenobiotic induced inhibition of thyroperoxidase and subsequent adverse neurodevelopmental outcomes in mammals (endorsed OECD).

AOP 134: Sodium Iodide Symporter (NIS) Inhibition and Subsequent Adverse Neurodevelopmental Outcomes in Mammals (under development).

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AOP 12: Chronic binding of antagonist to N-methyl-D-aspartate receptors (NMDARs) during brain development leads to neurodegeneration with impairment in learning and memory in aging (endorsed OECD).

AOP: The interaction of non-dioxin-like PCBs with ryanodine receptors (RyRs) causes their sensitisation affecting neuronal connectivity that results in behavioral deficits (developmental neurotoxicity) (under development)

AOP: Deficit in learning and cognition induced by exposure to mixture of metals As–Cd–Mn–Pb mediated by multiples MIEs (von Stackelberg et al., 2016, Risk Analysis).

Evaluation of selected novel biomarkers of effect: only a few biomarkers after As exposure can be directly linked to molecular initiating events or key events in the AOPs related to DNT mentioned above. These are changes in thyroid function urine markers in adults exposed to arsenic (Ciarrocca 2012), changes in thyroid hormone receptor gene and protein levels in cerebellum of adult mice with learning and memory deficits (Guan 2016) (AOP 134, 54, 42). In addition, reduced BDNF in prefrontal cortex of developmental As exposed mice exhibiting poor sociability and poor social novelty preference (Htway 2019), and in hippocampus of rats developmentally exposed to As and exhibiting cognitive deficits (Panday 2018) (AOP 12, 13, 54). However, the data would have been strengthened by measuring thyroid disruption markers or BDNF both in blood and brain tissues in the animals showing neurobehavioral deficits, instead of brain tissues only. This weakens the translational value to human studies where blood measurements linked to neurobehavioral deficits are the only option.

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4.3 Lead (NCRWE and MUW)

Summary of biomarkers associated with lead exposure and neurodevelopment based on 24 articles selected from the initial search. Biomarkers in red indicate that causal relationship is likely (in bold red when associations were found in two independent studies).

Authors	Type of work	Candidate markers	Notes
Maternal stress			
Ji et al. 2018	Original work	HDL Maternal stress	Elevated early childhood blood Pb levels increased the risk of ADHD (boys more vulnerable) This risk of ADHD in boys was reduced by one-half if the mother had adequate high-density lipoprotein (HDL) levels or low maternal stress
Tamayo et al. 2017	Original work	NLE	Maternal stress measured as negative life events (NLE) scale derived from the CRYISIS questionnaire. Prenatal stress exposure as a modifier of the well-known neurotoxic effects of prenatal Pb
Tamayo et al. 2016	Original work	Infant saliva cortisol	Increased early gestation Pb exposure alters diurnal cortisol rhythms and the association is modified by infant age, perhaps representing an early maturation of cortisol homeostasis
Epigenetic markers			
Keil and Lein 2016	Review	Gene methylation Dnmt1 LINE-1 methylation p16	Human ESCs (the majority of genes were hypomethylated) DNA (cytosine-5)-methyltransferase 1 (rats only; high Pb doses) In men, patellar lead levels are inversely associated with global LINE-1 DNA methylation levels in blood. Similarly, maternal lead levels are inversely correlated with genomic DNA methylation of the LINE-1 element in umbilical cord blood Adult men exposed to lead, those with the highest blood lead levels had complete DNA methylation of the p16 gene, a tumor suppressor gene involved in neurodegeneration. In contrast, men with lower lead levels had partial to no DNA methylation of the p16 gene
Conclusion: lead-induced changes in DNA methylation may play a role in developmental neurodevelopmental disorders, possibly by altering genes important for calcium ion import, neuron projection development, actin cytoskeletal arrangement, and neurodegeneration			
Wu et al. 2017	Original work	CLEC11A DNHD1	Prenatal low-level Pb exposure was associated with newborn DNA methylation, particularly in female infants. CpG cg10773601 showed an epigenome-wide significant negative association with prenatal Pb exposure annotated to C-Type Lectin Domain Family 11, Member A (CLEC11A) , which functions as a growth factor for primitive hematopoietic progenitor cells One CpG (cg24637308), which showed a strong negative association with prenatal Pb exposure among female infants was annotated to Dynein Heavy Chain Domain 1 gene (DNHD1) which is highly expressed in human brain
Gene Variants/SNPs			
Liu et al. 2015	Original work	DRD2	No significant association between dopamine receptor-2 (DRD2) Taq IA polymorphism and neurodevelopment of children exposed to Pb
Pilsner et al. 2010	Original work	MTHFR	Methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase (MTHFR) gene is important for folate metabolism. We did not observe significant MTHFR genotype x LEAD interactions with respect to any of the subject biomarkers of LEAD exposure. The maternal MTHFR 677T allele is an independent predictor of poorer child neurodevelopment at 24 mo
Wagner et al. 2017	Original work	SPP1	SPP1 (secreted phosphoprotein 1) is a novel direct NRF2 target gene. SNP rs12641001 significantly associated with the Cognitive Development Index (CDI). Findings reveal that Pb induces an NRF2-dependent transcriptional response in neural stem cells and identified SPP1 up-regulation as a potential novel mechanism linking Pb exposure with neural stem cell function and neurodevelopment in children
Wright et al. 2003	Original work	APOE	Apolipoprotein E (APOE) regulates cholesterol and fatty acid metabolism, and may mediate synaptogenesis during neurodevelopment. Subjects with the E4 isoform of APOE may have advantages over those with the E2 or E3 isoforms with respect to early life neuronal/brain development
BDNF			
Zhou et al. 2019	Original work	BDNF	Pb levels were significantly negatively associated with serum BDNF concentrations in all the subjects and boys but not in girls
Ren et al. 2016	Original work	BDNF	Prenatal Pb exposure results in poor neonatal neurobehavioral development. Cord blood BDNF was negatively correlated with neonatal neurodevelopment, may serve as a useful biomarker

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Screenings

Wang et al. 2017	Original work	Genome-wide gene-environment interaction study (GWIS)	
		UNC5D	UNC5D (Unc-5 Netrin Receptor D) is a receptor for the netrin NTN4 that promotes neuronal cell survival. Two SNPs: rs9642758 and rs10503970
		SLC1A5	SLC1A5 (encodes ASCT2) transports neurotransmitter glutamate; is involved in synaptic function, neuronal development, and excitotoxicity
		CHUK, TWIST1	Five hub genes (25 direct interactions), including two genes from GWIS (CHUK and TWIST1) and three genes from in vitro assays (PRKCD, HSPA5, and XBP1). Both CHUK and TWIST1 play important roles in early neurogenesis
		PRKCD, HSPA5, XBP1	As a biological and physiological analogue to Ca ²⁺ , Pb can directly activate Ca²⁺-dependent PKCs (α, β1, β2, and γ). HSPA5 and XBP1 are key genes in ER stress pathways
Zimmer et al. 2012	Original work	Tubb3, Syp, App, Mapt, Nrn1, Prnp	Embryonic stem cells: short exposure to Pb during the final differentiation phase, disturbed neuronal maturation indicated by lower expression of Tubb3, Syp, App, Mapt, Nrn1 and Prnp

Immune factors

Srivivasai et al. 2013	Original work	CRP	Pb exposure is associated with adverse changes in inflammatory marker C reactive protein (CRP) and SBP. GST polymorphisms are among the genetic determinants related to lead-induced inflammatory
Pajewska-Szmyt et al.	Review	Cytokines	Cytokines are important immunomodulators; toxicants cause stimulation or suppression of this compounds

Metallome

Shah-Kulkarni et al. 2017	Original work	Fe	Detrimental effect of prenatal Pb exposure in late pregnancy on cognitive development up to 36 months in children of mothers having less dietary iron intake during pregnancy . Importance to reduce prenatal Pb exposure and have adequate iron intake for better neurodevelopment in children
Ettinger et al. 2009	Original work	Ca	Calcium supplementation associated with modest reductions in blood Pb when administered during pregnancy, maybe an important secondary prevention effort to reduce circulating maternal Pb and, consequently,
Liu et al. 2014	Original work	Ca, Fe, Zn	"Drinking milk and supplements of Ca, Fe, or Zn are protective factors of high BLLs"
Liu et al. 2018	Original work	Cu	Interaction effect between second trimester copper and lead exposures for cognition at 24 months. Significant positive associations between second trimester exposure to copper and Bayley Scales of Infant and Toddler Development cognition score at 24 months, and cognitive trajectories across 6-24
Modabbernia et al. 2017	Original work	Mn, Cu	Tooth-matrix biomarker provide support for the role of metal exposure during critical neurodevelopmental periods in psychosis
Mora et al. 2015	Original work	Mn, Cu	Higher prenatal dentine Mn levels associated with poorer visuospatial memory outcomes at 9 years and worse cognitive scores at 7 and 10.5 years in children with higher prenatal Pb levels
Parajuli et al. 2013	Original work	Zn	Cord blood levels of Pb and As, but not Zn , showed significant inverse association with the neurodevelopment of newborns.
Yasuda et al. 2013	Original work	Zn, Mg	Infant zinc- and magnesium-deficiency and/or toxic metal burdens may epigenetically play principal roles as environmental factors in autistic disorders

Vitamins

Li et al. 2011	Original work	Vit A, E, C	Data suggested "there may be certain interaction between antioxidant vitamin A, E, C and heavy metals lead, cadmium, mercury"
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Classic effect biomarkers/Neurodevelopment: Full-scale IQ (Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children), Mental Development Index (Bayley Development Test), General Cognitive Index (McCarty test)

Classic effect biomarkers/Lead exposure: Iron status (Hb, Hct, sTFR (serum transferrin receptor), SF (serum ferritin) together with CRP (C-reactive protein) to control for inflammation); plasma/serum calcium.

Novel effect biomarkers: BDNF and epigenetic markers: LINE-1-methylation, p16, CLC11A, DNHD1

Selected biomarker(s) and experimental support

At this stage of the literature search, we suggest classical biomarkers (iron/calcium status) together with LINE-1-methylation (and other epigenetic markers) as a promising set of biomarkers. The interaction of iron and lead is well-established. It is based on both animal and human studies confirming that iron deficiency and iron deficiency anemia increase intestinal lead absorption and lead body burden (Baker and Greer 2010).

It is well documented that lead (Pb²⁺) blocks the N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor (NMDA) (Bal-Price and Meek 2017). According to AOP12 (*Chronic binding of antagonist to NMDARs during brain development leads to neurodegeneration with impairment in learning and memory in aging*) and AOP13 (*Chronic binding of antagonist to NMDARs during brain development induces impairment*

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of learning and memory abilities) decreased calcium influx and reduced levels of Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) are cellular key events. Therefore, BDNF (*BDNF* methylation, gene expression and/or blood BDNF levels) should be included in the set of biomarkers.

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4.4 Mercury (CNRS, UCY and ISCIII)

The following flow-chart summarizes the mercury-related human studies retrieved from Pubmed using the Mesh terms (see D14.5) specific for each health endpoint. Among the seven health endpoints (Reproduction, Neurodevelopment, Metabolic, Immune, Endocrine, Cancer and Multiple endpoints), a total of 264 articles were retrieved, out of which, 51 studies reported effect biomarkers in human matrices after abstract screening of irrelevant articles and examination of biomarkers of effect in the full article.

Figure 5: Flow chart of mercury-related human studies

Search terms for cancer retrieved 9 articles however none reported relevant effect biomarkers as most pertained to mercury present in medical devices or were review articles. For endocrine-related search terms, no articles were retrieved. Due to technical problems with search terms, which provided a high non-approachable number of references, the specific search for “metabolic” effect biomarkers was not developed. Thus, the metabolic biomarkers that have been presented here were retrieved from the “multiple endpoint” search.

Articles retrievable using search terms from a minimum of two health endpoints were classified under “multiple endpoints” to remove overlaps (see D14.5). This group retrieved multiple effect biomarkers relevant for all health endpoints of interest, with some articles featuring multiple health endpoints. Identified Effect Biomarkers (51 articles examined)

1. Reproductive effect biomarkers

1.1 Classical reproductive biomarkers

The risk of SGA (small for gestational age) by weight decreased with increased Me-Hg concentration (Kishi et al., 2017). In cord blood, total mercury was negatively associated with birth weight of male newborns (Tatsuta et al., 2017).

In adolescent girls, significant negative associations were observed between total Hg in hair and age at menarche (Croes et al., 2014). In men; Inhibin B, predominantly excreted by Sertoli cells, is correlated with sperm concentration and counts and serves as a marker of spermatogenesis. A

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strong positive association between mercury in whole blood and inhibin B in serum was confirmed (Lenters et al., 2015).

1.2 Novel reproductive biomarkers

In whole blood of boys, correlations were observed between mercury in hair and gene expression of ARID4A (Croes et al., 2014), a member of the ARID (AT-rich interaction domain) gene family which play important roles in Sertoli cell function (Wu et al., 2013)

In men, the average methylation levels of H19, one of the best characterized imprinted genes in humans, was negatively correlated with urinary Hg concentrations. Specifically, 3 out of 7 CpG sites on H19 differentially methylated region (CpG2, CpG4 and CpG6) demonstrated a significant negative correlation with urinary Hg levels (Lu et al., 2018). Animal experiments found that mercury is easy to accumulate in the testicles, which resulted in inhibit DNA methyltransferase activity in spermatozoa through Hg induced oxidative stress, such as demethylation of the regulatory sequences of H19 in male germ cells (Lu et al., 2018).

The Glutathion S-transférase M1 (GSTM1) null allele has been associated with increased susceptibility to cancers and poor clearance of hazardous agents, and has also been suggested to play a role in human reproduction. In blood, higher GSTM1_P266 CpG site methylation was measured for the higher exposure Hg group (mean = 35.8%) compared with the lower exposure Hg group (mean = 25.7%; $P= 0.04$; Fig. 1a). However, no significant correlation was detected ($r = 0.17$; $P= 0.27$) between Hg concentration and methylation at this site (Hanna et al., 2012).

A family of zinc-dependent proteinases involved in the degradation of extracellular matrix during normal and pathological tissue remodelling that are known as matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) play a critical role in embryo implantation, placentation, cervical dilation and fetal-maternal membrane lysis. The distribution of the different MMP isoforms with respect to the mean metal concentrations of As, Cd, Hg, Mn and Pb exhibited metal-specific changes in plasma MMP profiles. The MMP isoforms 1, -2, -7, -9 and -10 are known to play crucial roles in reproductive function. High maternal third trimester plasma MMP-9 was associated with first trimester blood mercury and lead. Mean plasma concentration for the high MMP-7 group was associated with third trimester mercury exposure (Au et al., 2016).

Cervical dilation is a necessary step for labor and parturition to occur, yet few studies have examined the impact of environmental exposures on epigenetic changes in the cervix during pregnancy. During the 2nd trimester, expression of 17 cervical miRNA was associated with toenail mercury levels (let-7a and let-7b, and miRs-205, 125b, 200c, 342, 203, 24, 22, 23b, 375, 23a, 210, 200b, 99a, 21 and 193b). The four most significant mercury-associated miRNAs were miR-205, miR-125b, let-7b and miR-200c. Functional enrichment analyses revealed that mercury-associated miRNA gene targets are involved in reproductive system development and morphology (Sanders et al., 2015).

2. Neurodevelopmental and behavioural effect biomarkers

2.1 Classical neurodevelopmental biomarkers

Hair, fingernail or toenail methylmercury levels were negatively correlated with the **Bayley-III scale score of expressive language**. Total Hg levels in Meconium were not associated with expressive language scores, suggesting that greater MeHg exposure in the postnatal period reduces expressive language performance compared to exposure in the prenatal period (Hsi et al., 2014).

Exposure of infants to Hg via mothers during either pregnancy and/or neonatal life may induce oxidative stress that might contribute to observed infant neurodevelopmental delays. Infant's MeHg

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in hair and 8-OHdG and MDA levels were significantly associated with a delay in **Denver Developmental Screening Test II (DDST-II) performance** (Al-Saleh et al., 2016).

Hit Reaction Time latencies (HRT) in the Continuous Performance Test (CPT) (CPT-HRT) is considered a higher-order cognitive function involving the speed in processing visual information. The latencies may involve different neuropsychological functions depending on the time from test initiation, i.e., first orientation, learning and habituation, then cognitive processing and focused attention, and finally sustained attention as the dominant demand. Hit Reaction Time latencies (HRT) in the 2nd stage of the Continuous Performance Test (CPT) is hypothesized to involve speed processing and selective focused attention and was highly associated with cord and maternal hair methylmercury. HRT in the 3rd stage is presumed to add assessment of sustained attention and showed the strongest associations with cord and maternal hair methylmercury. As current mercury concentrations did not show any clear associations, prenatal exposure to methylmercury seems to have a stronger neurotoxic effect that also differs qualitatively from the effects of postnatal exposure. The sustained attention functioning may be particularly susceptible to prenatal methylmercury neurotoxicity because of the stronger effects observed during the final part of test duration. Such deficits indicate probable underlying dysfunctions of the frontal lobes (Julvez et al., 2010).

In adults, beneficial effects of high Selenium status on motor functions were reported in a population with elevated Hg exposure. Blood Hg concentrations influenced the associations between Selenium biomarkers and **psychomotor functions** determined. Hg-induced toxic effects may be offset by the anti-oxidant effects of selenium (Lemire et al., 2011).

In Pacific Island children, significant associations were observed between toenail mercury and **externalising, aggression, rule breaking, and attention problems** (Karatela et al., 2017).

In children with different severity of autism, Mercury intoxication-associated urinary porphyrins were significantly correlated with **increasing autism severity (CARS scores) and oxidized glutathione levels (GSSG) levels** (Geier et al., 2009).

Changes in **urinary porphyrin** excretion patterns might be used as a specific marker to evaluate Hg tissue accumulation and biological effects.

A study on subjects with ASD suggests that the level of Hg may increase the severity of autism. A positive correlation was observed between the levels of Hg in the blood and the CARS, and between Hg in blood and urinary porphyrin levels (pentacarboxyporphyrin, coproporphyrin, precoproporphyrin, uroporphyrin, and hexacarboxyporphyrin) (Khaled et al., 2016).

Mercury can cause increased **urinary pentacarboxyporphyrin (5cxP), precoproporphyrin (prcP), and coproporphyrin (cP)** by inhibiting uroporphyrinogen decarboxylase (UROD) and/or coproporphyrinogen oxidase (CPOX). In children diagnosed with ASD by CARS, levels of **Hg-toxicity-associated porphyrins (5cxP, prcP, and cP)** are higher than controls (Kern et al., 2011).

Mercury-associated porphyrins are associated with the features of autism determined by CARS & **ATEC (Autism Treatment Evaluation Checklist)** evaluations. In children, overall ATEC scores and their scores on each of the ATEC subscales (Speech/Language, Sociability, Sensory/Cognitive Awareness, and Health/Physical/Behavior) had a linear relationship with some ratio measures of the mercury-associated porphyrin(s) (5cP, PrcP and [5cP + PrcP]) to some non-mercury-associated porphyrin(s) (uP and [7cP + uP]) (Kern, Geier, Adams, & Geier, 2010).

Methylmercury (MeHg) neurotoxicity has been recognized for a long time and alterations of visual functions are well known signs of MeHg exposure. Visual deficits were reported and constriction of the visual field was a predominant sign among mercury-poisoned individuals following contamination episodes in Japan and Iraq. Rice and Gilbert (1990), who studied the developmental

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effects of dietary MeHg on non-human primate spatial and temporal visual functions, reported contrast sensitivity deficits at spatial frequencies of 3–7 cpd, suggesting a preferential damage to the parvocellular pathway. There is also evidence that Hg could accumulate in ocular structures and affect rods and cones. **Visual and ocular health examinations reported reduced contrast sensitivity** at low and intermediate spatial frequencies was associated with hair Hg. In addition, hair Hg was associated with **acquired color vision loss** (Fillion et al., 2013). Presbyopia, the normal age-related loss of near vision acuity, results from the eye's reduced ability accommodate and depends upon lens elasticity and ciliary muscle functioning. In adults over 40 years of age, hair Hg was associated with increased odds of presenting **clinical near visual impairment**, with near visual acuity loss progressing more quickly with higher Hg exposure. No such association was observed in younger people (Fillion et al., 2011).

In order to develop a practical toolkit to enable conducting a rapid assessment of the health situation of gold miners, biomarkers for chronic Inorganic Mercury Intoxication were evaluated in gold miners across 3 countries (Zimbabwe, Indonesia, Tanzania, Mongolia & Philippines). Hair mercury was determined as an essential indicator for the diagnosis of Chronic Inorganic Mercury Intoxication (CIMI) and relevant indicators for CIMI were: **metallic taste, excessive salivation, tremor, sleeping problems, discoloration of oral cavity, ataxia of gait, dysdiadochokinesia, heel to shin ataxia, proteinuria, matchbox test, and the pencil taping test** (Doering, Bose-O'Reilly, & Berger, 2016).

2.2 Novel neurodevelopment/behaviour biomarkers

Significant correlations were also observed between mercury in hair and **gene expression** in whole blood of boys (**JAK2, Hist1HA4L**) and in girls (**PIAS2, MANN1B1, GIT and ABCA1**). Although no direct links were found between the HIST1H4L and PIAS2 genes and human diseases, it is likely that these genes too might affect neurological functions (Croes et al., 2014).

One of the most widely studied epigenetic modifications is DNA methylation at the 5' position of cytosine (C) nucleotides, also referred to as **5-methylcytosine (5mC)**. More recently, it has been demonstrated that 5mC can undergo oxidation by the ten-eleven translocation (TET) family of enzymes to form **5-hydroxymethylcytosine (5hmC)**. Regulation of gene expression by 5hmC has been shown to be independent of 5mC and plays a crucial role during embryogenesis, particularly in neurogenesis. Prenatal mercury exposure (determined by red blood cell mercury concentrations), measured during the second trimester of pregnancy, was associated with lower % - 5hmC genomic content and a corresponding increase in the ratio of % - 5mC to % - 5hmC in cord blood and midchildhood blood. (Cardenas et al., 2017).

Higher DNA methylation levels of the **Paraoxonase 1 (PON1)** region are associated with lower cognitive test scores (determined by Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test (PPVT)) in early childhood for both sexes. Maternal mercury levels (determined in red blood cells) were associated with lower regional **cord blood DNA methylation at the Paraoxonase 1 gene (PON1) in males** that persisted in early childhood and was attenuated in mid-childhood blood. In the absence of genotype information, it is not possible to determine if genetic variants are responsible for the observed methylation differences. However, it has been shown that MeHg exposure inhibits PON1 activity even after controlling for the major known genetic variants, suggesting a dominant epigenetic control mechanism for the enzyme (Cardenas et al., 2017b).

However in adults, no association with blood levels of Hg and serum MDA or plasma PON1 activity or genotype was noted (Almeida Lopes et al., 2017)

In cord serum, **BDNF concentrations** decreased slightly with MeHg exposure, and maternal smoking enhanced the decrease in serum BDNF induced by MeHg exposure. A negative

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correlation between prenatal MeHg exposure and serum BDNF only in girls born to nonsmoking mothers (Spulber et al., 2010).

In addition, two loci (cg09606766; cg01636003) located in South shore regions of **CpG islands of the BDNF gene were hypomethylated** ($P = 0.004$) while one loci (cg18595174) located in an open sea region was hypermethylated ($P = 0.015$) with increasing toenail mercury concentrations. Selenoprotein P is central to selenium homeostasis, SEPP1 encodes a selenoprotein potentially involved in Hg toxicity protection. For the **SEPP1 gene**, one loci (cg04502814) located in an open sea region increase in methylation with increasing toenail mercury concentrations (Cardenas et al., 2015).

Among male dental professionals, higher hair Hg levels were significantly associated with decreased **SEPP1 methylation (average and CpG site-specific)** in a region discovered to have great inter-individual variability. The importance of SEPP1 in Hg toxicokinetics and protection against toxicity via direct binding and antioxidant properties is well established though there is a scarcity of data on epigenetic regulation of SEPP1. Previous studies identified selenium levels, gender, BMI, SEPP1 genotype, I-Hg exposure, and cancer status as predictors of SEPP plasma concentration, SEPP isoform prevalence, and/or Hg binding to the protein (Goodrich et al., 2013).

3. Immune System and/or oxidative stress effect biomarkers

3.1 Classical Immune and/or oxidative stress biomarkers

Higher levels of oxidative stress and disturbed anti-inflammatory capacity could lower children's defense against other insults, such as air pollution, and provoke chronic airway inflammatory status, including asthma. In school childer, Blood Hg concentrations at 7–8 years of age were associated with an **increased risk of asthma** at age 11-12. Specifically, Hg concentration was also associated with **wheezing, asthma medication use and airway hyperresponsiveness** (Kim et al., 2015). In adolescents, significant negative associations were observed between total Hg and MMHg in hair and **asthma**, and between MMHg and allergy for animals. In mothers, a negative association was observed between mercury and asthma (Croes et al., 2014).

Increased maternal toenail Hg was associated with a decrease in the proportion of **monocytes** and an increase in the propotion of **B-cells** in cord blood of females (Cardenas et al., 2015).

Total IgG level in cord blood was significantly associated with cord and maternal blood total mercury level. However, neither maternal nor cord blood cytokine levels of any of the cytokines analyzed were significantly associated with either maternal or cord blood mercury levels. Neither total antinuclear autoantibody nor antinuclear IgG titer in either maternal or cord blood was significantly associated with maternal or cord blood mercury levels (Nyland, Wang, et al., 2011).

Increasing blood Hg levels are associated with **serum inflammatory markers** in children (**Complement Factor B, Complement component C6, Carboxypeptidase N subunit 2, Inter-alpha-trypsin inhibior heavy chain H1, Complement C3, Ceruloplasmin, Hemopexin, Alha-1-antichymotrypsin, Inter-alpha-trypsin inhibitor heavy chain H4, Alpha-1B-glycoprotein, Gelsolin, and apolipoprotein A-II**). Most importantly, the associations demonstrated here were significant at Hg levels well below the potential health risk level of 5.8 µg/L that has been established by the US EPA (Gump et al., 2012).

A number of studies have shown that mercury may induce oxidative stress with subsequent oxidative damage in several organs or systems (Santos et al., 2018). Low body burden of Hg may induce high levels of oxdiative stress in mother and infants. Urinary Hg level in mothers and infants were correlated with increased urinary **malondialdehyde (MDA)** and **8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine (8-OHdG)** levels, used as indicators of lipid peroxidation and DNA damage, respectively (Al-Saleh et al., 2016).

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Lactational exposure to Hg can induce oxidative stress in breast-fed infants and may play a role in the pathogenesis of many health problems, particularly during neurodevelopment. **MDA levels** in infant urine increased with increasing Hg levels in breast milk, suggesting not coexcretion but rather an induction of lipid peroxidation due to maternal Hg exposure (Al-Saleh et al., 2013). In children from 3 localities in Yucatan Mexico, compared to samples without detectable levels of urine Hg, samples with detectable levels of urine had higher blood **MDA** levels, lower **GSH** values, and in one of the 3 localities, higher **PON-1** levels (Rangel-Méndez et al., 2016).

Mercury may aggravate impaired glutathione synthesis by depleting glutathione in lymphocytes and monocytes, leading to an increased risk of immuno and cytotoxic effects. In children with ASD, a negative correlation between Hg & Pb in red blood cells and **vitamin E & GST** in plasma was observed. In addition, an inverse relationship between decreased levels of plasma GST and the severity of autism, as measured by the SRS and CARS, was reported (Alabdali et al., 2014). In autistic subjects, mercury levels in hair were markedly higher and **GSH levels** were significantly decreased, consistent with the importance of glutathione for its elimination. A comparison of hair mercury levels with serum thiol levels revealed a significant inverse correlation with serum levels of **cysteine, cystine and GSSH** in control subjects but not in autistic subject (Hodgson et al., 2014).

Ferritin has a dual action on the oxidative stress system: as a scavenger it is cytoprotective, but as a donor of free iron it causes oxidative stress. In a low-exposure state or acute exposure, ferritin has anti-oxidant activity by consuming Fe²⁺ that produces toxic free radicals in the Fenton reaction. However, if the burden of oxidative stress outweighs the scavenging capacity, ferritin can damage tissue by loss of sequestering Fe²⁺ from the Fenton reaction in which the oxidation to Fe³⁺ donates single electron to convert harmless reactive species (i.e., peroxides) into highly toxic radicals. Serum **ferritin** is positively associated with blood Hg in adult men with high serum ferritin levels (Lee & Hwang, 2014).

3.2 Novel immune biomarkers

Significant correlations were also observed between mercury in hair and **gene expression of HLAdrb5** in whole blood of girls (Croes et al., 2014).

In cord blood, **DNA methylation of a genomic region associated with the TCEANC2** gene was inversely associated with total and methylmercury concentrations, which may be related in part to mercury-induced changes in blood cell composition (B cells, CD4⁺ T cells, CD8⁺ T cells, granulocytes, monocytes, natural killer cells and whole blood). The functional consequences of altered methylation at the TCEANC2 region have not yet been determined as a relationship between TCEANC2 DNA methylation and gene expression was not observed in the small number of available cord blood RNA samples (n = 34). (Bakulski et al., 2015)

In women, antinuclear antibodies (ANAs) are highly sensitive for a variety of autoimmune conditions, including systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE), scleroderma, and Sjögren's syndrome. MeHg, at low levels generally considered safe, was associated with subclinical autoimmunity among reproductive-age females. Hair and blood, but not urinary, mercury were associated with **antinuclear antibody (ANA) positivity** (Somers et al., 2015).

In adults and adolescents, MeHg exposure was associated with an **increased ANA** and changes in **serum cytokine profile**. Moreover, alterations in serum cytokine profiles differed based on ANA response, suggesting a specific phenotype of MeHg susceptibility. **Elevated anti-nuclear antibodies (ANA)** titers in serum were associated with blood and plasma Hg levels. **Proinflammatory (IL-6, IFN- γ , IL-4, IL-7)** increased with MeHg exposure but in the subset of the population with elevated ANA, IL-1 β , IL-6, IFN- γ , and TNF- α and IL-4 cytokine levels were decreased with MeHg exposure. High Hg exposure and a high positive ANA titer had lower pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines than those individuals with low Hg exposure. Specifically, a

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positive association between IL-4 levels and plasma and blood Hg. IL-6 and IL-7 serum levels were positively associated with blood, plasma and hair Hg. IFN- γ was positively associated with plasma and blood Hg (Nyland, Fillion, et al., 2011).

Elevated titers and prevalence of **anti-nuclear autoantibodies (ANA) and anti-nucleolar autoantibodies (AnoA)** were found in human populations exposed to mercury in artisanal gold mining. Levels of the **pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β , TNF- α , and IFN- γ** are significantly higher in mercury-exposed groups. In the High Hg/AN(o)A+ group, significantly higher levels of serum IL-1 β were found, as compared to individuals in the low mercury exposure groups, regardless of the AN(o)A status. TNF- α , another pro-inflammatory cytokine, was also elevated in the High Hg/AN(o)A+ group as compared to the Low Hg groups. IFN- γ , a cytokine generally associated with inflammatory responses of TH1 cells, was elevated in the High Hg/AN(o)A+ group compared to the Low Hg groups (Gardner et al., 2010).

After having previously reported that elevated serum titers of antinuclear autoantibodies (ANA) are associated with mercury exposures of miners in gold mining, autoimmune dysfunction in mining populations from Amazonian Brazil with and without exposures to mercury was investigated by Motts et al. (2014). The higher mercury-exposed gold miners had a higher number of different autoantibodies as compared to the diamond and emerald miners. Diamond and emerald miners experience many similar physical and environmental stresses compared to the gold miners, with the exception of occupational exposure to mercury. Average serum **autoantibody titers against “stimulated by retinoic acid 13”, “linker for activation of T cells”, “signal peptide peptidase like 2B”, “interferon induced transmembrane protein”, glutathione S-transferase A1 (GSTA1) and “tumor necrosis factor ligand superfamily member 13”** were upregulated more than 10-fold in the high mercury/high ANA samples compared to low mercury/low ANA samples. Importantly, the protein with the highest average autoantibody response in the high mercury/high ANA group was **GSTA1** (Motts et al., 2014).

In contrast, In a study on artisanal gold miners with higher Hg exposure, urine, blood and hair Hg **were not correlated** with ANA nor RF (**Rheumatoid factor (RF)**), the most prominent autoantibodies, both in terms of frequency and pathogenesis in autoimmune disorders (Sánchez Rodríguez et al., 2015).

4. Metabolic effect biomarkers

4.1 Classical metabolic biomarkers

Maternal urinary excretions of biomarkers of **oxidative stress (MDA, 8-OHdG) and renal function (ALB, α 1-MG, NAG, and Cr)** were high in the highest quartile of Hg (Al-Saleh et al., 2017). Subjects with the highest mercury quartile had significantly higher odds ratio in **metabolic syndrome** compared with the lowest mercury quartile group metabolic syndrome (defined by central obesity, blood pressure, fasting glucose, low HDL cholesterol) (Park et al., 2009).

In elderly in institutionalized care, whole blood Hg levels were also positively correlated with blood **albumin levels** (p=0.015). Additionally, albumin was recently defined as a mercury containing protein important for mercury metabolism in the human body (Yun et al., 2013) (Rambousková et al., 2014).

In a cross-sectional study on Inuits, whole blood mercury was positively associated with **fasting plasma glucose and 2h glucose**, but only weakly associated with impaired fasting glycemia and type 2 diabetes (Jeppesen et al., 2015).

Chronic viral liver disease may alter the pace of MeHg hepatobiliary elimination in reproductive-age women – and therefore also affect the risk of neurotoxicity to the developing fetus. In women with

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chronic hepatitis B had 1.52 times the total blood mercury of those never having had contact with the HBV virus or vaccine (Sheehan et al., 2012).

4.2 Novel metabolic biomarkers

Significant correlations were also observed between mercury in hair and gene expression of **ABCA1** in whole blood of girls (Croes et al., 2014).

5. Endocrine effect biomarkers

5.1 Classical endocrine effect biomarkers

In adolescents, significant negative associations were observed between the logarithm of MeHg in hair and **free testosterone levels** (Croes et al., 2014).

A blunted diurnal cortisol slope is a precursor for many disorders. Increasing blood Hg was associated with **blunted diurnal salivary cortisol** (Gump et al., 2012).

In adults, Blood mercury was associated with decreases in **serum total and free T3 and total T4** (Yorita Christensen, 2013).

5.2 Novel neurodevelopmental/behaviour/endocrine effect biomarkers

Several studies have tested this hypothesis and show that increased **methylation of the glucocorticoid receptor NR3C1** is associated with reduced gene expression and neurobehavioral risk in infancy. Higher exposure to Hg was associated with increased **placental methylation NR3C1**. (Appleton et al., 2017).

6. Cancer effect biomarkers

6.1 Novel cancer effect biomarkers

Significant correlations were also observed between mercury in hair and gene expression of **Hist1HA4L** in whole blood of boys (Croes et al., 2014).

Micronuclei (MN) have been extensively used as biomarkers of chromosomal damage and genome instability in populations exposed to geno-toxic agents. The cytokinesis-block micronucleus (CBMN) assay is the most widely used method for measuring micronucleus frequency in human peripheral blood lymphocytes. Age and gender are the most accepted variables affecting MN frequency; however, dietary factors, genetic factors, ionizing radiation, air pollution, heavy metals and some lifestyle factors may also have an influence. Correlations between fathers and mothers cannot be attributed to a shared genetic background, and suggests the influence of environmental and/or lifestyle exposures. Elevated blood mercury levels were associated with an increase in **micronucleated binucleated cells (MNBC) frequency** in pregnant women and fathers (Lope et al., 2009).

Table 10: Classical and novel effect biomarkers identified related to multiple health endpoints

No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
1	Mothers and newborns paris (n=255; mean age= 30) and adolescents (n=210; mean age 14.8); Flemish biomonitoring programmes FLEHS I (2002–2006) and FLEHS II (2007–201)- Flanders (Belgium).	<p>Classical Immune biomarkers: In adolescents, significant negative associations were observed between <u>total Hg and MMHg in hair and asthma</u>, and between <u>MMHg and allergy for animals</u>. In mothers, a negative association was observed between <u>mercury and asthma</u>.</p> <p>Classical reproductive biomarkers: In adolescents, significant negative associations were observed between total <u>Hg in hair and age at menarche in girls</u></p>	(Croes et al., 2014)

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No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
		<p>Classical endocrine biomarkers: In adolescents, significant negative associations were observed between the logarithm of <u>MMHg in hair and free testosterone levels</u></p> <p>Novel biomarkers: Significant correlations were also observed between <u>mercury in hair and gene expression in whole blood of JAK2, ARID4A, Hist1HA4L (boys) and HLAdrb5, PIAS2, MANN1B1, GIT and ABCA1 (girls).</u></p>	
2	Men (n=243; mean age = 31) from a reproductive medical clinic in Shanxi (China).	Novel reproduction biomarkers: In sperm, the average <u>methylation levels of H19</u> was negatively correlated with urinary Hg concentrations. Specifically 3 out of 7 CpG sites on H19 DMR, namely CpG2, CpG4 and CpG6 demonstrated a significant negative correlation with urinary Hg levels.	(Lu et al., 2018)
3	Mothers and newborns (n= 497 singleton neonates); Sapporo (Japan).	Classical reproductive biomarkers: the risk of SGA (small for gestational age) by weight decreased with increased Me-Hg concentration.	(Kishi et al., 2017)
4	neonates (n=306) and early childhood (n=68; age 2.9 to 4.9 years); Massachusetts (US)	Novel (neuro)development biomarkers: Prenatal mercury exposure (determined by <u>red blood cell mercury concentrations</u>) was associated with <u>lower % - 5hmC genomic content</u> in cord blood and a corresponding <u>increase in the ratio of % - 5mC to % - 5hmC in cord blood and midchildhood blood.</u>	(Cardenas et al., 2017)
5	neonates (n=222); Rhode Island Child Health Study (US)	Novel neuro(development)/endocrine biomarkers: Several studies have tested this hypothesis and show that increased NR3C1 methylation is associated with reduced gene expression and neurobehavioral risk in infancy. Higher exposure to Hg (determined by toe nail) was associated with increased placental methylation of the glucocorticoid receptor NR3C1.	(Appleton et al., 2017)
6	neonates (n=321), children (n=75, aged 2.9 -4.9; n=291, aged 6.7-10.5)	Novel (neuro)development biomarkers: maternal mercury levels (determined in red blood cells) were associated with <u>lower regional cord blood DNA methylation at the Paraoxonase 1 gene (PON1) in males that persisted in early childhood and was attenuated in mid-childhood blood.</u> Higher DNA methylation levels of the PON1 region <u>are associated with lower cognitive test scores</u> in early childhood for both sexes.	(Cardenas et al., 2017b)
7	mother-infant pairs (n=138; mean age = 31 years); New hampshire (US)	<p>Classical immune biomarkers: Increased maternal toenail Hg was associated with a decrease in the proportion of monocytes and an increase in the propotion of B-cells in cord blood of females.</p> <p>Novel neurodevelopment markers: Two loci (cg09606766; cg01636003) located in South shore regions of CpG islands of the BDNF gene were <u>hypomethylated</u> (P = 0.004) while one loci (cg18595174) located in an open sea region was <u>hypermethylated</u> (P = 0.015) with increasing toenail mercury concentrations. For the SEPP1 gene, one loci (cg04502814) located in an open sea region <u>increase in methylation</u> with increasing toenail mercury</p>	(Cardenas et al., 2015)

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No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
		concentrations.	
8	newborns (n=141); Baltimore (US)	Novel immune biomarkers: In cord blood, DNA <u>methylation of a genomic region associated with the TCEANC2 gene was inversely associated with total and methylmercury concentrations</u> , which may be related in part to mercury-induced changes in blood cell composition (B cells, CD4+ T cells, CD8+ T cells, granulocytes, monocytes, natural killer cells and whole blood). The functional consequences of altered methylation at the TCEANC2 region have not yet been determined as they did not observe a relationship between TCEANC2 DNA methylation and gene expression in the small number of available cord blood RNA samples (n = 34). (The CHARM an array-based method did not overlap with SEPP1; 15 CHARM probes were within 50 kb of this gene, but none showed association with methylmercury; In our study, there were 19 CHARM probes within 5 kb of the GSTM1 gene and 29 probes within 5 kb of the GSTM5 gene).	(Bakulski et al., 2015)
9	placenta samples (n=192) with infants with toenail data (n=41; mean age=) infants with	Novel neurodevelopment/behaviour biomarkers: <u>EMID2 hypomethylation may represent a novel mechanism linking in utero Hg exposure and adverse infant neurobehavioral</u> Specifically, infant toenail Hg was associated with placental hypomethylation of loci related to high-risk newborn neurobehavioral profile (defined by the NNNS), including <u>hypomethylation of EMID2</u> , moderately correlated with EMID2 expression.	(Maccani et al., 2015)
10	case study on ASD in infants (n=27 cases vs 27 controls; mean age =5.4);(Oman)	Classical Immune/oxidative stress biomarkers: in autistic subjects, mercury levels in hair were markedly <u>higher</u> and GSH levels were significantly decreased, consistent with the importance of glutathione for its elimination. A comparison of hair <u>mercury levels with serum thiol levels revealed a significant inverse correlation with serum levels of cysteine, cystine and GSSH in control subjects but not in autistic subjects.</u>	(Hodgson et al., 2014)
11	Dental professionals (n=131; mean age= 55.8); Michigan (US)	Novel neurodevelopmental biomarkers: <u>a significant negative correlation was observed between average SEPP1 methylation (acquired from buccal swabs) and hair Hg in males only, and persisted with individual SEPP1 CpG sites</u>	(Goodrich et al., 2013)
12	Women undergoing a first completed IVF cycle (n= 58; mean age = 36) California (US)	Novel reproductive biomarkers: In blood, <u>higher GSTM1 P266 CpG site methylation was measured for the higher exposure Hg group compared with the lower exposure Hg group (mean = 25.7%; P= 0.04; Fig. 1a). However, no significant correlation was detected (r = 0.17; P= 0.27) between Hg concentration and methylation at this site.</u>	(Hanna et al., 2012).
13	Mother-newborn pairs (n=489; mean age= 31); North East (Japan)	Classical reproductive biomarkers: In cord blood, <u>total mercury was negatively associated with birth weight of male newborns.</u>	(Tatsuta et al., 2017)
14	Mother-infant paris (n=944; median age=30); Riyadh	Classical metabolic biomarkers: <u>Maternal urinary excretions of biomarkers of oxidative stress (MDA, 8-</u>	(Al-Saleh et al., 2017)

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No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
	(Saudi Arabia)	<u>OhdG</u>) and renal function (ALB, α 1-MG, NAG, and Cr) were high in the highest quartile of Hg.	
15	Case study; Adults (n=343; mean age=46.5); Ajou (Korea)	Classical metabolic biomarkers: Subjects with <u>the highest mercury quartile had significantly higher odds ratio in metabolic syndrome</u> compared with the lowest mercury quartile group metabolic syndrome (defined by central obesity, blood pressure, fasting glucose, low HDL cholesterol).	(Park et al., 2009)
16	Mother (n=145), Fathers (n=144) and newborn (n=135); Madrid (Spain)	Novel (cancer?) biomarkers: Micronuclei (MN) have been extensively used as biomarkers of chromosomal damage and genome instability in populations exposed to geno-toxic agents. The cytokinesis-block micronucleus (CBMN) assay is the most widely used method for measuring micronucleus frequency in human peripheral bloodlymphocytes. Age and gender are the most accepted variables affecting MN frequency; however, dietary factors, genetic factors, ionizing radiation, air pollution, heavy metals and some lifestyle factors may also have an influence. Correlations between fathers and mothers cannot be attributed to a shared genetic background, and suggests the influence of environmental and/or lifestyle exposures. <u>Elevated blood mercury levels were associated with an increase in micronucleated binucleated cells (MNBC) frequency in pregnant women and fathers.</u>	(Lope et al., 2009)
17	newborns (n=395); (Faroe Islands)	Novel neurodevelopmental biomarkers: In cord serum, BDNF concentrations decreased slightly with MeHg exposure, and maternal smoking enhanced the decrease in serum BDNF induced by MeHg exposure. <u>A negative correlation between prenatal MeHg exposure and serum BDNF only in girls born to nonsmoking mothers.</u>	(Spulber et al., 2010)
18	mother-infant pairs (n=61; mean age = 21years); Amazon (Brazil)	Classical immune biomarkers: <u>Total IgG level in cord blood was significantly associated with cord blood and maternal mercury level.</u> However, neither maternal nor cord blood cytokine levels of any of the cytokines analyzed were significantly associated with either maternal or cord blood mercury levels. Neither total antinuclear autoantibody nor antinuclear IgG titer in either maternal or cord blood was significantly associated with maternal or cord blood mercury levels.	(Nyland, Wang, et al., 2011)
19	Cross sectional study; children (n=100; age 9-11 years old); New York (USA)	Classical endocrine biomarkers: A blunted diurnal cortisol slope is a precursor for many disorders. Increasing blood Hg was associated with blunted diurnal salivary cortisol. Classical immune biomarkers: <u>Increasing blood Hg levels are associated with serum inflammatory markers in children</u> (Complement Factor B, Complement component C6, Carboxypeptidase N subunit 2, Inter-alpha-trypsin inhibitor heavy chain H1, Complement C3, Ceruloplasmin, Hemopexin, Alpha-1-antichymotrypsin, Inter-alpha-trypsin inhibitor heavy chain H4, Alpha-1B-glycoprotein, Gelsolin, and	(Gump et al., 2012)

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No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
		apolipoprotein A-II). Most importantly, the associations demonstrated here were significant at Hg levels well below the potential health risk level of 5.8 µg/L that has been established by the US EPA.	
20	Case study from NHANES; women (n= 5088; age=); (US)	Classical metabolic biomarker: Chronic viral liver disease may alter the pace of MeHg hepatobiliary elimination in reproductive-age women – and therefore also affect the risk of neurotoxicity to the developing fetus. <u>In women with chronic hepatitis B had 1.52 times the total blood mercury</u> of those never having had contact with the HBV virus or vaccine.	(Sheehan et al., 2012)
21	Cross sectional study from NHANES; adults (n=1587; media age = 45 years); (US)	Classical endocrine biomarkers: <u>Blood mercury was associated with decreases in serum total, free T3 and total T4.</u>	(Yorita Christensen, 2013)
22	mother-infants pairs (n=155; mean age= 30); (Saudi Arabia)	Classical oxidative stress biomarkers: Lactational exposure to Hg can induce oxidative stress in breast-fed infants and may play a role in the pathogenesis of many health problems, particularly during neurodevelopment. <u>MDA levels in infant urine increased with increasing Hg levels in breast milk,</u> suggesting not coexcretion but rather an induction of lipid peroxidation due to maternal Hg exposure.	(Al-Saleh et al., 2013)
23	mother-newborn pairs (n=250; median age=28); (Saudi Arabia)	Placental Hg was positively correlated with cord and maternal blood Tail Moment (TM), a measure of DNA damage in the comet assay. Hg in cord blood had a significantly positive association with crown-heel length. Unexplainably, placental Hg was associated with reduced birth height.	(Al-Saleh et al., 2014)
24	mother-infant pairs (n=83; age=3); (Taiwan)	Classical neurodevelopmental biomarkers: Hair, fingernail or toenail <u>methylmercury levels were negatively correlated with the Bayley-III scale score of expressive language.</u> Total Hg levels in Meconium were not associated with expressive language scores, suggesting that greater MeHg exposure in the postnatal period reduces expressive language performance compared to exposure in the prenatal period.	(Hsi et al., 2014)
25	Elderly (n=197; mean age = 83); (Czech Republic)	Classical metabolic biomarkers: Whole blood Hg levels were also positively correlated with blood albumin levels (p=0.015). Additionally, albumin was recently defined as a mercury containing protein important for mercury metabolism in the human body (Yun et al., 2013).	(Rambousková et al., 2014)
26	Men (n=600) (Ukraine, Greenland & Poland)	Classical reproductive biomarkers: Inhibin B, predominantly excreted by Sertoli cells, is correlated with sperm concentration and counts, and serves as a marker of spermatogenesis. <u>A strong positive association between mercury in whole blood and inhibin B in serum</u> was confirmed.	(Lenters et al., 2015)
27	Cross-sectional study NHANES; Adult females (n=1352; mean age=32); (US)	Novel immune biomarkers: Antinuclear antibodies (ANAs) are highly sensitive for a variety of autoimmune conditions, including systemic lupus	(Somers et al., 2015)

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No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
		erythematosus (SLE), scleroderma, and Sjögren's syndrome. MeHg, at low levels generally considered safe, was associated with subclinical autoimmunity among reproductive-age females. <u>Hair and blood, but not urinary, mercury were associated with antinuclear antibody (ANA) positivity.</u>	
28	Cross-sectional study on Inuits; Adults (n= 2640; median age=44); (Greenland)	Classical metabolic biomarker: <u>Whole blood mercury was positively associated with fasting plasma glucose and 2h glucose,</u> but only weakly associated with impaired fasting glycemia and type 2 diabetes	(Jeppesen et al., 2015)
29	Children (n=107; median age =8); Yucatan (Mexico)	Classical oxidative stress biomarkers: Compared to samples without detectable levels of urine Hg, samples with detectable levels of urine had <u>higher MDA levels, lower GSH values, and</u> in one of the 3 localities, higher PON-1 levels.	(Rangel-Méndez et al., 2016)
30	Cross-sectional study of dentists (n=64; mean age = 39); Monastir (Tunisia)	Classical neurodevelopment/behaviour biomarkers: Mean levels of urinary mercury were detected in dentists. Dentists with <u>high levels of urinary mercury presented neuropsychological manifestations</u> (bilateral and symmetric intentional tremor in both upper limbs).	(Chaari et al., 2015)
31	Case study on ASD (n=100; age 3-6); Giza (Egypt)	Classical neurodevelopment/behaviour biomarkers: A positive correlation was observed between the <u>levels of Hg in the blood and the CARS,</u> and between <u>Hg in blood and urinary porphyrin levels</u> (pentacarboxyporphyrin, coproporphyrin, precoproporphyrin, uroporphyrin, and hexacarboxyporphyrin).	(Khaled et al., 2016)
32	Mother-infant pair (n=944; mean age = 30 years; mean age= 8 months); Riyadh (Saudi Arabia)	Classical oxidative stress biomarkers: urinary Hg level in mothers and infants were correlated with increased 8-OHdG and MDA levels. Classical neurodevelopment biomarkers: infant's MeHg in hair and 8-OHdG and MDA levels were significantly associated with a delay in Denver Developmental Screening Test II (DDST-II) performance.	(Al-Saleh et al., 2016)

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Table 11: Classical and novel effect biomarkers identified related to reproductive outcomes

No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
1	Mother-infant pairs (n=1553); 10 sites from the MIREC study (Canada)	Novel reproductive biomarkers: The high maternal third trimester plasma <u>MMP-9 was associated with first trimester blood mercury and lead</u> . Mean plasma concentration for the <u>high MMP-7 group was associated with third trimester mercury exposure</u> .	(Au et al., 2016)
2	Pregnant women (n=60; mean age= 28); (Mexico)	Novel reproductive biomarkers: During the 2 nd trimester, <u>expression of 17 cervical miRNA was associated with toenail mercury levels</u> (let-7a and let-7b, and miRs-205, 125b, 200c, 342, 203, 24, 22, 23b, 375, 23a, 210, 200b, 99a, 21 and 193b). The four most significant mercury-associated miRNAs were miR-205, miR-125b, let-7b and miR-200c. Functional enrichment analyses revealed that mercury-associated miRNA gene targets are involved in reproductive system development and morphology.	(Sanders et al., 2015)
3	Adolescences (n=878; age=14); (Faroe islands)	Classical neurodevelopmental biomarkers: Hit Reaction Time latencies (HRT) in the 2 nd stage of the Continuous Performance Test (CPT) is hypothesized to involve speed processing and selective focused attention and was highly associated with cord and maternal hair methylmercury. HRT in the 3 rd stage is presumed to add assessment of sustained attention and showed the strongest associations with cord and maternal hair methylmercury.	(Julvez et al., 2010)

Table 12: Classical and novel effect biomarkers identified related to neurodevelopment

No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
1	Pacific Island children (n=278; age=9); Auckland (New Zealand)	Classical neurodevelopmental/behaviour biomarkers: significant associations were observed between toenail mercury and externalising, aggression, rule breaking, and attention problems.	(Karatela et al., 2017)
2	Adults (n=832; age>40); (Southern Brazil)	Novel neurodevelopmental/behavioural biomarkers: For blood Hg, no association with serum MDA or with plasma PON1 activity or genotype was noted.	(Almeida Lopes et al., 2017)
3	Cross-sectional study; Adults (n=349; mean age=35.9); State of Para (Brazil)	Classical neurodevelopmental/behavioural biomarkers: In adults over 40 years of age, hair mercury was associated with increased odds of presenting clinical near visual impairment, No such observation was note in younger people.	(Fillion et al., 2011)
4	Case study on ASD; children (n=40; mean age = 6.6 years); Texas (USA)	Classical neurodevelopmental/behavioural biomarkers: Levels of Hg-toxicity-associated porphyrins (5cxP, prcP, and cP) are higher in children with an ASD diagnosis than controls.	(Kern et al., 2011)
5	Case study on ASD and pervasive developmental disorder (PDD); children (n=24; mean age = 5.75 years); Texas (USA)	Classical neurodevelopmental/behavioural biomarkers: Overall <u>ATEC scores and their scores on each of the ATEC subscales (Speech/Language, Sociability, Sensory/Cognitive Awareness, and</u>	(Kern et al., 2010)

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No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
		<u>Health/Physical/Behavior</u>) had a linear relationship with some ratio measures of the mercury-associated porphyrin(s) (5cP, PrcP and [5cP + PrcP]) to some non-mercury-associated porphyrin(s) (uP and [7cP + uP]) (Kern et al., 2010).	
6	Cross-sectional study; Men (n=2832; mean age=44.1); (Korea)	Classical oxidative stress biomarkers: Serum ferritin is <u>positively associated with blood Hg in adult men with high serum ferritin levels.</u>	(Lee & Hwang, 2014)
7	Cross-sectional case study on ASD; male children (n=82; mean age= 7)	Classical oxidative stress biomarkers: A <u>negative correlation between Hg & Pb in red blood cells and plasma vitamin E & GST was observed in ASD patients.</u>	(Alabdali et al., 2014)
8	Cross-sectional study; (n=228; mean age = 35.3); Para (Brazil)	Classical neurodevelopmental/behavioural biomarkers: Near visual contrast sensitivity and acquired color vision loss was negatively associated with Hair Hg.	(Fillion et al., 2013)
9	Adults; (n=407; mean age = 41.5); Para (Brazil)	Classical neurodevelopmental/behavioural biomarkers: <u>Blood Hg concentrations influenced the associations between Selenium biomarkers and motor performance outcomes</u> determined. Hg-induced toxic effects may be offset by the anti-oxidant effects of selenium.	(Lemire et al., 2011)
10	Case study; Children with ASD (n=28; age=4.6); Texas (USA)	Classical neurodevelopmental/behavioural biomarkers: <u>Mercury intoxication-associated urinary porphyrins were significantly correlated with increasing autism severity (CARS scores) and oxidized glutathione levels (GSSG) levels.</u>	(Geier et al., 2009)

Table 13: Classical and novel effect biomarkers related to Immunity and oxidative stress

No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
1	Cross-sectional case study; adult (n=291); Colombia	Novel immune biomarkers: In goldminers with higher Hg exposure, urine, blood and hair Hg was not correlated with anti-nuclear antibodies (ANA) or rheumatoid factor.	(Sánchez Rodríguez et al., 2015)
2	Cross-sectional case study on gold miners; adults (n=884; mean age = 1502); Zimbabwe, Mongolia, Indonesia, Tanzania, & Philippines	Classical neurodevelopmental/behaviour biomarkers: Relevant indicators for Chronic Inorganic Mercury Intoxication were determined (<u>metallic taste, excessive salivation, tremor, sleeping problems, discoloration of oral cavity, ataxia of gait, , dysdiadochokinesia, heel to shin ataxia, proteinuria, matchbox test, and the pencil taping</u>).	(Doering et al., 2016)
3	Case study on miners (n=371); Para (Brazil)	Novel immune biomarkers: Average serum autoantibody titers against stimulated by retinoic acid 13, linker for activation of T cells, signal peptide peptidase like 2B, and interferon induced transmembrane protein, GSTA1 and tumor necrosis factor ligand superfamily member 13 were upregulated	(Motts et al., 2014)

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No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
		more than 10-fold in the high mercury/high ANA samples compared to low mercury/low ANA samples.	
4	Cross-sectional study; (n=232; age 15-87); Amazonian region (Brazil)	<p>Novel immune biomarkers:</p> <p><u>Elevated anti-nuclear antibodies (ANA) titers in serum were associated with blood and plasma Hg levels. Proinflammatory (IL-6, IFN-γ, IL-4, IL-7) increased with MeHg exposure but in the subset of the population with elevated ANA, IL-1β, IL-6, IFN-γ, and TNF-α and IL-4 cytokine levels were decreased with MeHg exposure.</u></p> <p>High Hg exposure and a high positive ANA titer had <u>lower pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines</u> than those individuals with low Hg exposure. A <u>positive association between IL-4 levels and plasma and blood Hg. IL-6 and IL-7 serum levels were positively associated with blood, plasma and hair Hg. IFN-γ was positively associated with plasma and blood Hg.</u></p>	(Nyland, Fillion, et al., 2011)
5	Case study on Miners; (n=246); Para (Brazil)	<p>Novel immune biomarkers:</p> <p><u>Elevated titers and prevalence of anti-nuclear autoantibodies (ANA) and anti-nucleolar autoantibodies (ANoA) were found in human populations exposed to mercury in artisanal gold mining. Mercury-exposed gold-miners with detectable ANA or ANoA in serum had significantly higher concentrations of pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1β, TNF-α, and IFN-γ in serum.</u></p>	(Gardner et al., 2010)
6	Longitudinal study; Children (n=4350; age=7-8; 11-12); (South Korea)	<p>Classical immune biomarkers:</p> <p><u>Blood Hg concentrations at 7–8 years of age were associated with an increased risk of asthma at age 11–12. Specifically, Hg concentration was also associated with wheezing, asthma medication use and airway hyperresponsiveness.</u></p>	(Kim et al., 2015)

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4.5 Mycotoxins (INSA and MU)

4.5.1 Fumonisin

The results of the literature survey obtained for Fumonisin and effect biomarkers are presented in the following table.

Table 14: Outputs generated by the literature search of Fumonisin and effect biomarkers and the target health endpoints

Mycotoxin and health endpoint	Search terms*	Total number of papers	Last 10 years (>2008)	Exclusion criteria	Papers included (AOP-related)	Human studies with effect biomarkers
Fumonisin AND cancer	(Fumonisin B1 OR FB1 OR 116355-83-0 OR multiple mycotoxins) AND (((((((("Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Uterine Cervical Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Urologic Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Liver Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Hereditary Breast and Ovarian Cancer Syndrome"[Mesh] OR "Early Detection of Cancer"[Mesh]) OR ("Urogenital Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Testicular Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Endometrial Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Vaginal Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Uterine Neoplasms"[Mesh])) OR ("Prostatic Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Ovarian Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Endocrine Gland Neoplasms"[Mesh])) OR ("Breast Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Neoplasms, Germ Cell and Embryonal"[Mesh] OR "Tumor	627	97	No Fumonisin, review, exposure only, synthesis only, papers in plant or invertebrates	29	3

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Mycotoxin and health endpoint	Search terms*	Total number of papers	Last 10 years (>2008)	Exclusion criteria	Papers included (AOP-related)	Human studies with effect biomarkers
	Microenvironment"[Mesh])) OR ("Thyroid Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Pituitary Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Brain Neoplasms"[Mesh]))) OR (Cancer OR hormone-dependent cancer OR neoplasm OR malignant tumor OR colon neoplasms OR tumor OR tumour))					
Fumonisin AND nephrotoxicity	(Fumonisin B1 OR FB1 OR 116355-83-0 OR multiple mycotoxins) AND ((Kidney OR renal) AND (failure OR disorder OR impairment OR toxicity) OR (Nephrotoxicity OR nephropathy OR nephrosis OR nephrotic OR nephritis))	267	53	No Fumonisin, review, exposure only, synthesis only, papers in plant or invertebrates	9	2
Fumonisin AND hepatotoxicity	(Fumonisin B1 OR FB1 OR 116355-83-0 OR multiple mycotoxins) AND ((Hepatotoxicity OR hepatic OR liver) AND (toxicity OR injury OR impairment OR damage))	333	68	No Fumonisin, review, exposure only, synthesis only, papers in plant or invertebrates	35	2
CRAB search	--human study/epidemiology ----tumor related ----biomarkers	79 5 11				3

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Classical effect biomarkers

In general, the major mechanisms underlying FB1-induced toxicity is its capacity to act as an inhibitor of ceramide synthase, a key enzyme in the biosynthesis of sphingolipids, thereby leading to the disruption of sphingolipids metabolism (reviewed in Riley and Merrill, 2019). Increases in sphinganine (Sa) and decrease in sphingosine (So) levels and their ratio have been used as biomarkers of FB1 effects (Table 15).

In the PubMed search concerning Human Biomonitoring studies that include effect biomarkers, after applying the exclusion criteria previously described (Table 1), a total of 5 studies was identified (Tables 3 and 4). An additional search using CRAB3 text mining for the terms fumonisin and cancer in the last 10 years allowed identifying 3 additional population studies relevant, among 967 hits (Table 4). As to the three works that analyse effect biomarkers associated with cancer (Table 4), two of them describe the level of Sa, So, and Sa/So ratio measured in urine as an adequate effect biomarker (Wangia et al, 2019; Xue et al., 2015). Riley et al (2015) showed a correlation between FB1 intake and changes in Sa 1-P and the Sa 1-P/So 1-P ratio in human blood (Riley et al., 2015). However, other studies concluded that Sa, So, and the Sa/So ratio in serum and urine may not be a valid and sensitive fumonisin biomarkers in human populations (Xu et al., 2010; Cano-Sancho et al., 2011; van der Westhuizen et al., 2015).

Given the conflicting results above referred, no conclusions about the most adequate effect biomarker for FB1 could be drawn.

Table 15: List of effect biomarkers reported for Fumonisin in HBM studies

Effect biomarker	# of studies in the search	Hazard/ Health Outcome
Disruption of sphingolipids metabolism: sphinganine (Sa), sphingosine (So), and Sa/So ratio in urine or blood	6 (Wangia et al, 2019; Xue et al., 2015; Riley et al., 2015; Xu et al., 2010; Cano-Sancho et al., 2011; van der Westhuizen et al., 2015)	Cancer*
	1 (Wangia et al, 2019)	Nephrotoxicity
	2 (Wangia et al, 2019; Domijan et al., 2009)	Hepatotoxicity

* The disruption of the sphingolipids metabolism in FB1-exposed populations has been also associated with neural tube defects in newborns (Riley et al., 2015)

Other classical effect biomarkers described in papers using cell systems or experimental animals include apoptosis, reactive oxygen species (ROS), inflammatory cytokines, and DNA fragmentation (Khalil et al., 2015).

Khalil et al (2015) reported the measurement of liver enzymes, i.e., alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), and creatinine, in serum of rats exposed to FB1, to assess hepatotoxicity and nephrotoxicity. However, these biomarkers were not evaluated in the set of HBM studies surveyed.

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Novel putative effect biomarkers

No novel effect biomarkers were identified in epidemiological studies concerning FB1 exposure. In contrast, several in vitro reports have evidenced some endpoints that may be promising for future development and application. In vitro studies have pointed to alterations in DNA methylation (Chuturgoon et al., 2014), CYP1A activity and CYP1A transcription (Chuturgoon, Phulukdaree and Moodley 2014), Ahr activity, MiR27b expression, mitochondria and deregulation of calcium signaling and expression of HLA class I heavy chain and/or defects of LMP2 and TAP1 expression, upon FB1 exposure (Yao et al. 2011). However, it must be stressed that all these references concern studies in target cells, such as kidney and liver, and not in human samples in the context of HBM studies. Thus, much work has still to be performed before some of these endpoints may be considered effect biomarkers associated to human FB1 exposure.

Conclusions. Selected biomarker(s) and experimental support

The activity of ALT, AST, ALP and creatinine appear as very unspecific effect biomarkers associated with hepatotoxicity and nephrotoxicity, respectively. Since FB1 has been recognised as an inhibitor of ceramide synthase, involved in lipid metabolism, the sphingolipid metabolism is the most reliable and specific effect biomarker to use. However, few (3) HBM studies using this biomarker have been reported and thereby, it still needs validation in epidemiological studies. Conversely, other studies in humans do not support the correlation of Sa, So, and Sa/So ratio with the FB1 exposure or effect. Furthermore, potential individual susceptibilities need to be ascertained since, for example, altered sphingolipid metabolism has been associated also with asthma phenotype (Kowal et al., 2019). An advantage of using Sa, So, and Sa/So ratio is that several methods are already available to measure these parameters in blood or urine. However, further epidemiological research is necessary to prove both, the association between FB1 exposure and altered Sa/So ratio and the association of this biomarkers with a health effect, e.g., hepatocellular carcinoma.

4.5.2 Deoxynivalenol (DON)

The results of the literature survey obtained for DON and effect biomarkers are presented in the following table.

Table 16: Outputs generated by the literature search of DON and the target health endpoints

Mycotoxin and health endpoint	Search terms*	Total number of papers	10 years old (>2008)	Exclusion criteria	Papers included (AOP-related)	Human studies with effect biomarkers
Deoxynivalenol AND Immune System AND Allergy	(Deoxynivalenol OR 51481-10-8 OR multiple mycotoxins) AND ("Allergy and Immunology"[Mesh] OR "Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR "Rhinitis, Allergic, Seasonal"[Mesh] OR "Food Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR "Drug	552	274	No DON, review, exposure only, synthesis only, papers in plant or invertebrates	178	1

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Mycotoxin and health endpoint	Search terms*	Total number of papers	10 years old (>2008)	Exclusion criteria	Papers included (AOP-related)	Human studies with effect biomarkers
	Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR "Shellfish Hypersensitivity"[Mesh] OR Allergy OR Hypersensitive OR respiratory allergy OR gastrointestinal allergy OR multiple chemical sensitivity OR allergic hypersensitivity disease OR contact allergy OR "Immune System"[Mesh] OR "Immune System Diseases"[Mesh] OR Immune system OR autoimmune disease OR cytokines OR white cells OR innate immune system OR adaptive immune system)					
Deoxynivalenol AND Reproductive	(Deoxynivalenol OR 51481-10-8) AND (reproductive OR puberty OR pregnancy OR infertility OR semen quality OR placenta OR anogenital distance OR hypospadias OR cryptorchidism OR "Reproductive Health"[Mesh] OR "Reproductive Medicine"[Mesh] OR "Reproduction"[Mesh] OR "Reproductive Techniques, Assisted"[Mesh] OR "Infertility"[Mesh])	161	100	No DON, review, exposure only, synthesis only, papers in plant or invertebrates	45	0
Deoxynivalenol AND Endocrine	(Deoxynivalenol OR 51481-10-8) AND ("Endocrine	80	50	No DON, review, exposure only,	40	0

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Mycotoxin and health endpoint	Search terms*	Total number of papers	10 years old (>2008)	Exclusion criteria	Papers included (AOP-related)	Human studies with effect biomarkers
	System"[Mesh] OR "Endocrine Glands"[Mesh] OR "Endocrine System Diseases"[Mesh] OR "Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Gonadal Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Placental Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Pituitary Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Growth Hormone"[Mesh] OR "Thyroid Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Gastrointestinal Hormones"[Mesh] OR "Sex Hormone-Binding Globulin"[Mesh] OR "Adrenocorticotrophic Hormone"[Mesh] OR "Adrenal Cortex Hormones"[Mesh] OR Endocrine system OR hypothyroidism OR hyperthyroidism OR adrenal)			synthesis only, papers in plant or invertebrates		
CRAB search	--human study/epidemiology ----tumor related ----biomarkers	215 3 8	172 (all ref. pooled)	HBM, quantification in Food, review, risk assessment, DON synthesis	13	4 (incl. 1 found in PubMed searches)

Deoxynivalenol (DON) is a toxic fungal metabolite that frequently contaminates cereal crops including wheat, maize and barley. Despite knowledge of frequent exposure through diet, the current understanding of the potential consequences of human exposure remains limited, in part due to the lack of validated exposure biomarkers.

The literature search conducted in PubMed to associate DON exposure to health endpoints, which included immunotoxicity, reprotoxicity and endocrine disruption, retrieved a single study. This study associated exposure to DON, among other mycotoxins assessed (e.g., aflatoxin M1, ochratoxin A

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and fumonisin B1), with autism spectrum disorders (deSantis et al., 2017). In addition, weak associations were found between the level of mycotoxins (including DON) in the body and a group of IgGs against fungal and food antigens or a group of cytokines/chemokines of pro-inflammatory signals. These parameters, which reflect the immune system response, may be potentially used as effect biomarkers for DON and neurobehavioral diseases, like autism. However, the evidences from the literature are still scarce and need to be verified.

The application of the CRAB tool allowed the identification of 3 references that had not been retrieved in the PubMed search but only one of them provided valuable information about the use of effect biomarkers. In that study, the urinary metabolome was characterised by nuclear magnetic resonance coupled with multivariate statistical analysis. Metabolic profiling suggested that hippurate levels were correlated with DON exposure and potential health effects in humans (Hopton et al., 2010).

4.5.3 Conclusions

Even though the number of Human Biomonitoring studies about human exposure to mycotoxins, including FB1 and DON has been increasing in the last decade, only very few of them have included the analysis of effect biomarkers. Concerning FB1, the only specific effect biomarker that has been reported to date is the measurement of sphingolipids in blood or urine, relying on the recognised mechanism of toxicity of this substance. Nonetheless, the sensitivity of this biomarker is still a matter of debate. On the other hand, diverse in vitro and a few in vivo studies have been better characterising the cellular and molecular mechanism of action of FB1, particularly, its genotoxicity and tumor promoting activity. These works have pointed to some endpoints and methodological approaches, e.g., gene expression or gene methylation analyses, that deserve to be further explored in an attempt to discover novel effect biomarkers. Regarding DON, a single study referring the use off effect biomarkers related to its immunotoxicity and autism was retrieved.

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4.6 Pesticides excluding organophosphates (INSERM/CNRS/VITO/UGR)

4.6.1 Chlorpyrifos, Organophosphates (UGR)

Chlorpyrifos is an organophosphate pesticide that inhibits the acetylcholinesterase, thus causing poisoning through a collapse of the central nervous system of the insect. The World Health Organization (WHO) considers this pesticide moderately hazardous to humans. Based on its acute toxicity and its chronic exposure, chlorpyrifos has been associated with neurological effects and developmental and autoimmune disorders. It is widely used for agriculture and in domestic gardens, although its employment is forbidden in food industry and for the manufacture of biocides.

Figure 6: Flow-chart on chlorpyrifos in PubMed data base

4.6.1.1 Neurodevelopment Health Endpoint

Classical Effect Biomarkers: Diverse epidemiological studies have found a significant negative association between the levels of CPS, concretely 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol and a downregulation of the butyrylcholinesterase and acetylcholinesterase (Berents et al., 2014; Crane et al., 2013; Ellison et al., 2012).

Novel Effect Biomarkers: In this case-control study with idiopathic Parkinson's Disease (PD) patients exposed to CPS, polymorphism of the PON1 gene: PON1Q192R, PON1192QQ and PON155MM had largest ORs for PD. Finally, Potera et al., found that children exposed in utero had an enlargement of some regions of the brain, with an increase of the glia or white matter and, in girls, the reduction of the parietal lobe (Potera, 2012).

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Table 17: Effect biomarkers for chlorpyrifos and neurodevelopment health endpoint

No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
1	n=140; children aged 6-9 years from Puerto Rico. Cross-sectional study.	Higher urinary TCPy concentrations were associated with poorer working memory in boys, poorer visual motor coordination, increased prevalence of parent-reported cognitive problems/inattention, oppositional disorders and ADHD and decreased ability to discriminate colors.	van Wendel de Joode et al., 2013
2	n=53 CPF workers and 60 referent workers, 41.2 and 41.3 years respectively. A longitudinal prospective study from The United States.	CPF workers had significantly greater CPF exposures during the study period than did referents at levels where physiologic effects on plasma butyrylcholinesterase (BuChE) activity were apparent and with higher 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol (TCPy/Cr) urinary excretion ($p<0.0001$) and lower average BuChE activity ($p<0.01$)	Berents et al., 2014
3	Cases n= 287; controls n = 440 with 69.0 and 67.6 years respectively. Case-control study with idiopathic Parkinson's disease (PD)patients from three rural agricultural counties in California (USA)	The odds ratio (OR) for Caucasians exposed to OPs at either residential or workplace addresses varied by PON1 genotype ; for exposed carriers of the "faster" metabolizer genotypes, ML or LL, we estimated lower odds ratios (range, 1.20-1.39) than for exposed carriers of the "slower" metabolizer genotype MM (range, 1.78-2.45) relative to unexposed carriers of the faster genotypes. We observed similarly increased ORs for exposure across PON1Q192R genotypes , but no differences across PON1C-108T genotypes. The largest ORs were estimated for exposed carriers of both PON1192QQ and PON155MM (OR range, 2.84-3.57)	Lee et al., 2013
4	Adolescent pesticide applicators (n=57; 2-21 years of age) and age-matched non-applicators (n=38) from the same villages were followed for 10 months in 2010. Case-control study from Egypt.	Applicators demonstrated significantly higher 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol (TCPy) concentration and Blood acetylcholinesterase and butyrylcholinesterase (BChE) depression than non-applicators. Both groups exhibited significantly elevated TCPy and depressed BChE , compared with their respective baseline	Crane et al., 2013
5	n= 120 Egypt's workers were chosen in order to determine the influence of PON1 genotype on the activity of blood cholinesterase as well as the effect of CPF exposure on serum PON1 in workers occupationally exposed to CPF	Workers had significantly inhibited AChE and BuChE after CPF application; however, neither CPOase activity nor POase activity was associated with ChE depression when adjusted for CPF exposure (as determined by urinary TCPy levels) and stratified by PON1 genotype.	Ellison et al., 2012
6	Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) data for 40 children at age 6–11 years half of whom had umbilical plasma CPF levels of 4.39 pg/g or greater and half of whom had levels below 4.39 pg/g. Columbia Center for Children's Environmental Health (CCCEH)	Children in the higher-exposed group were more likely to have significant enlargement of the regions of the brain that control attention, language, social cognition (e.g., ability to recognise faces), emotion and inhibition, and executive functions (e.g., planning and reasoning), compared with the lower-exposed group. Much of the brain enlargement consisted of glia, or white matter . Higher CPF exposure also was associated with reduction or reversal of normal sex-related differences in brain development. For instance, the right parietal lobe is generally larger in girls than boys, but this was reversed in higher-exposed children	Potera, 2012
7	n=221 mothers and 244 children. In addition, 219 of these women and 236 of the newborns had adequate samples available for PON1 enzyme activity measurements in maternal and umbilical cord blood. Data from the CHAMACOS study, USA.	Significant associations between organophosphate pesticide levels in blood and metabolite levels in urine were limited to models adjusting for PON1 levels. Increased maternal PON1 levels were associated with decreased odds of chlorpyrifos and diazinon detection.	Huen et al., 2012

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4.6.1.2 Reproductive Health Endpoint:

Classical Effect Biomarkers: From the abstract-preliminary selected studies, just one study from the Odense Child Cohort study (Denmark) was selected. It found an association between the maternal levels of 3-PBA and shorter abdominal circumference in females, while no associations were found for elongation of the anogenital-distance (AGD).

Novel Effect Biomarkers: Non-novel effect biomarkers were found for this health outcome.

Table 18: Effect biomarkers for chlorpyrifos and reproductive health endpoint

No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
1	n=858; participants from the Odense Child Cohort (OCC), Denmark	Maternal urinary 3-PBA concentration associated with <u>shorter abdominal circumference</u> in females. A non-significant dose-related elongation of anogenital distance (AGD) in females was seen for 3-PBA and diethyl phosphates.	Dalsager et al., 2018

4.6.1.3. Endocrine Health Endpoint

Classical Effect Biomarkers: Two selected epidemiological studies from the same cohort, NHANES, found a downregulation of the thyroxine in men and women and no association with free and total triiodothyronine and thyroglobulin with urinary levels of TCPY. However, they got different results with the thyroid-stimulating hormone: Jain et al., 2017 did not found any association while Fortenberry et colleagues found a negative association in men at 18-40 years old and >60 years old while; in females, they found a positive association between TSH and TCPY in women older than 60 years (Jain, 2017; Fortenberry et al., 2012).

Novel Effect Biomarkers: For this health endpoint, no novel effect biomarker has been found.

Table 19: Effect biomarkers for chlorpyrifos and endocrine health endpoint

No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
1	Data from National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) for the years 2007-2008 were used to evaluate the association between serum levels of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), free triiodothyronine (FT3), free thyroxine (FT4), total triiodothyronine (TT3), total thyroxine (TT4), and thyroglobulin (TGN) with the urinary levels of 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol (TCPY). 1064 males and 951 females from more than 12 to 65 years.	TCPY levels were not found to be associated with the levels of TSH, FT3, FT4, and TT3 for either males or females. TCPY levels in the third tertile as compared to first tertile were found to be negatively associated ($p \leq 0.01$) with TT4 levels for both males and females. TGN levels for those males who were in third tertile of TCPY were statistically significantly lower ($p < 0.01$) than for those who had their TCPY levels in first or second tertile	Jain, 2017
2	3249 children and adults from NHANES. The aim of this study was to examine circulating T4 and TSH levels in relation to urinary concentrations of 3, 5, 6-trichloro-2-pyridinol (TCPY). NHANES 1999-2002	In male participants, an interquartile range (IQR) increase in urinary TCPY was associated with statistically significant increases in serum T(4) of 3.8% (95th CI 0.75 to 7.0) among those 12-18 years of age and 3.5% (95th CI 0.13 to 7.0) in the 18-40 year age group, relative to median T4 levels using unweighted models. An IQR increase in TCPY was also associated with decreases in TSH of 10.7% (-18.7-2.05) among men 18-40 years old and 20.0% (95th CI -28.9 to -9.86) among men >60 years old. Conversely, urinary TCPY was positively associated with TSH in females >60 years of age.	Fortenberry et al., 2012

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4.6.1.4 Metabolic Health Endpoint

Classical Effect Biomarker: In one study, we found data regarding neurodevelopment and no metabolic diseases, which were 6 neurodevelopmental tests (Rohlman et al., 2016).

Novel Effect Biomarker: There was not any novel effect biomarker for this health outcome.

Table 20: Effect biomarkers for chlorpyrifos and metabolic health endpoint

No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
1	The aim of the study was to examine the impact of chlorpyrifos exposure on neurobehavioral performance in 95 Egyptian adolescents (57 applicators and 38 non-applicators) at 12–21 years old before, during and after the application season.	The tests with significant differences at multiple intervals include tests assessing psychomotor and <u>executive function</u> (i.e., Tapping, Symbol-Digit), fine motor (i.e., Santa Ana), and working memory and attention (i.e., Serial Digit Learning, <u>Digit Span</u> , Selective Attention). Furthermore, these effects persisted for five months after application had ended.	Rohlman et al., 2016
2	Analyse the exposure level and metabolic characteristics of chlorpyrifos pesticide in 45 urban adults and 60 farmers with/without occupation pesticide contact. China	Significant increase of urinary 8-hydroxydeoxyguanosine (8-OHdG) was observed on the first day after chlorpyrifos spraying, which indicates a potential oxidative damage in farmers. However, urinary 8-OHdG returned to its baseline level within two days	Wang et al., 2016

4.6.1.5 Multiple Endpoints

All studies found in this section were related to neurodevelopment.

Classical Effect Biomarkers: Anthropometric measurements, such as the head circumference (HC) was associated with the exposure to Chlorpyrifos (Silver et al., 2018). Additionally, several classical neurodevelopmental scales have been successfully used and associated with pre/postnatal exposure to Chlorpyrifos and children neurodevelopment disorders such as the Trail Making B, the Archimedes Spirals (for motor function), Conners' Parental Rating Scales-Revised (CRS-R), Conners' Continuous Performance Test (CPT), Behavior Assessment System for Children-2 (BASC-2), the Griffiths mental developmental scale and the Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children Fourth edition (WISC-IV) (Ismail et al., 2017; Rauh et al., 2015; Fortenberry et al., 2013; Ostrea et al., 2012 and Rauh et al 2012). Furthermore, butyrylcholinesterase has been negatively associated with the exposure to this pesticide (Ismail et al., 2017)

Novel Effect Biomarkers: From Silver et al, the visual acuity score, could be a novel scale to be integrated in HBM programs (Silver et al., 2018). Several brain regions had been morphologically altered by the exposure to this chemical (Rauh et al., 2012), thus MIRs could be a feasible effect biomarker for neurodevelopmental diseases.

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Table 21: Effect biomarkers for chlorpyrifos and multiple health endpoints

No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
1	359 women with healthy, uncomplicated, singleton pregnancies were enrolled into a longitudinal study from Fuyang Maternal and Children's Hospital between 2008 and 2011, China	Prenatal chlorpyrifos exposure was associated with lower 9-month grating visual acuity (VA) scores; scores were 0.64 (95% CI: -1.22, -0.06) points lower for exposed versus unexposed infants ($p = 0.03$). The chlorpyrifos and phorate examined were significantly inversely associated head circumference (HC) at 9 months;	Silver et al., 2018
2	To compare neurological outcomes from two cohorts of Egyptian adolescents working as pesticide applicators	Except for one test (Trail Making B), there were no significant differences between either applicators or non-applicators of both cohorts on the neurobehavioral outcome measures ($p > 0.05$). The 2005 cohort showed greater inhibition of serum BChE activity than the 2009 cohort ($p < 0.05$). In addition, participants with depressed BChE activity showed more symptoms and signs than others without BChE depression ($p < 0.05$).	Ismail et al., 2017
3	Prenatal exposure to CPF was evaluated in 263 inner-city at approximately 11 years of age on order to test possible associations with motor dysfunction. Prospective study, USA	At the age of 11 years, children were asked to draw the Archimedes spirals in order to evaluate possible motor function dysregulation. Children with prenatal CPF exposure in the upper quartile range ($n=43$) were more likely to exhibit mild or mild to moderate tremor (≥ 1) in either arm ($p=0.03$), both arms ($p=0.02$), the dominant arm ($p=0.01$), and the non-dominant arm ($p=0.055$). Logistic regression analyses showed significant CPF effects on tremor in both arms, either arm, the dominant arm (p -values < 0.05), and the non-dominant arm ($p=0.06$), after adjustment for sex, age at testing, ethnicity, and medication	Rauh et al., 2015
4	From 187 mother-child pairs the tested the association between in utero exposure to chlorpyrifos, chlorpyrifos-methyl, and/or 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol (TCPY) and ADHD in school-age Mexican children at 11 years of age. Early Life Exposures in Mexico to Environmental Toxicants (ELEMENT) study.	They did not observe any statistically significant associations between tertiles of maternal TCPY concentrations and ADHD-related outcomes in children. However, compared to the lowest tertile we found suggestive evidence for increased ADHD index in the highest TCPY tertile in boys and increased attention problems for the middle tertile in girls. Neurodevelopmental test employed were: Conners' Parental Rating Scales-Revised (CRS-R) , Conners' Continuous Performance Test (CPT) , and Behavior Assessment System for Children-2 (BASC-2)	Fortenberry et al., 2013
5	They investigated associations between prenatal CPF exposure and brain morphology using magnetic resonance imaging in 40 children, from 5.9 to 11.2 years old.	High CPF exposure was associated with enlargement of superior temporal, posterior middle temporal, and inferior postcentral gyri bilaterally , and enlarged superior frontal gyrus, gyrus rectus, cuneus, and precuneus along the mesial wall of the right hemisphere. High-exposure children also showed frontal and parietal cortical thinning , and an inverse dose-response relationship between CPF and cortical thickness .	Rauh et al., 2012
6	Mothers were prospectively recruited during mid-pregnancy in Bulacan, Philippine and children ($N=754$) were assessed at 2 year of age.	Infants were examined at 2 years of age and their neurodevelopment outcome was assessed by the Griffiths mental developmental scale . No significant association between chlorpyrifos and motor development in children	Ostrea et al., 2012
7	265 children at 7-year of age. Columbia Center for Children's Environmental Health	Neurodevelopmental status were assessed using the Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children, 4th edition (WISC-IV). For each standard deviation increase in CPF exposure (4.61 pg/g), Full-Scale intelligence quotient (IQ) declined by 1.4% and Working Memory declined by 2.8%	Rauh et al., 2011

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4.6.2 Dimethoate, Organophosphates (UGR)

Dimethoate is a widely used organophosphate (OP) insecticide and acaricide on several agricultural crops, tree crops, and ornamentals. Like other OPs, dimethoate is an acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibitor, leading to acetylcholine accumulation, hyperstimulation of nicotinic and muscarinic receptors, and disrupted neurotransmission.

Reproduction N=5	Excluded articles Risk assessment: 2 Ecotoxicology: 1	Included articles Effect biomarker: 2
Neurodevelopment N=8	Excluded articles Risk assessment: 1 Ecotoxicology: 1 Other: 5	Included articles Effect biomarker: 1
Metabolic N=8	Excluded articles Review: 1 Exposure: 1 In vivo: 1 Ecotoxicology: 1 Other: 2	Included articles Effect biomarker: 2
Immune N=1	Excluded articles 0	Included articles Effect biomarker: 1
Endocrine N=2	Excluded articles Other: 2	Included articles Effect biomarker: 0
Cancer N=3	Excluded articles Risk assessment: 3	Included articles Effect biomarker: 0
Multiple endpoints N=7	Excluded articles In vivo: 1 Other: 1	Included articles Effect biomarker: 5 (IN VITRO - human cells)

Figure 7: Flow-chart for Dimethoate search on PubMed data base

In plants and in the environment, dimethoate occurs as a break down product within a few days after dimethoate application. In humans, dimethoate is absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract, the lungs, and through the skin. Among professional pesticide applicators and formulators, dimethoate exposure can occur by skin contact or from inhaling aerosols or dust. Workers in treated fields can have exposure to dimethoate, omethoate, or both by skin contact. Dimethoate is widely distributed to body tissues and metabolised in the liver to omethoate via the cytochrome P450 enzyme system, which is then rapidly broken down to several methylated dialkyl phosphate (DAP) metabolites that are eliminated in urine within 1-2 days.

In animal studies, inhibition of erythrocyte AChE appeared to be the most sensitive indicator of dimethoate exposure and toxicity. High doses of dimethoate, omethoate, and other OP pesticides result in excess acetylcholine at nerve terminals. Acute cholinergic symptoms include nausea, vomiting, weakness, paralysis, and seizures. Dimethoate has moderate acute toxicity in mammals (e.g., the LD50 in mice and rats is 150 and 400 mg/kg bodyweight, respectively), while omethoate is about 10 times more toxic and a more potent cholinesterase inhibitor than dimethoate. Chronic exposure to dimethoate and other OP insecticides may also adversely affect the central nervous system.

Carcinogenicity studies in animals have been inconsistent. While the U.S. EPA classified dimethoate as a possible human carcinogen, the International Agency for Research on Cancer

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(IARC) has not evaluated dimethoate or omethoate with regard to human carcinogenicity. Dimethoate is considered mutagenic, but it is not a teratogen. Reproductive toxicity was seen at doses that also caused overt maternal toxicity.

The following chart summarises the dimethoate-related human studies retrieved from Pubmed and their classification following Abstract screening. A total 34 articles were retrieved, out of which 11 studies reported effect biomarkers in human matrices.

Table 22: Summary of dimethoate-related human studies for all health outcomes

No	Endpoint	Human/ in vitro	Exposure assessment	Outcome/effect biomarker	Main observations	Reference
1	Reproduction	Human (case-control)	Pesticide application within 500 m radius of maternal residence in early pregnancy	Hypospadias in male newborns	OR=2.45 (1.36–4.39) for <1.34 pounds of dimethoate applied vs. no exposure	Carmichael et al., 2013
2	Reproduction	Human (cross-sectional)	Exposed vs. non-exposed villages (women and children <12 yrs) - high levels of dimethoate and other pesticides in ground water of exposed villages.	Spontaneous abortion, premature births; Children: language delay, blue line in gums, mottling of teeth and gastrointestinal problems.	Outcomes frequencies were higher in exposed vs. non-exposed villages.	Thakur et al., 2010
3	Neurodevelopment	Human (case-control)	Consumption of private-well water polluted with pesticides	Parkinson's disease (PD)	No association between possible well-water contamination with dimethoate and risk of PD	Gatto et al., 2009
4	Metabolic	In vitro	Human serum albumin after intoxication with dimethoate and omethoate	Tyrosine adducts (o,o-dimethyl phosphotyrosine and o,o-dimethyl thiophosphotyrosine) and disulfide adduct (cysteine-proline dipeptide)	Results demonstrated suitability of these biomarkers for sensitive verification of human poisoning with OPs.	Kranawetvogl et al., 2018
5	Metabolic	Human	Occupational exposure to OP pesticides (farmers vs. non-farmers)	Erythrocyte AChE	Study protocol (not specifically focused on dimethoate)	Cotton et al., 2005
6	Immune system	Human (cross-sectional)	Occupational exposure to omethoate (exposed workers vs. non-exposed)	Relative telomere length (RTL) in peripheral blood leukocytes DNA and polymorphisms of encoding miRNA genes.	Prolongation of RTL in exposed workers associated with AG+GG genotypes in rs353291 polymorphism of encoding miR-145 gene.	Wang et al., 2019
7	Multiple endpoints	In vitro	Effect of dimethoate in human peripheral blood lymphocytes	Citotoxicity: malondialdehyde (MDA) and protein thiol levels, and superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase activities	Dimethoate caused increase in MDA, decrease in protein thiol levels, and increase in SOD and catalase activities at different concentrations.	Gargouri et al., 2011
8	Multiple	Human (cross-	Occupational exposure to	Relative telomere length (RTL) and	Prolonged RTL in exposed workers, and	Duan et

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No	Endpoint	Human/ in vitro	Exposure assessment	Outcome/effect biomarker	Main observations	Reference
	endpoints	sectional)	omethoate (exposed workers vs. non-exposed)	telomere length of CA genotype polymorphism locus	higher telomere length of CA genotype individuals of p21 rs1801270 polymorphism locus compared to CC genotype in the control group	al., 2017
9	Multiple endpoints	In vitro	Effect of dimethoate and chlorpyrifos on human dendritic cells	Immunotoxicity: dendrites of DC, cytokine IL-10 (anti-inflammatory), protein kinases - Akt family, ERK	Shortened and damaged dendrites, downregulation of cytokine IL-10, and inhibition of protein kinases I (DIM+CHLOR)	Schäfer et al., 2013
10	Multiple endpoints	In vitro	Effect of dimethoate on deiodinase using SH-SY5Y cells	Gene expression of T3-treated and deiodinase-knockdown SH-SY5Y cells	Dimethoate altered 10 genes	Song et al., 2013
11	Multiple endpoints	In vitro	Oxidative stress induced by dimethoate in human erythrocytes	MDA levels, and SOD and catalase (CAT) activities	Dimethoate caused increase in MDA levels, and SOD and catalase activities.	Abdallah et al., 2011

4.6.3 Fipronil (CNRS)

Fipronil is a broad-spectrum insecticide and acaricide of the phenylpyrazole family. It is widely used in crop protection due to its systemic nature, in urban areas for insect control and in veterinary practice. Its neurotoxicity arises from non-competitive blocking of gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA)-gated chloride channels resulting in excessive neuronal stimulation and death. Its specificity for target organisms derives from its higher affinity for invertebrate GABA-A and GABA-C receptors than those of mammals. Fipronil is metabolised by CYP3A4 to Fipronil-sulfone which is relatively more biologically active and considerably more toxic, persistent, bioaccumulative and less selective than the parent compound.

Adverse effects have been found in numerous non-target organisms including beneficial insects such as bees and termites, and vertebrates including fishes, reptiles, birds, and mammals. In addition to oncogenicity concerns following induced thyroid follicular cell tumours in rats, Fipronil has been shown to cause adverse effects on the central nervous system in animal studies or in neuroblastoma cell lines. Fipronil can induce transient behavioral and neurological impairment in rodents, neurotoxic symptoms such as seizures and vomiting in humans after acute poisoning, and disrupt the thyroid axis in animal models, occupational workers and newborns.

The following flow-chart summarises the pyrethroid-related human studies retrieved from Pubmed and their classification following Abstract screening. A total 32 articles were retrieved, out of which, only 1 study reported effect biomarkers in human matrices and concerned thyroid hormones in occupational workers.

Figure 8: Flow-chart on Fipronil search in PubMed data base

Note: An additional article pertaining to fipronil's effect in human studies entitled “*Distribution of fipronil in humans, and adverse health outcomes of in utero fipronil sulfone exposure in newborns*” was not retrieved using our search strategy, possibly due to a lack of Mesh terms associated to the article and not being classified in either “human” or “other animals” species in pubmed (Kim et al., 2019). This article can be retrieved using following title screening without preliminary species screening.

4.6.3.1 Endocrine and developmental Health Endpoints

Only two epidemiological studies reported effect biomarkers for Fipronil

Classical endocrine biomarkers: Thyroid-Stimulating Hormone (TSH) in serum; Triiodothyronine (T3) and free T3 in cord serum

Table 23: Classical developmental biomarkers - Agpar scoring

No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
1	n=159 men and women from a factory manufacturing fipronil-containing veterinary drug; mean age = 34; France	Fipronil sulfone was negatively correlated with TSH levels in serum of fipronil-exposed workers	(Herin et al., 2011)
2	n=59 pregnant woman-newborn pairs; mean age = 32; Korea	In cord blood serum, fipronil sulfone levels were negatively correlated with T3 and free T3 levels, and 5-min Apgar scores (a marker for developmental vulnerability) were inversely associated with infantile fipronil sulfone levels	(Kim et al., 2019)

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The effects of fipronil on the Hypothalamus-Pituitary-Thyroid axis are substantiated by *in vivo* and *in vitro* evidence. Fipronil exposure decreased circulating thyroid hormone levels in rats, at least partially mediated by increased clearance following elevated activity and expression of phase II hepatic enzymes (Leghait et al., 2009; Moser et al., 2015; B. B. Roques et al., 2012; B. Roques, Leghait, Martin, Pineau, & Viguie, 2013; Viguie et al., 2013). Using *in vitro* reporting gene assays, fipronil-sulfone showed antagonistic activity via TR β in a dose-dependent manner, suggestive of another potential mechanism of action for fipronil's thyroid disrupting effect (Lu et al., 2015).

4.6.4 Glyphosate (VITO)

The Appendix summarises all information related to glyphosate, glyphosate-based herbicides, or AMPA retrieved from epidemiological studies, experimental *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies, and AOP Wiki. The main findings are described below.

Figure 9: Flow-chart on glyphosate search on PubMed data base

4.6.4.1 Classic effect biomarkers

Cancer: Only one epidemiological study was retrieved, which showed an association of glyphosate exposure with a high risk of melanoma. Oxidative stress and DNA damage were observed in different types of human cells *in vitro* as well as in fish, although absence of DNA damage in PBMCs at low or realistic glyphosate exposure was also reported. AMPA demonstrated anti-carcinogenic effects via cell cycle arrest and apoptosis *in vitro* and in a mouse model.

Immune system: One epidemiological study found an inverse association of glyphosate use with exacerbation of asthma symptoms, which may have been confounded by avoidance of glyphosate use by asthma cases prone to exacerbation. Inhalation of glyphosate caused an inflammatory immune response in lungs of mice. Immunosuppressive effects were decreased viability of human PBMCs at high concentrations and altered interleukin-1 β , interleukin-10, and heme oxygenase-1 expression in fish.

Neurobehaviour: Premature mortality from Parkinson's disease and the occurrence of autism spectrum disorder were associated with glyphosate exposure in humans. In rats, oxidative stress and apoptosis were observed in the brain. *In vivo* studies showed effects of glyphosate on

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locomotor activity, anxiety, memory, and depressive-like behavior. Deregulation of the dopaminergic, glutamatergic and/or cholinergic systems and oxidative stress may be involved. Glyphosate was reported to inhibit acetylcholinesterase in several experimental studies. In *C. elegans* and in fish, glyphosate impaired neuronal development, potentially through oxidative stress.

Metabolism: No epidemiological studies related to metabolic disorders were found. In rats, blood glucose and serum insulin levels increased and in mice, glyphosate inhibited liver fatty acid oxidation enzymes and increased the levels of triglycerides and cholesteryl esters. In fish, effects on glucose levels in liver, muscle and plasma, energy metabolism, protein and amino acid metabolism and nucleosides metabolism, and on glycogen, total lipid, cholesterol and triglyceride levels were observed.

Endocrine disruption: Hypothyroidism risk was associated with glyphosate use in an epidemiological study. Both increased and decreased TSH levels were reported in rats. Contradicting effects of glyphosate on serum testosterone levels in rats were published.

Reproduction: Epidemiological studies showed an association of glyphosate in urine with shortened gestational length and an increased number of miscarriages in areas in which glyphosate was sprayed. In rats, altered development and functioning of the uterus was observed and related to embryo losses. Female fertility was affected in in vivo studies: glyphosate impaired folliculogenesis and ovary development and function, decreased estrogen and progesterone secretion, and caused oxidative stress and histological alterations in ovaries.

Ex vivo exposure to a high glyphosate concentration reduced human sperm progressive motility; decreased sperm quality and quantity was also observed after exposure of murine germ cells and Sertoli cells, mice, rats, and fish. In rats, these effects were accompanied by altered serum levels of reproductive hormones (testosterone, luteinizing hormone (LH), follicle stimulating hormone (FSH) and prolactin). Ca(2+) overload, cell signaling misregulation, stress response of the endoplasmic reticulum, and/or depleted antioxidant defenses could contribute to Sertoli cell spermatogenesis disruption in rats. Some studies reported apoptosis or necrosis in testicular cells. Equivocal results with respect to the role of oxidative stress in testicular tissue were reported.

4.6.4.2 Novel effect biomarkers

Novel molecular or biochemical effect biomarkers were not reported in epidemiological studies, except for serum S100B as a predictor of neurologic complications in patients with acute glyphosate poisoning. Experimental studies showed the following:

Cancer: Deregulation of calcyclin, calgranulin-B upregulation, and down-regulation of superoxide dismutase were observed in murine skin. In vitro studies reported increased estrogen signaling and altered ER α , ER β , VEGFR2, pERK, PI3K(p85), and PCNA expression in breast cancer cells.

Immune system: No novel effect biomarkers were reported.

Neurobehaviour: One in vitro study showed induction of autophagy and apoptotic pathways (with possible involvement of the Beclin-1 gene) in neuronal cells, while another one did not find evidence for triggering of molecular events involved in the development of Parkinson's disease.

Metabolism: Glyphosate inhibited adipogenesis by inhibition of PPAR gamma induction and inhibition of proliferation in murine (pre)adipocytes.

Endocrine disruption: In rats, genes regulated by thyroid hormones or involved in thyroid hormone metabolism and transport showed altered expression: reduction of deiodinases 2 (Dio2) and 3 (Dio3) and TH transporters Slco1c1 (former Oatp1c1) and Slc16a2 (former Mct8) in hypothalamus;

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induction of Dio2, thyroid hormone receptor genes (Thra1 and Thrb1), and Slc16a2 in the pituitary; induction of Thra1 and Thrb1 in liver. In male rats, glyphosate increased ESR1 expression.

Reproduction: Local gene expression changes were observed in rats related to uterine organogenetic differentiation (PR, Hoxa10, Erα, Wnt7a), uterus signaling (Wnt5a, Wnt7a, β-catenin, Dkk1 and sFRP4), and embryonal implantation (estrogen and progesterone receptors, Nr2f2, and Bmp2, Ki67 (Mki67), and HOXA10). Interference with progesterone and estrogen secretion was related to altered steroidogenesis-related genes expression (GnRH, LHR, FSHR, 3β-HSD and Cyp19a1) in pregnant mice. ERα, ERβ, progesterone receptor, and complement 3 expression was affected in uterus of rats. In zebrafish, altered oocyte maturation and ovarian ultrastructure were associated with increased expression of SF-1. Decreased expression of protamine 1 and histone 1 testicular in sperm and increased aromatase expression, Gper1, and blood-testis-barrier markers in testes were observed in rats. XAF1 (X-linked inhibitor of apoptosis-associated factor 1) was reported to play a role in murine male germ cell apoptosis.

4.6.4.3 Selected biomarker(s) and experimental support

Oxidative stress was shown to be involved in effects of glyphosate on DNA damage, neurobehavioural parameters, sperm quantity and quality, and female fertility in experimental studies. Effects on Parkinson's disease were demonstrated in one epidemiological study and experimental studies showed equivocal results. Effects on neurodevelopment were only shown in two experimental studies. AOP 260 shows, however, that oxidative stress may cause neurodegenerative effects. DNA damage related to oxidative stress was only observed in experimental studies but supported by AOP 296.

Behavioural effects were only reported in in vivo studies. A role of deregulation of the glutamatergic system is supported by AOP 13, 17 and 48 and of acetylcholinesterase inhibition in AOP 281.

Effects on estrogen signaling leading to breast cancer were only demonstrated in vitro but supported by AOP 200. In addition, AOP 293 and 294 link oxidative stress and DNA damage to breast cancer. Although no studies reported a role of these events in effects of glyphosate on breast cancer, they are linked to glyphosate in studies on other endpoints. Estrogen receptor methylation, expression, or activation could be used as an effect biomarker for breast cancer, as well as for effects on female fertility. This may be associated with decreased estrogen levels and altered steroidogenic factor 1 (SF-1), ERα and ERβ expression, although this was only reported in experimental studies and not supported by AOPs.

Sperm quality and quantity could be assessed to verify effects found in experimental studies.

Effects on melanoma, the immune system, and hypothyroidism were demonstrated in one epidemiological study and supported by few experimental studies but no AOPs. Two epidemiological studies show an association with pregnancy outcomes, which was supported by experimental studies that did not report systemic effect biomarkers. Two other epidemiological studies showed an association with autism spectrum disorders, but this was not supported by experimental studies or AOPs. Effects on metabolism and endocrine disruption were only reported in experimental studies, the latter with equivocal results, and not supported by AOPs. No specific, novel effect biomarkers were retrieved for these endpoints.

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Table 24: The following table shows effect biomarkers selected for glyphosate exposure linked to the AOP wiki information

Human biomarker of effect	Link of biomarker with exposure and health outcome in epidemiological study	Experimental evidence and suggested mechanisms of action	KE	AO P
Cancer				
Melanoma	Past occupational use of glyphosate was associated with a high risk of cutaneous melanoma (Fortes et al., 2016).	Proteins known to be involved in key carcinogenic processes like apoptosis, growth-inhibition, and anti-oxidant responses were deregulated in glyphosate-treated mouse skin: calcyclin and calgranulin-B upregulation and down-regulation of superoxide dismutase [Cu-Zn] were proposed as effect biomarkers. In addition, effects on translation elongation factor eEF-1 alpha chain , carbonic anhydrase III , annexin II , fab fragment anti-VEGF antibody , peroxiredoxin-2 , and stefin A3 were reported (George, Prasad, Mahmood, & Shukla, 2010). In vitro, glyphosate induced cell membrane stiffening and the appearance of cytoskeleton structures at a subcellular level in keratinocytes (Heu, Berquand, Elie-Caille, & Nicod, 2012).	-	-
Breast cancer	-	Glyphosate stimulated breast cancer cell proliferation in vitro via the estrogen receptor/ERK1/2 signaling pathway both at low and high concentrations. The S phase of the cell cycle, and protein levels of the cyclin family were significantly increased, and expression of proliferative signaling-related proteins including ERα , ERβ , VEGFR2 , pERK , PI3K (p85), and PCNA induced (Mesnage et al., 2017; Sritana et al., 2018; Thongprakaisang, Thiantanawat, Rangkadilok, Suriyo, & Satayavivad, 2013).	748 1065 1180 1181 1182 1189 1310 1505	200
Genotoxicity	-	Mitochondrial dysfunction , ROS formation , and DNA damage were observed in glyphosate-exposed human bronchial epithelial and neuronal cells (Allewa et al., 2016). Cytotoxicity and DNA-damage were observed in human-derived buccal epithelial cells exposed to glyphosate and Roundup concentrations that correspond to a 450-fold dilution of spraying used in agriculture (Koller et al., 2012). DNA damage was also found in CHO-K1 cells (Roustan, Aye, De Meo, & Di Giorgio, 2014) and human lymphocytes (Kwiatkowska et al., 2017; Santovito, Ruberto, Gendusa, & Cervella, 2018; Wozniak et al., 2018), while other studies reported the absence of DNA damage at low (Mladinic, Perkovic, & Zeljezic, 2009) or realistic concentrations (Mladinic, Berend, et al., 2009). In fish, DNA damage was observed with an equivocal role of oxidative stress (de Moura, da Silva Lima, et al., 2017; Guilherme, Gaivao, Santos, & Pacheco, 2010, 2012; Guilherme, Santos, Barroso, Gaivao, & Pacheco, 2012; Marques, Guilherme, Gaivao, Santos, & Pacheco, 2014; Nwani, Nagpure, Kumar, Kushwaha, & Lakra, 2013). POEA was also reported to induce oxidative stress and DNA damage in fish (Navarro & Martinez, 2014).	356 768 1088 1112 1185 1194 1278 1294 1392 1483 1608 1634 1636	296
Anti-carcinogenic effects	-	AMPA was shown to cause cell cycle arrest and apoptosis (accompanied by altered p53, p21, Procaspase9, cyclin D3, caspase 3, and poly (adenosine diphosphate [ADP]-ribose) polymerase protein levels) and inhibit metastasis in (prostate) cancer cells (but not in normal cells) in vitro and in a mouse model, suggesting anti-carcinogenic effects (Q. Li et al., 2013; Parajuli, Zhang, Liu, & You, 2015, 2016).	1262 1365 1505 1513	-
Immune system				
Asthma	From an inverse association with exacerbation of asthma symptoms and glyphosate use, it was concluded that asthma cases prone to exacerbation may avoid glyphosate as it would trigger symptoms (Henneberger et al., 2014).	An inflammatory immune response (increased eosinophil and neutrophil counts, mast cell degranulation, and production of IL-33, TSLP, IL-13, and IL-5) was observed in lungs of mice after glyphosate inhalation (Kumar et al., 2014).	313 1225 1493	-

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Human biomarker of effect	Link of biomarker with exposure and health outcome in epidemiological study	Experimental evidence and suggested mechanisms of action	KE	AO P
Immunosuppression	-	Glyphosate, AMPA and impurities decreased viability and ATP level and altered cell granularity and size of human peripheral blood mononuclear cells at high concentrations (Kwiatkowska et al., 2016). Glyphosate altered interleukin-1β , interleukin-10 , and heme oxygenase-1 expression (Richard et al., 2014) and caused immunosuppression in fish (Kreutz et al., 2011).	403	-
Neurodevelopment				
Parkinson's disease	Premature mortality from Parkinson's disease was associated with exposure to land-use associated with glyphosate (Caballero et al., 2018).	In rats, glyphosate exposure caused oxidative stress in the brain, loss of mitochondrial transmembrane potential and cardiolipin content, and activation of calpain apoptotic cascade resulting in DNA fragmentation (Astiz, de Alaniz, & Marra, 2009). Glyphosate inhibited viability of PC12 cells and induced both autophagy and apoptotic pathways, in which the Beclin-1 gene seemed to be involved (Gui, Fan, Wang, Wang, & Chen, 2012). In human neuroblastoma and melanoma cell lines, on the other hand, glyphosate did not trigger molecular events involved in the development of Parkinson's disease (Chorfa et al., 2013).	896 1088 1112 1185 1262 1294 1365 1392 1510 1513 1514	260
Autism	Glyphosate use has increasing trends that correlate positively to the rise in autism (Nevison, 2014). The risk of autism spectrum disorder was associated with ambient pesticides within 2000 m of the mother's residence during pregnancy (von Ehrenstein et al., 2019).	-	-	-
Behaviour	-	Repeated glyphosate exposure affected locomotor activity , anxiety and memory in mice (Baier, Gallegos, Raisman-Vozari, & Minetti, 2017), locomotor activity and anxiety in prenatally exposed rats (Abarikwu, Akiri, Durojaiye, & Adenike, 2015; Gallegos et al., 2016), and behavioral parameters in rats (Hernandez-Plata, Giordano, Díaz-Munoz, & Rodriguez, 2015) and zebrafish (Bridi, Altenhofen, Gonzalez, Reolon, & Bonan, 2017). In rats, the dopaminergic system was affected (Hernandez-Plata et al., 2015). Recognition memory was impaired after glyphosate exposure during early stages of rat development, accompanied by brain oxidative stress markers and activity of enzymes involved in the glutamatergic and cholinergic systems (Gallegos et al., 2018). Prenatal and postnatal exposure of rats caused oxidative stress and affected cholinergic and glutamatergic neurotransmission (decreased glutamate uptake and metabolism, NMDA receptor activation, impairment of cholinergic transmission, astrocyte dysfunction, ERK1/2 overactivation, decreased p65 NF- κ B phosphorylation) in offspring hippocampus, which was associated with depressive-like behavior (Cattani et al., 2017; Cattani et al., 2014). Glyphosate is an inhibitor of acetylcholinesterase in rats (Larsen, Lifschitz, Lanusse, & Virkel, 2016) and fish brain (Braz-Mota, Sadauskas-Henrique, Duarte, Val, & Almeida-Val, 2015; Cattaneo et al., 2011; Gholami-Seyedkolaei, Mirvaghefi, Farahmand, & Kosari, 2013; Modesto & Martinez, 2010a, 2010b; Salbego et al., 2010; Samanta, Pal, Mukherjee, & Ghosh, 2014). Acute exposure of (zebra)fish caused decreased cell viability , mitochondrial impairment , and oxidative stress in brain, and induced behavioral impairments (de Moura, Brentegani, Gemelli, Sinhorin, & Sinhorin, 2017; Pereira et al., 2018; Santo et al., 2018).	12 388 1088 1185 1112 1294 1350 1392 1488	13 17 48 281
Neurodevelopment	-	In <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> (<i>C. elegans</i>) (McVey et al., 2016) and fish (Sobjak et al., 2017) glyphosate impaired neuronal development , potentially through oxidative stress.	1510	260
Intoxication	Serum S100B was a	-	-	-

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Human biomarker of effect	Link of biomarker with exposure and health outcome in epidemiological study	Experimental evidence and suggested mechanisms of action	KE	AO P
	significant predictor of neurologic complications in patients with glyphosate poisoning (Lee et al., 2017). Altered level of consciousness was observed in fatal cases (Roberts et al., 2010).			
Metabolic disorders				
Metabolism	-	In rats, blood glucose and serum insulin levels increased, and degenerative changes were observed in glandular pancreatic acinar cells and islets of Langerhans (Tizhe et al., 2018). Glyphosate inhibited liver fatty acid oxidation enzymes and increased the levels of triglycerides and cholesteryl esters in mice (Ford, Bateman, Gutierrez-Palominos, Park, & Nomura, 2017). In fish, effects on energy metabolism , protein and amino acids metabolism and nucleosides metabolism, glucose levels in liver, muscle and plasma, and on glycogen , total lipid , cholesterol and triglyceride levels were observed (de Moura, da Silva Lima, et al., 2017; Frontera, Vatrnick, Chalet, & Rodriguez, 2011; M. H. Li et al., 2017; Persch, Weimer, Freitas, & Oliveira, 2017).	881 1060 1289 1296	-
Obesity	-	Glyphosate inhibited adipogenesis by inhibition of PPAR gamma induction and inhibition of proliferation in murine (pre)adipocytes (Martini, Gabrielli, Brandani, & Vila Mdel, 2016).	233	-
Endocrine disruption				
Reproductive hormones	-	Glyphosate exposure was associated with androgen-like effects such as increased anogenital distance in both male and female rats, delay of first estrous and increased testosterone in females (Manservisi et al., 2019). In contrast, no effects on testosterone (and estradiol and progesterone) levels or lower testosterone levels were observed in rats exposed to different doses of glyphosate (Dai, Hu, Tang, Li, & Li, 2016; Johansson et al., 2018; R. M. Romano, Romano, Bernardi, Furtado, & Oliveira, 2010). In male rats, glyphosate increased ESR1 expression but no effects on estrogen and testosterone serum levels were observed (Altamirano et al., 2018). No effect of glyphosate on testosterone production was observed in a murine Leydig cell model (Forgacs et al., 2012).	446 808 1612	-
Thyroid hormones	Hypothyroidism risk was significantly increased among ever- vs. never-users of glyphosate (Shrestha et al., 2018).	An increase in plasma TSH concentration was observed in glyphosate-treated male rats (Manservisi et al., 2019). Several genes regulated by thyroid hormones or involved in thyroid hormone metabolism and transport showed altered expression (reduction in expression of deiodinases 2 (Dio2) and 3 (Dio3) and transporters Slco1c1 (former Oatp1c1) and Slc16a2 (former Mct8) in hypothalamus; higher expression of Dio2, thyroid hormone receptor genes (Thra1 and Thrb1), and Slc16a2 in the pituitary; increased expression of Thra1 and Thrb1 in liver), after intrauterine exposure of rats to glyphosate, which was associated with peripheral metabolism. The hormonal profiles showed decreased concentrations of TSH in these rats, with no effect on the levels of T3 and T4 (de Souza et al., 2017).	753 1002 1023	-
Reproductive effects				
Sperm quantity & quality	Ex vivo exposure to a high glyphosate concentration reduced sperm progressive motility (Anifandis et al., 2018).	Spermatogenesis was impaired in mice germ cells (Jiang et al., 2018) and Sertoli cells (Vanlaeys, Dubuisson, Seralini, & Travert, 2018). Decreased sperm motility and concentration , and increased sperm deformity were observed in mice (Jiang et al., 2018), rats (Abarikwu et al., 2015; Owagboriaye et al., 2017) and fish (Goncalves et al., 2018; Harayashiki et al., 2013; Lopes et al., 2014; Sanchez et al., 2017). In rats, these effects were accompanied by altered serum levels of reproductive hormones (testosterone, luteinizing hormone	50 257 356 505 520 1088 1112 1294	26

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Human biomarker of effect	Link of biomarker with exposure and health outcome in epidemiological study	Experimental evidence and suggested mechanisms of action	KE	AO P
		(LH), follicle stimulating hormone (FSH) and prolactin) and equivocal effects related to oxidative stress in testicular tissue and degenerative testicular architectural lesions (Abarikwu et al., 2015; Owagboriaye et al., 2017). Prenatal exposure of rats caused hypersecretion of androgens, increased gonadal activity, and altered sperm production (M. A. Romano et al., 2012). Another study did not find effects on sperm concentration and motility in rats after acute exposure, but did observe increased abnormal sperm morphology and decreased expression of protamine 1 and histone 1 testicular in sperm and increased aromatase expression, Gper1 , and blood-testis-barrier markers in testes (Cassault-Meyer, Gress, Seralini, & Galeraud-Denis, 2014). Ca(2+) overload, cell signaling dysregulation, stress response of the endoplasmic reticulum, and/or depleted antioxidant defenses could contribute to Sertoli cell spermatogenesis disruption in rats (de Liz Oliveira Cavalli et al., 2013). Glyphosate caused necrosis in rat Sertoli cells, while Roundup also affected other cell types. Germ cells showed apoptosis after high dose exposure of testicular cells. At lower non-toxic concentrations of Roundup and glyphosate a decrease in testosterone was observed in rat testicular cells (Clair, Mesnage, Travert, & Seralini, 2012). XAF1 (X-linked inhibitor of apoptosis-associated factor 1) was reported to play a role in murine male germ cell apoptosis (Jiang et al., 2018).	1392 1506 1515 1538	
Female fertility	-	Subchronic exposure of female rats induced impaired folliculogenesis and ovary development , decreased estrogen secretion, oxidative stress and histological alterations in ovaries (Hamdaoui et al., 2018). Glyphosate caused ovarian failure , interference with progesterone and estrogen secretion by affecting steroidogenesis-related gene expression (GnRH, LHR, FSHR, 3 β -HSD and Cyp19a1) and the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis, and oxidative stress in pregnant mice (Ren et al., 2018). ERα , ERβ , progesterone receptor , and complement 3 expression was affected in uterus after glyphosate exposure of rats (Varayoud et al., 2017). Glyphosate disrupted zebrafish oocyte maturation (Maskey, Crotty, Wooten, & Khan, 2019) and caused an increase in diameter of oocytes , altered ovarian ultrastructure , and increased expression of SF-1 (Armiliato et al., 2014).	1088 1112 1294 1392	-
Pregnancy outcome	The number of miscarriages was increased in areas in which glyphosate was sprayed (Camacho & Mejia, 2017). Glyphosate concentrations in urine were associated with shortened gestational length (Parvez et al., 2018).	Embryo losses in rats were related to disrupted uterine signaling (Wnt5a, Wnt7a, β -catenin, Dkk1 and sFRP4 expression in uterine tissue) (Ingaramo et al., 2017) and altered decidualization response, decreased expression of estrogen and progesterone receptors , Nr2f2 , and Bmp2 , and increased expression of HOXA10 and the proliferation marker Ki67 (Mki67) at the embryonal implantation site (Ingaramo et al., 2016). Morphological changes of the uterus and altered expression of proteins involved in uterine organogenetic differentiation (PR, Hoxa10, Er α , Wnt7a) were also observed in rats (Guerrero Schimpf, Milesi, Ingaramo, Luque, & Varayoud, 2017). Glyphosate exposure was associated with less but larger embryos in fish (Zebral et al., 2018).	1046	-

4.6.5 Pyrethroids (INSERM)

Pyrethroids are a class of insecticides that are used world wide for crop protection and pest control. The pyrethroid family includes several compounds, of which, some are approved for use in the European Union. In this Pubmed search, we have included the following pyrethroids that are approved for use in the European Union: Pyrethroid, Bifenthrin, Beta-Cyfluthrin, Alpha-Cypermethrin, alphasmethrin, Cypermethrin, Zeta-Cypermethrin, Pyrethrin, Deltamethrin, Esfenvalerate, Etofenprox, Gamma-Cyhalothrin, Lambda-Cyhalothrin, tau-Fluvalinate, Tefluthrin.

The following flow-chart summarises the pyrethroid-related human studies retrieved from Pubmed and their classification following Abstract screening. A total 357 articles were retrieved, out of which, 68 studies have reported effect biomarkers for pyrethroids for the six health endpoints examined, and the full-text of these 68 studies were examined. The main findings for each health endpoint are described below.

Figure 10: Pyrethroid-related human studies retrieved from Pubmed and their classification

4.6.5.1 Reproduction Health Endpoint

For Reproduction, 20 epidemiological studies that reported effect biomarkers were identified from Pubmed search. The identified effect biomarkers are reported in the Table and are underlined.

Classical biomarkers: Three epidemiological studies reported an association between pyrethroid metabolites/ pesticides in mothers and anthropometric biomarkers (body weight, anogenital distance, abdominal circumference etc) in children. Apart from this, delayed puberty, sperm DNA damage, reduced sperm motility and abnormal sperm morphology were reported in 4

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epidemiological studies. In females, a study found an association between urinary pyrethroid levels and the time required to conceive baby. Associations between indoor pesticide use and low anti-mullerian hormone levels was observed in one epidemiological study.

Novel biomarker: Sperm related chromosomal abnormalities observed following pesticide exposure could serve as novel biomarkers. Two epidemiological studies have reported sex chromosome disomy and disomy of chromosomes 18 and 21 in men with increased levels of a permethrin pyrethroid metabolite, cis-3-(2,2-Dichlorovinyl)-1-methylcyclopropane-1,2-dicarboxylic acid (CCDA).

Table 25: Effect biomarkers selected for Pyrethroids exposure and Reproductive Health Endpoint

No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
1	n=75; men aged 20–54 from infertility evaluation at Massachusetts General Hospital Fertility Center	Urinary concentrations of cis-3-(2,2-Dichlorovinyl)-1-methylcyclopropane-1,2-dicarboxylic acid (a permethrin metabolite) were associated with <u>increased semen sex chromosome disomy (XX18, XY18, and YY18)</u>	Young et al., 2013
2	n=496 women from the Shanghai Birth Cohort	High urinary diethylthiophosphate (DETP; an OP metabolite) and 3-phenoxybenzoic acid (3PBA; a pyrethroid metabolite) associated with significantly <u>longer time to conception and infertility.</u>	Hu et al., 2018
3	n=674; Venda Health Examination of Mothers, Babies, and their Environment (VHEMBE) prospective birth cohort study, Limpopo Province, South Africa	Maternal high urinary concentrations of DDT/E were associated with higher rates of <u>persistent fevers and severe sore throats (in children)</u> , particularly <i>p,p'</i> -DDE. Limited evidence that pyrethroid metabolite concentrations were associated with the studied outcomes	Huang et al., 2013
4	n=286; men aged under 45 years of age who attended an infertility clinic in Lodz, Poland with normal semen	A positive association was observed between urinary cis-3-(2,2-Dichlorovinyl)-1-methylcyclopropane-1,2-dicarboxylic acid (CDCCA; a permethrin metabolite) and the percentage of <u>sperm medium DNA fragmentation index (DFI) and the percentage of immature sperm.</u>	Jurewicz et al., 2015
5	n=858; participants from the Odense Child Cohort (OCC), Denmark	Maternal urinary 3-PBA concentration associated with <u>shorter abdominal circumference</u> in females. A non-significant dose-related elongation of <u>anogenital distance (AGD)</u> in females was seen for 3-PBA and diethyl phosphates. In males, exposure to 2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (a herbicide) showed a statistically significant shorter AGD.	Dalsager et al., 2018
6	n=195; Men aged under 45 years of age who attended infertility clinic in Lodz, Poland	CDCCA was associated with <u>disomy of chromosome 18</u> . The level of trans-3-(2,2-dichlorovinyl)-2,2dimethylcyclopropane carboxylic acid (TDCCA) in urine was related to <u>XY disomy and disomy of chromosome 21</u> . Urinary 3-PBA levels were related to <u>disomy: XY, YY, 21, 18 and total disomy.</u>	Radwan et al., 2015
7	n=305; Girls at the ages of 9–15 years old who lived in Hangzhou, China	Association between 3-PBA levels in urine and increase risk of <u>delayed pubertal onset</u> in girls.	Ye et al., 2017
8	n=42; male partner of couples from a <u>gynecology</u> clinic in Tokyo for <u>infertility</u> consultation	Association between urinary 3-PBA levels and <u>sperm motility</u>	Toshima et al., 2012
10	n=240; Study subjects were volunteers from affiliated hospitals of Nanjing Medical University, China	A significant inverse correlation was observed between the urinary 3-PBA level and the <u>sperm concentration</u> . Also a significant positive correlation between urinary 3-PBA level and <u>sperm DNA fragmentation</u>	Ji et al., 2011
11	n=454 mother-infant pairs from Binhai Hospital, China	An adverse association of prenatal exposure to maternal urinary pyrethroids (the sum of cis-DCCA, trans-DCCA, and 3-PBA) with <u>decreased birth weight</u> .	Ding et al., 2015
12	n=195 men from infertility clinic in Lodz, Poland	Urinary 5OH MEHP, CDCCA to TDCCA and 1-OHP was negatively related to <u>Y:X sperm chromosome ratio</u>	Jurewicz et al., 2016

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No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
13	n=708 mother-children pair ; children ≤2 years old participating in the prospective South Africa VHEMBE birth cohort	Maternal serum p,p'-DDT concentration associated with increased body composition and body weight in young girls. Maternal urinary pyrethroid metabolite concentrations (particularly cis-DBCA and trans-DCCA) were negatively associated with <u>body weight and body composition</u> in young boys.	Coker et al., 2018
14	n=323; Cross-sectional survey on the reference value of semen quality of Japanese men	No associations between urinary 3-PBA and serum hormone levels (LH, FSH, SHBG, testosterone and inhibin B).	Yoshinaga et al., 2014
15	n=334 men who attended the infertility clinic for diagnostic purposes in an infertility clinic in Lodz, Poland	The concentrations of 3PBA and DBCC more were negatively associated with one of the CASA parameters (<u>sperm counts and percentage motility</u>). Sum of pyrethroids (3PBA, CDCCA, TDCCA, and DBCA) was positively associated with the percentage of <u>sperm with abnormal morphology</u> .	Radwan et al., 2014
16	n= 562 mother-infant pairs from the Department of Gynecology and Obstetrics of a county hospital in Jiaozuo, Henan, China	Level of synthetic pyrethroid pesticide exposure (cis-Cl2CA, trans-Cl2CA, and 3-PBA) was negatively related to the <u>neural and mental development of infants</u>	Xue et al., 2013
17	n=463 boys at the age of 9-16 years old were recruited in Hangzhou, Zhejiang, China.	An association of increased urinary pyrethroid exposure with <u>elevated gonadotropins levels (LH and FSH)</u> and early <u>pubertal development</u> in boys.	Ye et al., 2017
18	n=150 couples that underwent intracytoplasmic sperm injection for male factor infertility (ICSI) from fertility center, Egypt	Higher concentrations of any studied polychlorinated biphenyls and pesticides in follicular fluid are associated with <u>thinner endometrial thickness</u> . The higher the level of Pretilachlor, β-cyfluthrin, PCB 28 and 180, the <u>lower the retrieval, fertilisation, and embryo cleavage rates</u> . High PCB and pesticide concentrations in the follicular fluid adversely affected <u>embryological ICSI outcomes</u> .	Al-Hussaini et al., 2018
19	n=420 women from Limpopo, South Africa	Women who reported indoor residual spraying in homes had 25% <u>lower anti-Müllerian hormone concentrations</u> compared with women who reported no spraying.	Whitworth et al., 2015
20	<u>Breastfeeding</u> dyads (n = 40) were recruited in metropolitan Western Australia	No significant association was found between p,p'-DDE concentrations in human milk and infant growth outcomes such as weight, length, head circumference and percentage fat mass.	Du et al., 2017

The effect biomarkers are not underlined if no association is reported.

4.6.5.2 Neurodevelopmental Health Endpoint

Classical biomarkers: Out of 23 studies identified, 11 studies have reported an association with pyrethroids or other pesticides with neurodevelopment and behavior in children. These include poor working memory and verbal comprehension, social difficulties, externalising behavior difficulties, learning problems, low Mental Developmental Index etc. Three studies found an association between pesticides and Autism Spectrum Disorders (ASD) in children, and three reported an association between Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorders (ADHD) and pesticide levels in urine. Two studies observed declining cognitive functions in elders as well as depression that associated with urinary pesticide levels. Another study identified risk of peripheral nerve impairment in farmers who has pesticide effect.

Novel biomarkers: Two studies showed that exposure to pyrethroids and other pesticides significantly reduced or inhibited acetylcholinesterase and butyryl cholinesterase activities in the blood of pesticide applicators. Perhaps, this could serve as biomarkers for pesticide effect.

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Table 26: Effect biomarkers selected for Pyrethroids exposure and Neurodevelopment Health Endpoint

No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
1	n=206; children from three kindergartens from Nanjing (including urban and rural areas), China.	Association between urinary organophosphate trichloropyridinol (TCP) and pyrethroid pesticides (3-PBA level) with <u>children's working memory and verbal comprehension</u>	Wang et al., 2016
2	n=687 from 8-15 year old participants from National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey, The US.	Strong associations between urinary 3-PBA levels and <u>Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD)</u> in boys compared to girls.	Wagner-Schuman et al., 2015
3	Group 1- A total of 40 children were recruited in this case-control study by Neuropsychiatric Unit of the Bellaria Hospital of Bologna and by the Laboratorio NovEra srl, Civitanova Marche, Italy. Group 2-65 children were recruited in this case-control study. Of these, 29 (26 males and 3 females) had a diagnosis of Autism Spectrum Disorders (ASD), and 36 (26 males and 10 females) were CTR children.	Urine concentration of 3-BPA in <u>ASD children</u> had higher values than in the control group, which were marginally significant (p = 0.054). Mg results were significantly decreased in ASD with respect to controls, while V, S, Zn, and Ca/Mg were marginally increased, without reaching statistical significance.	Domingues et al., 2016
4	A nested case-control study to identify the association between urinary pyrethroid metabolite levels and ADHD in U.S. children between the ages of 6 and 15 years (n = 2123)	Urinary pyrethroid pesticides (3-phenoxybenzoic acid; 3-PBA) increases the risk of being diagnosed with <u>Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD)</u> .	Richardson et al., 2015
5	A cross-sectional study in 140 children living near banana plantations and plantain farms in the Talamanca County, Costa Rica	Higher urinary TCPy concentrations were associated with <u>poorer working memory in boys</u> . Higher 3-PBA concentrations were associated with <u>poorer processing speed scores</u> , particularly in girls.	van Wendel et al., 2016
6	403 households in Nepal and adopted the Test-mate ChE Cholinesterase Test System to monitor acetylcholinesterase activity across pesticide application season on the 127 individuals of the sampled households.	Exposure to organophosphates and pyrethroids significantly reduced <u>acetylcholinesterase activity across pesticide application season</u> .	Atreya et al., 2012
7	n=633 elders; The continuous National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES), The US population	Association between <u>organochlorine pesticides</u> p,p'-dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT), p,p'-dichlorodiphenyldichloroethylene (DDE), trans-nonachlor, oxychlorodane, heptachlor <u>epoxide</u> , and β-hexachlorocyclohexane and <u>reduced cognitive score in elders</u> .	Kim et al., 2015
8	n= 287 mothers-child pair from The PELAGIE cohort, France	Childhood urinary 3-PBA and cis-DBCA concentrations were both negatively associated with <u>verbal comprehension scores and with working memory scores</u> . No associations were observed for the three other childhood pyrethroid metabolite concentrations (4-F-3-PBA, cis-DCCA, and trans-DCCA)	Viel et al., 2015
9	n=54, 6–8 year old, healthy male and female Thai children recruited from rice (N=25) and aquaculture farming (i.e., shrimp farms) (N= 29) regions outside of Bangkok, Thailand	No significant adverse neurobehavioral effects were observed between participant groups during either the high or low pesticide use season.	Fiedler et al., 2015

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No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
10	n=1,081 children 6–11 years of age, in 15 sites spread across Canada	No association between exposure to organophosphate pesticides and behavioral scores in children. The pyrethroid metabolite <i>cis</i> -DCCA [3-(2,2-dichlorovinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane carboxylic acid] was significantly associated with high scores for <u>total difficulties on the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire</u>	Oulhote et al., 2013
11	N= 287 mother-child pair from the PELAGIE cohort, France	Increased prenatal <i>cis</i> -3-(2,2-dichlorovinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane carboxylic acid (DCCA) concentrations were associated with <u>internalising difficulties</u> . For childhood 3-phenoxybenzoic acid (PBA) concentrations, a positive association was observed with <u>externalising difficulties or borderline social behaviour</u> . High childhood <i>trans</i> -DCCA concentrations were associated with <u>reduced externalising disorders</u> .	Viel et al., 2017
12	162 mother/child pairs with complete exposure and behavioral outcomes data from the Mount Sinai Children's Environmental Health Center, The US	Suggestive evidence that prenatal exposure to 3-PBA and <i>cis</i> -DCCA may be associated with a variety of <u>behavioral and executive functioning deficits</u> .	Furlong et al., 2017
13	Cross-sectional study to analyse association between postnatal pyrethroid exposure and parental report of learning disability (LD) and attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) in children 6-15 years of age, National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey, The US	Postnatal pyrethroid exposure was not associated with parental report of learning disability (LD) and attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD).	Quiros-Alcala et al., 2014
14	Participants included mothers and children (n=283) living in the agricultural Salinas Valley of California	A decrease in verbal <u>comprehension</u> for use of organophosphate pesticides. Similar decrements for increased use for two organophosphates (acephate and oxydemeton-methyl) and three neurotoxic pesticide groups (pyrethroids, neonicotinoids, and manganese fungicides).	Gunier et al., 2017
15	Cross-sectional study evaluating the prevalence of common mental disorders and self-reported depression in a sample of 869 adult individuals resident in Dom Feliciano, Brazil	A positive association between self-reported pesticide poisoning and <u>common mental disorders</u> as well as self-reported <u>depression</u> . Individuals who reported depression had a greater odds of exposure to pyrethroids.	Campos et al., 2016
16	n= 741; Pregnant women were prospectively enrolled into the study at midgestation at the Bulacan Provincial Hospital (BPH) outpatient clinic, Philippines	At 2 years of age, prenatal exposure to propoxur, a carbamate insecticide was associated with <u>poorer motor development in children</u>	Ostrea et al., 2012
17	Adolescents between 12 and 18 years of age, were recruited in 2005 and 2009 (N = 41 in 2005 and N = 21 in 2009), and adolescents who had never worked in the cotton fields was also recruited (N = 38 in 2005 and N = 20 in 2009) as a comparison group from Menoufia Governorate, Egypt	Pesticide applicators in both cohorts reported more neurological symptoms and signs than non-applicators, particularly among participants in the 2005 cohort. The 2005 cohort showed greater <u>inhibition of serum butyryl cholinesterase (BChE)</u> than the 2009 cohort.	Ismail et al., 2017
18	A total of 224 farmers were initially enrolled from two villages within China. An eligible farmer was defined as the person who was over 18 years old and mainly sprayed	The short- and medium-term OPs exposures were mainly associated with <u>liver damage and peripheral nerve impairment</u> , respectively	Huang et al., 2016

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No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
	pesticides in the household.		
19	Participants in this study were part of a prospective cohort of black and Dominican mothers and newborns living in low-income neighborhoods in New York City. 342 subjects for permethrin in personal air; 272 subjects for permethrin in plasma; and 230 subjects for PBO in personal air.	Children more highly exposed to piperonyl butoxide in personal air samples scored 3.9 lower on the <u>Mental Developmental Index</u> than those with lower exposures.	Horton et al., 2011
20	Maternal urinary 3-phenoxybenzoic acid (3-PBA) concentrations during the third trimester of pregnancy as a measure of in utero pyrethroid exposure to the fetus among participants in an established Mexico City birth cohort (n=187).	Participants in the medium and high 3-PBA categories had lower <u>Mental Development Index (MDI)</u> scores at 24 months compared to those in the low 3-PBA category, with slightly stronger associations among female children.	Watkins et al., 2016
21	The CHAMACOS study is a longitudinal birth cohort study, examining pesticide and other environmental exposures in the agricultural Salinas Valley, California. Up to as many 330 children were followed through the 7-year of age for neurodevelopmental assessment.	Although maternal residence during pregnancy near high agricultural use of multiple neurotoxic pesticides was associated with <u>Full Scale Intelligence Quotient (FSIQ) deficit</u> , the magnitude of the associations showed potential for sub-additive effects.	Coker et al., 2017
22	Participants were California children enrolled in the Childhood Autism Risks from Genetics and the Environment (CHARGE) case-control study at age 2-5 y, were clinically confirmed to have ASD (n=296) or typical development (n=220), and had information on maternal supplemental folic acid (FA) and pesticide exposures.	Associations between pesticide exposures and <u>autism spectrum disorders (ASD)</u> were attenuated among those with high versus low folic acid intake during the first month of pregnancy.	Schmidt et al., 2017
23	Evaluated whether residential proximity to agricultural pesticides during pregnancy is associated with autism spectrum disorders (ASD) or developmental delay (DD) in the Childhood Autism Risks from Genetics and Environment (CHARGE) study. Participants were California children born from 2000-2007	This study of ASD strengthens the evidence linking neurodevelopmental disorders with gestational pesticide exposures, particularly organophosphates, and provides novel results of <u>autism spectrum disorders (ASD) or developmental delay (DD)</u> associations with, respectively, pyrethroids and carbamates.	Shelton et al., 2014

The effect biomarkers are not underlined if no association is reported.

4.6.5.3 Metabolic and Cardiovascular Health Endpoint

Classical biomarkers: One study identified that pyrethroid metabolites significantly increase the risk for coronary heart diseases. Significant changes in antioxidant enzymes like superoxide dismutase, catalase and glutathione and increased malondialdehyde levels were reported in pesticide workers in 4 studies. Two studies identified an increased prevalence of abnormal glucose regulation in pesticide users.

Novel biomarkers: No novel biomarkers were reported.

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Table 27: Effect biomarkers selected for Pyrethroids exposure and Metabolic and Cardiovascular Health Endpoint

No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
1	72 coronary heart disease (CHD) patients and 136 healthy subjects were recruited in Shanxi province in China from 2013 to 2014 by matching age and gender.	Upper tertile of urinary pyrethroid metabolites were associated with an increased risk of <u>coronary heart diseases (CHD)</u> compared with the lowest tertile.	Han et al., 2017
2	n=19 were included in the study group: 17 men and two women. Uppsala Sweden	No clear relationships could be found between exposure and inflammation markers in nasal mucosa (lysozyme, albumin) or between elevated 3-PBA levels and inflammation markers.	Elfman et al., 2009
3	The study was conducted in three different sizes of factories located in Lahore (large), Multan (medium), and Karachi (small) in Pakistan. Total 238 adult males consisting of 184 pesticide industrial workers (exposed group) from large-sized (67), medium-sized (61), small-sized (56) industrial formulation factories, and 54 controls (unexposed) were included in the study.	<u>Serum AST, ALT, creatinine GGT, malondialdehyde, total antioxidant, and CRP</u> were significantly raised among the workers of small and medium pesticide formulation factories as compared to large industrial unit and controls	Khan et al., 2010
4	A cross-sectional study was performed including 200 workers divided into 3 groups according to the level of exposure: highly exposed group (50 workers), moderately exposed group (50 workers) and unexposed group (100 workers) from a factory in Egypt	Highly exposed group to the α -cypermethrin had <u>lower CD4/CD8</u> as compared to an unexposed group with statistically significant difference. As regards <u>gene mutation, exons 5a and 6</u> were more frequent among the highly exposed group as compared to no mutation among moderately exposed and unexposed groups with significant difference. As regards antioxidants; <u>SOD, CAT, GSH and GPx</u> were higher among the unexposed group as compared to the highly and moderately exposed group with statistically significant difference.	El Okda et al., 2017
5	Ninety male and twenty-four female OPs, synthetic pyrethroid and carbamate-formulating workers were chosen. Their average age was 37.4 years and at least 5-year experience in pest-control in apple and cherry production, Mexico	Chronic exposure to organophosphate, synthetic pyrethroid and carbamate pesticides were associated with <u>increased activities of catalase, SOD and lipid peroxidation in erythrocytes.</u>	Ogut et al., 2011
6	The study population consisted of 208 participants who were divided into three study groups per their grade of pesticide exposure: reference, no pesticide exposure (n = 22), moderate pesticide exposure (n = 126), and high pesticide exposure (n = 60) from Mexico	The results suggest a significant <u>decrease of antioxidant enzymes</u> and a <u>positive correlation between DNA damage parameters and MDA levels</u> in occupational exposure to pesticide workers.	Zepeda-Arce et al., 2017
7	Subjects aged between 20 and 60 years in two pesticide factories were admitted from China. Group I consisting of 1347 subjects who were known to get exposed to pyrethroids for at least 8 h a day and sustained more than 1 year; Group II consisting of 1733 controls that had no known history of exposure to pyrethroids.	The prevalence of <u>abnormal glucose regulation (IGR and diabetes)</u> was increased significantly in the exposure group than controls.	Wang et al., 2011
8	A cross-sectional study was	Among sprayers who had only used pyrethroids, a	Hansen et

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No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
	performed among 116 pesticide sprayers from public vector control programs in Bolivia and 92 nonexposed controls.	significant positive trend was observed between cumulative pesticide exposure and <u>abnormal glucose regulation</u> .	al., 2014

The effect biomarkers are not underlined if no association is reported.

4.6.5.4 Allergy and Immune disorders Health Endpoint

For allergy/ immunology biomarkers, 6 epidemiological studies related to pyrethroids were identified from this Pubmed search. The identified effect biomarkers are reported in the Table and are underlined.

Classical biomarkers: Out of the six studies, one study has reported an association between pesticide application and rheumatoid arthritis/ allergy. Changes in blood parameters such as chromosomal aberrations, DNA damage and decrease in B lymphocytes were reported in farmers who sprayed pesticides. Increase of non-infectious cough were observed in children with indoor pesticide use.

Novel biomarkers: Two studies have reported changes in interleukin levels following exposure to pesticides. Changes in interferon- γ , IL-2, IL-8 and IL-22 were reported. The specificity of interferons for pesticide exposure needs to be confirmed.

Table 28: Effect biomarkers selected for Pyrethroids exposure and Allergy and Immune disorders Health Endpoint

No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
1	A cross sectional study was conducted among pesticide sprayers ($n = 80$) and the general population ($n = 90$) in Thessaly (Greece).	In the pesticide sprayers group, significantly higher frequencies for rheumatoid arthritis (RA) and <u>allergic rhinitis</u> were observed compared with the control group. Exposure to organophosphate, guanidine and quinone pesticides were associated with RA while organophosphates, pyrethroids and paraquat were associated with allergic rhinitis.	Koureas et al., 2017
2	The group of traditional agricultural system consisted of 85 farmers using pesticides (43 males and 42 females) from a main Portuguese agricultural area. The group of organic agricultural system was composed of 36 organic farmers not using pesticides (17 males and 19 females) from the same geographical area. The control group comprised 61 non-exposed individuals (26 males and 35 females), living in the same area.	When compared to controls and organic farmers, pesticide farmers presented a <u>significant increase of micronuclei in lymphocytes and reticulocytes, chromosomal aberrations, DNA damage, and a significant decrease in the proportion of B lymphocytes.</u>	Costa et al., 2014
3	The presence of symptoms of sick house syndrome (SHS) was evaluated using a validated self-administered questionnaire. Surveys and samplings of air and house dust in 41 dwellings were performed, and 134 occupants responded to questionnaires; Sapporo, Japan	Tributylphosphate was strongly and directly associated with mucosal symptoms of sick house syndrome (SHS); s-421 (an organochlorine synergist) was also directly associated with mucosal symptoms of SHS. Some chemicals such as diethylphthalate and TBEP inversely associated with SHS.	Kanazawa et al., 2010
4	The study population consisted of 30 male green house workers, whose task was to apply pesticide spraying treatments, and 30 male office workers, who served as	Exposed workers showed neither clinical signs of immunosuppression nor alterations in total leukocytes or leukocyte subpopulations, whereas significant differences were found for <u>IL-12p70</u> and highly significant differences for <u>INF-γ, IL-2 and IL-8</u> , which	Costa et al., 2013

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No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
	controls; their mean age was 35.6 ± 1.7 and 36.3 ± 1.4 years, respectively. All were volunteers and all resided in Ragusa, Italy.	are involved in antitumor immunity and response to infection.	
5	A cross-sectional study was conducted on a cohort of 64 workers employed in a greenhouse located in Eastern Sicily with at least 10 years workplace exposure to pesticides, compared with a control group ($n = 30$) of subjects with no history of occupational or environmental exposure to pesticides.	A relevant <u>increase in IL-22 concentration</u> was observed in the exposed subjects compared to controls. By distinguishing the two sub-groups of male and female workers, only IL-22 mean concentrations found in males still resulted significantly higher than controls. IL-17 did not show significant alterations.	Fenga et al., 2014
6	PBO and permethrins were measured in personal air during the third trimester of pregnancy and indoor residential air at age 5-6 years ($n=224$), CCCEH birth cohort, The US.	<u>Noninfectious cough</u> was reported among 14% of children at age 5-6 years. Measures of prenatal PBO, but not age 5-6 year PBO or permethrins, increased the odds of cough.	Liu et al., 2012

The effect biomarkers are not underlined if no association is reported.

4.6.5.5 Endocrine Health Endpoint

For Endocrine-related diseases, 5 epidemiological studies related to pyrethroids were identified from this Pubmed search. The identified effect biomarkers are underlined in the Table.

Classical biomarkers: Out of the five studies that we identified, four studies have examined the association between pyrethroid/ pesticide exposure and thyroid functions. For pyrethroids, 3-phenoxybenzoic acid (3-PBA) is considered to be a major urinary metabolite. None of the identified studies found an association between pyrethroid exposure and thyroid hormone levels or functions. However, two studies that examined thyroid functions found an association between PBA levels and anthropometric parameters and neurodevelopment.

Novel biomarkers: No novel biomarkers could be identified.

Table 29: Effect biomarkers selected for Pyrethroids exposure and Endocrine Health Endpoint

No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
1	Data from National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (The US) for the years 2007-2008 were used to evaluate the impact of the observed levels of 3-phenoxybenzoic acid (3-PBA) in urine on the levels of thyroid hormones in serum for those aged ≥ 12 years.	There was no evidence of any association between the levels of 3-PBA and thyroid function. As compared to their levels in 2001-2002, levels of 3-PBA rose ($p \leq 0.03$) in 2009-2010 for children, adolescents, adults aged 20-64 years, males, females, non-Hispanic whites, non-Hispanic blacks, Mexican Americans, non-smokers, and smokers. Rise in the levels of 3-PBA among children aged 6-11 years was higher than the similar rise in all other demographic groups.	Jain, 2016
2	The cross-sectional association between use of organochlorines and risk of hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism among female spouses ($n = 16,529$) in Iowa and North Carolina enrolled in the Agricultural Health Study	There was an increased odd of hypothyroidism with ever use of organochlorine insecticides and fungicides but no association with ever use of herbicides, fumigants, organophosphates, pyrethroids, or carbamates.	Goldner et al., 2010
3	The subjects of this study were 147 pairs each consisting of a mother and her newborn baby. The mothers, in their first trimester of	Multiple regression analyses with stepwise variable selection did not extract maternal 3-PBA as significant for neonatal fT4 and TSH, indicating that maternal pyrethroid exposure had no apparent effect on the	Zhang et al., 2014

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No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
	gestation, were recruited at Showa University Hospital located in Tokyo, during 2009–2011.	neonatal thyroid hormone status of the neonate subjects. For <u>birth weight and head circumference</u> , maternal 3-PBA was selected as significant with a positive partial regression coefficient along with other factors known to increase birth sizes of neonates (gestational weeks or maternal BMI).	
4	132 of the mother–baby pairs were followed after delivery until the baby was 18 months of age at University hospital in Tokyo	Mother who had higher pyrethroid exposure during pregnancy had a <u>higher developmental quotient (DQ) score</u> for infants. DQ of infants was better whose mother consumed fish more frequently during pregnancy.	Hisada et al., 2017
5	n=231; Four hundred twenty four pregnant women were randomly selected from outpatients of their first visit to obstetrics department of the Tokyo University, of which 315 (74.2%) agreed to participate in this study after giving full explanation of study design and procedures by survey staffs.	Multiple regression analysis was carried out by using either one of serum levels of thyroid-related measures as a dependent variable and urinary 3-PBA as well as other potential covariates (age, pre-pregnancy BMI, parity, urinary iodine, smoking and drinking status) as independent variables: 3-PBA was not found as a significant predictor of serum level of thyroid-related measures.	Zhang et al., 2013

The effect biomarkers are not underlined if no association is reported.

4.6.5.6 Cancer Health Endpoint

For Cancer, 5 epidemiological studies related to pyrethroids were identified from this Pubmed search. The identified effect biomarkers are underlined in the Table.

Classical biomarkers: Out of the five studies that we identified, three studies showed an association between pyrethroid use and cancer risk, especially childhood leukemia in children. One study found an association between pyrethroid use, rs4242382 genetic variant located on chromosome 8q24 and prostate cancer risk. Another study reported significant DNA damage in paippla of hair in children following exposure to pesticides.

Novel biomarkers: Perhaps, rs4242382 variant at chromosome 8q24 could be considered as a novel biomarker. This genetic variant is an established risk factor for prostate as well as other cancers. Pesticides, especially orrganophosphates, has been shown to strongly increase this risk (Koutos et al., 2010).

Table 30: Effect biomarkers selected for Pyrethroids exposure and Cancer Health Endpoint

No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
1	In total, 161 childhood brain tumor (CBT) cases and 170 controls were recruited from 2 children's medical centers in Shanghai (Xinhua Hospital and Shanghai Children's Medical Center) between September 2012 and June 2015.	Trans-DCCA, 3-PBA, and total metabolites (sum of the 3 metabolites) were positively associated with the increased risk of <u>childhood brain tumor (CBT)</u> . Children in the highest quartile had a nearly 3-fold increased risk of CBT compared with those in the lowest quartile after adjusting for confounding factors. Also found that exposure to both mosquitocide and cockroach killer was related to the increased risk of CBT .	Chen et al., 2016
2	Subjects diagnosed with incident prostate cancer between 1993 and 2004 who also provided a buccal cell sample were included in the current nested-case-control study. The Agricultural Health Study (AHS) is a prospective cohort of licensed private and commercial pesticide applicators in Iowa and North	The odds ratios (OR) for a <u>previously identified variant, rs4242382</u> , and <u>prostate cancer</u> increased significantly with exposure to the organophosphate insecticide fonofos. A similar effect modification was observed for three other organophosphate insecticides (coumaphos, terbufos, and phorate) and one pyrethroid insecticide (permethrin). Among ever users of fonofos, subjects with three or four risk alleles at rs7837328 and rs4242382 had approximately three times the risk of prostate cancer. We observed a significant interaction	Koutros et al., 2010

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No.	Study Details	Main Observations	Reference
	Carolina	among variants on chromosome 8q24, pesticide use, and risk of prostate cancer.	
3	Hospital-based case-control study of childhood acute lymphocytic leukemia (ALL) in Shanghai between 2010 and 2011. The study included 176 children aged 0-14 years and 180 controls matched for age and sex.	Compared with those in the lowest quartiles of total and individual metabolites, the highest quartiles were associated with an approximate 2-fold increased <u>risk of acute lymphocytic leukemia (ALL)</u> .	Ding et al., 2012
4	Study participants included ten Latino children age 7–9, recruited in collaboration with community partner, North Carolina (NC) Farmworkers Project, in the area of Benson, NC. From the participants, 45 hairs were collected, but only 20 (44%) passed visual inspection in the laboratory (i.e. had a visible follicle).	In this cohort of child participants, significant association was found between the number of pesticide detections and <u>DNA damage in the papilla region of the hairs</u> .	Vidi et al., 2017
5	Population-based case-control study in a Northern Italy community to assess the possible relation between passive exposure to agricultural pesticides and risk of acute childhood leukemia.	<u>Childhood leukemia risk</u> did not increase in relation with any of the crop types with the exception of arable crops, characterised by the use of 2,4-D, MCPA, glyphosate, dicamba, triazine and cypermethrin. The very few children (n=11) residing close to arable crops had an odds ratios (OR) for childhood leukemia, and such excess risk was further enhanced among children aged <5 years.	Malagoli et al., 2016

The effect biomarkers are not underlined if no association is reported.

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4.7 Organophosphate Pesticides (EASP)

Figure 11: Systematic search on biomarkers of effect for organophosphate pesticides

Figure 12: Distribution of references by health outcomes in human studies

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Table 31: Classic (or traditional) effect biomarkers

Health outcome	Biomarker of effect (Traditional)
Cardiovascular	Blood pressure, BMI, LDL, HDL, triglycerides, total cholesterol. Heart rate, Troponine I, creatine-kinase isoform muscle/brain (CK-MB).
Endocrine disruption	Thyroid hormones (fT3, fT4, total T3, total T4, TSH), LH, FSH, testosterone (total, free), estradiol, prolactine, inhibin B, cortisol, progesterone.
Genotoxicity	Chromosome breakage and DNA strand breaks Micronuclei Cytokinetic defects (binucleated cells), proliferative potential (basal cell), cell death (condensed chromatin, karyorrhectic).
Hepatotoxicity	Aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), alkaline phosphatase (ALP).
Nephrotoxicity	Blood urea nitrogen (BUN), creatinine.
Metabolic disorder	Fasting blood glucose and insulin serum levels Oral glucose test.
Neurotoxicity/ Neurological disorders/ Neurodevelopment	<p>CHILDREN:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children WISC-IV (FSIQ, Verbal Comprehension, Perceptual Reasoning, Working Memory, Processing speed). - Developmental quotients (DQs). - Reflexes, stationary, locomotion, grasping, visual-motor integration (V-M), composite scores (gross (GM), fine (FM), total motor (TM)). - Conners' Parent Rating Scale Performance (behavioural, social, and academic issues, including hyperactivity, aggressive behaviour, potential for violence, compulsive behaviours, among others). - Conners' Kiddie Continuous Performance Test (K-CPT) (Attention: reaction time, consistency, latency, Errors of omission/commission, Time of response). - Assessment System for Children-2 (BASC-2) (behavioural disorders). - Neurological Assessment (NBNA) (behavior, passive tone, active tone, primary reflexes and general assessment). - Neuropsychological Assessment Battery (NEPSY-II) (attention and executive functions, language and communication, sensorimotor functions,

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Health outcome	Biomarker of effect (Traditional)
	<p>visuospatial functions, learning and memory, social perception).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NICU Network Neurobehavioral Scale (NNNS) (neurobehavioral organization, neurological reflexes, motor development - active and passive tone, signs of stress). - Griffiths mental developmental scale (scales: locomotor, personal-social, hearing and language, eye and hand co-ordination, performance, practical reasoning). - Bayley Test (Psychomotor Development Index-PDI- and Mental Development Index-MDI-). <p>ADULTS: tests of memory, response speed, fine motor control, mental flexibility and strategy making; Neurocognitive impairment,</p> <p>butyrylcholinesterase (BChE) in plasma, acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity in brain or red blood cell).</p> <p>Neurosensorial:</p> <p>Visual processing (Functional Acuity Contrast Test (FACT score)</p> <p>Visuospatial performance</p> <p>Visual memory</p> <p>Grating visual acuity (VA score),</p> <p>Auditory brainstem response ((ABR) wave V latency and central conduction time)</p> <p>Pure tone audiometry.</p>
Oxidative stress	<p>Thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS, also known as malondialdehyde MDA or lipoperoxidation products LPO), ferric reducing ability of serum (FRAS), SHT (total thiol content), GGT, PON1, acetylcholinesterase (AChE), superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), glutathione peroxidase (GPx), glutathione reductase (GR) in erythrocytes.</p>
Reproductive effects	<p>Semen (pH, volume, viscosity, concentration), sperm (concentration, motility, morphology and sperm count).</p>

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Table 32: Novel effect biomarkers

Health outcome	Biomarker of effect (novel)
Cardiovascular	Preejection period (PEP).
Neurodevelopment	Cortical thickness (frontal, parietal...) Dopamine receptor D4 gene (DRD4) genetic polymorphisms.
Neurocognitive	Acylpeptide-hydrolase (ACPH).
Neurodegeneration	Metabolic (adiponectin) and inflammatory biomarkers. Microtubule derangements and tau protein hyperphosphorylation.
Neurotoxicity	Regional cerebral blood flow by 99mTc-ECD SPECT. Cytoskeletal and motor proteins involved in axonal transport, neurotrophins and their receptors, and mitochondria (especially their morphology and movement in axons).
Genotoxicity	Biomarkers of DNA damage Comet assay parameters (tail length, tail DNA % (TD %), tail moment (TM)) 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine Chromosome aberrations (e.g., specific translocations i.e. MLL).
Metabolic disorder	Homeostasis model assessment of insulin resistance (HOMA-IR).
Epigenetic changes	Genome-wide DNA methylation. DNA methylation on genes: - CDKN2B and CDKN2A - PON1
Reproductive toxicity	Nuclear and mitochondrial lipid composition in human placenta. Expression of ABCG2, GCM1, β hCG mRNAs. β hCG protein synthesis and secretion in placenta. Cytokines, arginase and ornithine decarboxylase expression in placenta (biomarkers of cytotoxicity).
Immunotoxicity	Cytokines, mutations in genes coding for immunoregulatory factors.
Oxidative stress	4-hydroxy-2-nonenal-mercapturic acid (HNE-MA) Nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor (Nrf2).
Embryology	Endometrial thickness, number of oocytes retrieved, fertilisation rate, early embryo cleavage rate, implantation rate.

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Health outcome	Biomarker of effect (novel)
Susceptibility to outcomes	Biomarkers of susceptibility: genetic polymorphisms related to metabolism (EPHX1, GSTM1, GSTT1, GSTP1, PON1, CYP450 (1A1)) and DNA repair (XRCC1 and XRCC2) .SNP in vitamin D pathway genes (for prostate cancer).
Others	DNA fragments in plasma. Telomere length (biomarker of aging).

Selected biomarker(s) and experimental support

The comprehensive search conducted identified only a few biomarkers of effect that might be considered as “novel biomarkers”. These biomarkers cover a wide spectrum of target organs toxicity, but only a small number of studies assessed them. Hence, the issue of reproducibility and validity represents an important limitation for their predictive value or initial chemical safety screening.

As occurred with traditional biomarkers, the nervous system is the target organ with the largest number of studies assessing novel biomarkers. These biomarkers are chiefly behavioral and cover different domains: neurodevelopment, neurobehavioral (neurocognitive), neurodegeneration and neurotoxicity as a broader and less specific domain. On the other hand, adverse effects on the nervous system can also be assessed by using molecular biomarkers and functional neuroimaging, which contribute to a better understanding of the relationship between activity in certain brain areas and specific mental functions.

Immunoregulatory molecules also appear to be promising biomarkers, not only for immune diseases but also for neurotoxicity due to the cross-talk between the immune and the nervous system.

Also, epigenetics (in particular DNA methylation, either genome-wide DNA methylation or methylation of specific genes) appear to be promising biomarkers. Although genome-wide DNA methylation provides a huge amount of information, such information suffers from a lack of working hypothesis, false positive associations due to multiple comparisons, and difficulties in the interpretation of findings.

Notably, there are many studies addressing non-organ specific toxicity biomarkers, as is the case of genotoxicity and oxidative stress. Most of them are traditional biomarkers and rather extensively studied, although under different conditions (exposures, cells, populations, methodology...), which might account partially for the lack of reproducibility as sometimes these biomarkers behave differently showing either increased or decreased levels. The consideration of “novel biomarkers” for a few of them depends more on their recent use than on their novelty itself.

Another group is represented by biomarkers of susceptibility, which consist mainly of genetic polymorphisms coding for xenobiotic detoxification enzymes and DNA repair enzymes. Although these have been widely used over many years, the consideration of “novel biomarkers” relies on the lack of use in former studies on OPs.

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4.8 UV-Filters (UGR, DTU and RegionH)

The following table summarises the effect biomarkers for benzophenone-3 retrieved from our literature search.

Table 33: Effect biomarkers for benzophenone-3 retrieved from literature search

Study design / Reference	Study population	BP-3 exposure assessment	Matrix/effect biomarker(s)	Main results
Reproductive Hormones				
Prospective cohort study in subfertile couples (USA)/ Minguéz-Alarcon et al., (2019)	304 women (18-45 years)	BP-3 was assessed in two spot urine samples collected during each ART cycle using LC-MS. Median: 147 ng/mL	Follicle stimulating hormone (FSH) was measured in a spot serum sample at the third day of the menstrual cycle. Markers of ovarian response to gonadotropin stimulation (total and mature oocyte yield).	Urinary BP-3 concentrations were not associated with FSH serum levels or total/mature oocyte yield.
Case-control study (Denmark)/ Joensen et al., (2018)	Cases: 65 men genotyped for Filaggrin gene (FLG) loss-of-function mutations (19 years) Controls: 130 men without FLG mutations (19 years)	BP-3 was assessed in urine samples using LC-MS/MS Median: 2,8 ng/mL	Follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), luteinizing hormone (LH), sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG), total testosterone (TT), estradiol (E2) and inhibin B were measured in serum samples. Semen quality parameters	Within the group of FLG mutation carriers, but not in the control group, higher urinary BP-3 concentrations were associated with higher TT and E2 serum levels and lower FSH levels. FLG mutation could be a potential biomarker of susceptibility for BP-3 reproductive effects.
Cross-sectional study (USA)/ Pollack et al., (2018)	143 premenopausal women (18-44 years)	BP-3 was assessed in spot urine samples using HPLC-MS/MS Median: 3,8 ng/mL	Estradiol, progesterone, luteinizing hormone (LH), and follicle stimulating hormone (FSH), measured in serum samples	Higher urinary creatinine-adjusted BP-1 and BP-3 were associated with increased progesterone and with decreased estradiol, FSH, and LH serum levels.
Cross-sectional study (Spain)/ Adoamnei et al., (2018)	215 young university students (18–23 years old)	BP-3 assessed in single spot urine samples using UHPLC–MS/MS. Geometric mean: 1,3 ng/mL	Semen quality parameters (semen sample), follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), luteinizing hormone (LH), testosterone (TT), inhibin B estradiol (E2) and sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG) (serum samples)	Significant positive association between urinary BP-3 concentrations and serum FSH levels.
NHANES. Cross-		BP-3 assessed in		Higher urinary BP-3

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Study design / Reference	Study population	BP-3 exposure assessment	Matrix/effect biomarker(s)	Main results
sectional Survey (USA)/ Scinicariello & Buser, (2016)	588 child and adolescents participants (6-19 years)	spot urine samples using LC-MS GM (male children): 15,57 ng/mL GM (male adolescents):20,03 ng/mL GM (female children): 18,31 ng/mL GM (female adolescents): 35,59 ng/mL	Total testosterone (TT) in serum samples.	concentrations were associated with significantly lower TT serum levels in male adolescents.
Longitudinal study (USA)/ Buck Louis et al., (2015)	413 men (>18 years)	BP-3 assessed in urine samples using LC-MS GM:4,13 ng/ mL	Semen quality parameters measured within 24 h	No associations were observed between higher urinary creatinine-adjusted BP-3 exposure and seminal quality.
Case-control study (China)/ Chen et al., (2013)	877 idiopathic infertile men and 713 fertile controls	BP-3 assessed in urine samples using LC-MS GM: 0,07 ng/mL (cases and controls)	Semen quality parameters	There were no relationships between urinary BP-3 concentrations and semen quality parameters.
Thyroid Hormones				
Prospective mother-child cohort (Mexico)/ Berger et al., (2018)	454 pregnant women (>18 years) and 365 neonates	BP-3 assessed in maternal spot urine samples (average of first and second trimester samples) using LC-MS GM: 27 ng/mL	Free thyroxine (FT4), total T4 (TT4), and thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) in serum of the pregnant women (second trimester). Additionally, TSH levels in their neonates were measured at the time of heel stick.	Higher urinary BP-3 concentrations were associated with lower TSH and free T4 serum levels in pregnant women.
Prospective mother-child cohort (Puerto Rico)/ Aker et al., (2016)	106 pregnant women (18-40 years old)	BP-3 assessed in spot urine samples at two different visits during pregnancy (median weeks: 16-20 and 24-28), using LC-MS	Free triiodothyronine (FT3), free thyroxine (FT4), total thyroxine (TT4) and thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) were measured in maternal serum samples at two different visits (median weeks: 16-20 and 24-28). Estradiol (E2), progesterone, and sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG) were also assessed.	Urinary BP-3 concentrations were inversely associated with maternal FT3 serum levels (average of the two time points during pregnancy). Although no associations were observed in general between urinary BP-3 concentrations and reproductive hormones, higher BP-3 concentrations were associated with

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Study design / Reference	Study population	BP-3 exposure assessment	Matrix/effect biomarker(s)	Main results
				greater SHBG serum levels measured during the second visit.
NHANES. Cross-sectional study (USA)/ Przybyla, Geldhof, Smit, & Kile, (2018)	710 females and 850 males (12 years)	BP-3 assessed in urine samples using GC-MS GM: 11,73 ng/mL	Thyroid hormones (Total T3, Total T4, and Thyroid Stimulating Hormones) were measured in serum samples	In adolescent males, urinary BP-3 levels were negatively associated with total thyroxine. In females, urinary BP-3 levels were positively associated with triiodothyronine serum concentrations, although this association was not statistically significant.
Case-control study nested within a longitudinal birth cohort (USA) A repeated measures study/ Aker et al., (2018)	439 pregnant women (>18 years). 116 preterm birth cases and 323 controls.	BP-3 assessed in maternal spot urine samples at four prenatal visits (median weeks: 10, 18, 26, 35). Average prenatal BP-3 concentrations. ID-LC-MS/MS GM: 55 ng/mL	Free thyroxine (FT4), total thyroxine (T4), total triiodothyronine (T3), and thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) in blood plasma at the four prenatal visits.	BP-3 was associated with all thyroid hormones at least at one visit. BP-3 was negatively associated with T3 levels at all visits except the second one and with T4 levels at all visits except the fourth one. BP-3 was also negatively associated with the T3/T4 ratio at the last visit. On the contrary, BP-3 tended to be positively associated with TSH, especially at the second and third visits.
Prospective study (Denmark)/ Krause et al., (2018)	183 pregnant women	BP-1 and BP-3 assessed in spot urine samples during the second trimester using LC-MS/MS (GM: 2.5 ng/mL)	Thyroid hormones triiodothyronine (T3), free triiodothyronine (fT3), thyroxine (T4) and free thyroxine (fT4), TSH, insulin-like growth factor I (IGF-I) and its binding protein IGFBP3. Serum samples	No significant associations between maternal urinary concentrations of BP-1 or BP-3 and serum thyroid or growth factor levels were observed.
NHANES Cross-sectional Survey (USA)/ Kim, Kim, Won, & Choi, (2017)	1829 individuals (>12 years old)	BP-3 assessed in spot urine samples using GC/MS	Free and total T3 and T4 as well as thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) were measured in serum samples.	Higher urinary BP-3 concentrations were associated with decreased TT4 and FT4 serum levels. BP-3 concentrations also tended to be associated with decreased TT3 and FT3 levels, but higher TSH serum levels.
Neurobehavioral tests				
Prospective mother-child cohort (France)/ Nakiwala et al., (2018)	452 mother-son pairs (5-6 years)	BP-3 in spot urine samples collected between 22 and 29 gestational weeks, using HPLC-MS.	IQ of children	BP-3 concentration was not associated with the boys' verbal or performance IQ

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Study design / Reference	Study population	BP-3 exposure assessment	Matrix/effect biomarker(s)	Main results
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Median: 2,2 ug/L

Prospective mother-child cohort (France)/ Philippat et al., (2017)	At 3 years old: 529 children At 5 years old: 464 children	BP-3 assessed in spot urine samples using HPLC-MS	Child behavior: conduct problems, hyperactivity–inattention, peer relationship problems, emotional symptoms and prosocial behavior.	BP-3 was not associated with child behavior
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Oxidative Stress/Inflammation

Longitudinal study (Puerto Rico)/ Watkins et al., (2015)	105 pregnant women (markers of inflammation) 54 pregnant women (markers of oxidative stress) (18-40 years)	BP-3 assessed in spot urine samples using HPLC-MS GM: 58 ng/mL	Serum markers of inflammation (c-reactive protein (CRP), IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-10, and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α)) and urinary markers of oxidative stress (8-hydroxydeoxyguanosine (OHdG) and 8-isoprostane)	Exposure to BP-3 was associated with an increase in 8-isoprostane levels (oxidative stress marker) and a decrease in CRP (inflammation marker) levels.
Cross-sectional study (Brazil)/ Rocha et al., (2018)	300 Brazilian children (6–14 years)	BP-3 assessed in urine samples using LC-MS/MS GM: 3,71 ng/mL	Oxidative DNA damage was evaluated from the urinary concentrations of 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine (8OHdG).	Higher urinary creatinine-adjusted BP-3 was associated with greater concentrations of 8OHdG

Kidney/Endothelial function

Cross-sectional study (Korea)/ Kang et al., (2019)	441 women (20-45 years)	BP-3 assessed in spot urine samples using LC-MS Median: 0,4 g/mL	Urinary albumin to creatinine ratio (ACR)	Higher urinary creatinine-adjusted BP-3 and BP-1 concentrations were associated with greater ACR values in urine among adult women.
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Classic effect biomarkers

Reproductive biomarkers: Based on the potential reprotoxicity of benzophenone-3 (Ghazipura, McGowan, Arslan, & Hossain, 2017), some studies have evaluated reproductive hormone biomarkers and sperm quality markers in diverse human populations. While benzophenone-3 has not been associated with poorer sperm parameters (Adoamnei et al., 2018; Buck Louis et al., 2015; Chen et al., 2013; Joensen et al., 2018), associations with altered hormone levels including total testosterone (TT), estradiol (E2) and FSH have been reported in adult or young male adults (Adoamnei et al., 2018; Joensen et al., 2018). Female exposure to benzophenone-3 was

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inconsistently associated with FSH and other reproductive hormones (Mínguez-Alarcón et al., 2019; Pollack et al., 2018).

Of note, a report of the U.S. National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES), observed that male adolescents with higher urinary benzophenone-3 concentrations showed significantly lower serum levels of TT (Scinicariello & Buser, 2016). Given the relevance of this period of development, other biomonitoring studies and longitudinal cohorts should confirm or rule out this association.

Thyroid hormones: Higher urinary BP-3 concentrations were negatively associated with TSH and free T4 serum levels in Mexican pregnant women (Berger et al., 2018), and with lower serum free T3 levels among Puerto Rican pregnant women (Aker et al., 2016). Another birth cohort study in North American women found that higher prenatal urinary BP-3 concentrations were associated with lower serum free T3 and T4, and higher serum TSH levels assessed at different times throughout pregnancy (Aker et al., 2018). On the contrary, a Danish cohort of pregnant women exposed to very low concentrations of urinary BP-3 did not find any association with serum thyroid hormone levels (Krause et al., 2018). Additionally, higher urinary BP-3 concentrations were associated with decreased TT4 and FT4 serum levels in male and female participants aged more than 12 years of age from the NHANES, and BP-3 concentrations also tended to be associated with decreased TT3 and FT3 levels, but higher TSH serum levels (Kim, Kim, Won, & Choi, 2017; Przybyla, Geldhof, Smit, & Kile, 2018). Taken together, urinary benzophenone-3 concentrations have been associated with altered thyroid hormone levels in different study populations, designs and age groups, with a trend showing reduced serum T3 and T4 levels, and increased serum TSH levels in some cases, suggesting a potential anti-thyroid effect.

Oxidative stress/inflammation: In pregnant women, urinary benzophenone-3 concentrations were positively associated with urinary 8-isoprostane levels (a marker of lipid peroxidation), while negatively associated with serum C-reactive protein levels (marker of systemic inflammation) (Watkins et al., 2015). Among Brazilian children, higher urinary benzophenone-3 concentrations were associated with greater urinary 8-OHdG levels, a marker of DNA damage. More studies are needed to confirm or rule out these associations (Rocha et al., 2018).

Kidney/Endothelial function: One study reported that higher urinary creatinine-adjusted benzophenone-3 concentrations were associated with greater urinary albumin to creatinine ratio (ACR) among adult Korean women aged 20-45 years (Kang et al., 2019). The ACR is a validated marker of early endothelial dysfunction (Bartz, Caldas, Tomsa, Krishnamurthy, & Bacha, 2015) that should be further studied in HBM studies.

Neurobehavioral function: Although emerging experimental data shows that benzophenone-3 could exert negative actions in the brain (Wnuk et al., 2018), higher prenatal urinary benzophenone-3 concentrations were not associated with behavioral or cognitive problems in the French EDEN cohort, as measured by neuropsychological tests (Nakiwala et al., 2018; Philippat et al., 2017). Further experimental and epidemiologic studies are needed to confirm or rule out this hypothesis.

Novel effect biomarkers

No novel effect biomarkers were found. However, Joensen et al. (2018) studied a susceptibility biomarker in relation to reproductive hormone markers, which represent a novel approach of interest for HBM studies. The authors showed that higher exposure to urinary benzophenone-3 concentrations was associated with altered serum TT, E2 and FSH levels in adult men, but only among those who carried the filaggrin gene (FLG) mutation. This study highlights the importance

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and need to identify susceptible gene-environment interactions, in this case related to benzophenone-3 exposure.

Selected biomarkers

Reproductive hormones: BP-3 could alter the androgen/estrogen balance based on experimental findings (Ghazipura et al., 2017), and urinary exposure to BP-3 was associated with decreased serum TT levels in adolescent males in the NHANES (Scinicariello & Buser, 2016). Therefore, this potential association in adolescents should be further studied.

Thyroid hormones: Our search showed that exposure to BP-3 is associated with altered thyroid hormone levels in several studies, including both pregnant women and adults. Experimental studies support that benzophenones may alter thyroid hormone balance by influencing their central regulation and metabolism (Lee, Kim, Park, Moon, & Choi, 2018), and inhibition of thyroid peroxidase (TPO) appears as a potential mechanism (Paul et al., 2014; Song, Kim, Park, & Ryu, 2012; Song et al., 2011). Moreover, effects may be more pronounced in a context of low iodide availability, still prevalent in many parts of the world (Schmutzler et al., 2007).

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4.9 Hexavalent Chromium (INSA, FIOH, INRS)

The methodology followed for the literature survey on chromium and effect biomarkers as well as the results obtained are schematically presented in the following figure:

Figure 13: Output of the literature search for chromium.

Classical effect biomarkers

The search conducted for Cr(VI) biomarkers of effect in HBM studies resulted in 196 articles, from which 49 were eligible and the abstracts were screened. In those abstracts, we found 57 effect biomarkers used in Cr(VI) exposure, some already validated, which can be seen in Table 2.

The following table lists conventional effect biomarkers retrieved from studies of HBM to Cr(VI) exposure. The biomarkers are sorted according the number of times they were found in the 49 articles that resulted from the search.

Table 34: Conventional effect biomarkers retrieved from studies of HBM to Cr(VI) exposure

Biomarker	# of studies in the search	Hazard/ Health Outcome
8-OHdG	11	Mutagenicity/Carcinogenicity
Comet assay	10	Mutagenicity/Carcinogenicity
MDA (malondialdehyde)	8	Oxidative stress, Mutagenicity/Carcinogenicity Immunotoxicity
Micronucleus test	8	Mutagenicity/Carcinogenicity
GSH (glutathione)	3	Oxidative stress, Mutagenicity/Carcinogenicity

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Biomarker	# of studies in the search	Hazard/ Health Outcome
SOD (superoxide dismutase)	3	Oxidative stress, Mutagenicity/Carcinogenicity Immunotoxicity
LPO (lipid peroxidation)	3	Oxidative stress, Mutagenicity/Carcinogenicity Immunotoxicity
TAC (total antioxidant capacity)	2	Oxidative stress, Mutagenicity/Carcinogenicity Immunotoxicity
B2-MG (β 2 microglobulin)	2	Nephrotoxicity
NAG (N-acetyl-beta-(D)-glucosaminidase activity)	2	Nephrotoxicity
ALAD (delta-aminolevulinic acid dehydratase)	2	Nephrotoxicity
Nitrite*	2	Oxidative stress/ Carcinogenicity
Nitrate*	2	Oxidative stress/ Carcinogenicity
Malb (microalbuminuria)	2	Nephrotoxicity
Chromosomal aberrations	2	Mutagenicity/Carcinogenicity
8-isopgf2 α (8-isoprostane)*	2	Oxidative stress/ Carcinogenicity and Lung toxicity
Cytokine production	2	Immunotoxicity
Sperm motility	1	Reproductive toxicity
Cat (catalase)	1	Oxidative stress, Mutagenicity/Carcinogenicity
Kim-1 (kidney injury molecule-1)	1	Nephrotoxicity
NGAL (Neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin)	1	Nephrotoxicity
DNA fragmentation index	1	Mutagenicity/Carcinogenicity
CEA (plasma carcinoembryonic antigen)	1	Carcinogenicity

Biomarker	# of studies in the search	Hazard/ Health Outcome
NSE (neuron specific enolase)	1	Carcinogenicity
SCC (squamous cell carcinoma antigen)	1	Carcinogenicity
CYFRA21-1 (cytokeratin fragment antigen 21-1)	1	Carcinogenicity
CA72-4 (cancer antigen 72-4)	1	Carcinogenicity
AFP (α -fetoprotein)	1	Carcinogenicity
3-nitrotyrosine	1	Carcinogenicity
Proline	1	
H ₂ O ₂ *	1	Lung toxicity
Ph value*	1	Lung toxicity
PCO (protein carbonyls)	1	Nephrotoxicity
Nitric oxide	1	Carcinogenesis and vascular diseases
Respiratory capacity	1	Lung toxicity
TTM (total thiol molecules)	1	
Neurobehavioral tests	1	Neuropsychological dysfunction
LTB4 (leukotriene B4)	1	Dysregulated immune response
PGE2 (prostaglandin E2)	1	Lung toxicity
PSA (prostate-specific antigen)	1	Carcinogenicity
Hs-CRP (high sensitive C reactive protein)	1	Immunotoxicity
CC16 (Clara cell secretory protein)	1	Lung carcinogenicity
SP-D (surfactant protein D)	1	Lung carcinogenicity
TNF- α (tumor necrosis factor- α)	1	Lung carcinogenicity

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Biomarker	# of studies in the search	Hazard/ Health Outcome
Lymphocyte subsets characterisation	1	Immunotoxicity
MT (metallothioneins)	1	Carcinogenicity and neurological toxicity
Plasma total homocysteine (thcy)	1	Carcinogenicity
Serum folate	1	Metabolic and reproductive toxicity

*Measured in exhaled breath condensate

Novel effect biomarkers

The table below summarises the novel biomarkers evaluated for Cr(VI). Within these, we would like to highlight the feasibility of gene expression (e.g. DNA repair and detoxifying genes) and proteomics:

Table 35: List of novel effect biomarkers found for Cr(VI) exposure during the literature search

Novel effect biomarker	Brief description of the effect biomarker	Scoring table procedure	Final Score (max. 20 points)
Gene expression (DNA repair) (detoxifying genes) Pizzino et al. 2014	The major mechanism of action of chromium is through the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and endocrine disruption. It is known that these two MoA can influence gene expression and since ROS can directly produce lesions in DNA, DNA repair genes and detoxifying genes can be augmented in exposure to chromium.	The biomarker was assessed in serum (3p). There is a plausible mechanism of action between the exposure and the biomarker (2p). No related AOP was found (0p). The biomarker has been implemented in epidemiologic studies (5p). The feasibility was considered to be "high" (5p).	17
DNA methylation levels Linqing et al. 2016	DNA methylation patterns can be modified by xenobiotics, including chromium. Both genomic and mitochondrial DNA can be methylated and unmethylated and consequently gene expression altered (suppression of tumour suppressor genes and activation of oncogenes).	The biomarker was assessed in serum (3p). There is a plausible mechanism of action between the exposure and the biomarker (2p). No related AOP was found (0p). The biomarker has been implemented in epidemiologic studies (5p). The feasibility was considered to be "middle" (2p).	12

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Novel effect biomarker	Brief description of the effect biomarker	Scoring table procedure	Final Score (max. 20 points)
<p>Proteomics</p> <p>Hu et al. 2017</p>	<p>Chromium exposure can influence gene expression and consequently protein expression. Identification of important deregulated pathways, through proteomics, after exposure to xenobiotics can easily be achieved. Through the new techniques low and high molecular weight proteins can be detected.</p>	<p>The biomarker was assessed in serum (3p). There is a plausible mechanism of action between the exposure and the biomarker (2p). No related AOP was found (0p). The biomarker has been implemented in epidemiologic studies (5p). The feasibility was considered to be “middle” (2p).</p>	<p>12</p>
<p>Circulating-free-DNA</p> <p>Savarino et al. 2014</p>	<p>Circulating-free-DNA in blood might suggest an imbalance between cell proliferation and cell death. It can be considered a good surrogate marker for cancer.</p>	<p>The biomarker was assessed in serum (3p). There is a plausible mechanism of action between the exposure and the biomarker (2p). No related AOP was found (0p). The biomarker has been implemented in epidemiologic studies (5p). The feasibility was considered to be “low” (0p).</p>	<p>10</p>
<p>miRNA expression</p> <p>Cárdenas-González et al. 2016</p> <p>Li et al. 2014</p>	<p>miRNAs are gene expression regulators that can be influenced by several xenobiotics and thus influence the expression of tumour suppressor genes and oncogenes. They can also influence immunologic responses by regulating immune-specific genes. Due to their size, they are extremely resistant in biological samples and can be found in almost any kind of biological sample.</p>	<p>The biomarker was assessed in serum (3p). There is a plausible mechanism of action between the exposure and the biomarker (2p). No related AOP was found (0p). The biomarker has been implemented in epidemiologic studies (5p). The feasibility was considered to be “middle” (2p).</p>	<p>12</p>

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Regarding the second literature search for MoAs and KEs of Cr(VI) exposure for the construction of the corresponding AOP associated to cancer, we retrieved 173 articles for Cr(IV) and cancer, from which 117 were eligible; for Cr(VI) and stomach cancer 12 articles from which 10 were eligible; for Cr(VI) and respiratory cancer 38 articles from which 29 were eligible, and finally, for Cr(VI) and lung cancer 69 articles from which 51 were eligible. The two most common referred MoA of Cr(VI) toxicity identified in these abstracts were related to oxidative stress and DNA damage.

Selected biomarker(s) and experimental support

Regarding the new proposed biomarkers of effect, Cr (VI) exposure can influence gene expression and, consequently, protein expression. Gene expression analysis of specific genes involved in response to xenobiotics, such as detoxifying genes and DNA repair genes, can give valuable information about cellular pathways that are affected by Cr(VI) exposure. Furthermore, disruption of these pathways may be associated with genotoxicity induction, carcinogenicity or other pathological processes, giving mechanistic insights on potential disease outcomes. From a practical point of view, gene expression analyses are performed in blood, which is easily collected and allow sampling through time, and high throughput methodologies can be used. In gene specific approaches the costs are low, making these biomarkers good implementation candidates. Literature search retrieved one article (Pizzino et al. 2014) that applied gene expression in exposure to Cr (VI). Pizzino et al. (2014) studied oxidative stress and gene expression of detoxifying genes and DNA repair genes in an adolescent population of Milazzo-Valle del Mela area (Sicily, Italy), an industrialised area. The authors assessed the expression levels of OGG1, NQO1, ST13 and MT1A. They showed a significant up-regulation of OGG1 (a protein involved in BER repair pathway) and MT1A (a protein involved in metal excretion) mRNA expression in exposed vs. non-exposed adolescents. They also showed a slight, but not significant up-regulation of NQO1 and ST13 (detoxifying proteins) mRNA in the adolescents living in the studied area. Nevertheless, alterations in the expression of detoxifying genes and DNA repair genes are not specific to chromium exposure, though an adequate characterisation of the environmental or occupational setting together exposure biomarkers analysis would allow associations between exposure and gene expression data to be established.

A recent area of toxicology research that has shown promising results is epigenomics. Epigenomic changes, i.e., histone modifications, changes in DNA methylation and changes in microRNA expression, regulate gene expression through time. Modifications in the epigenome can be measured from many types of biological samples, including blood, and microRNAs are stable even in harsh conditions. As a limitation, and depending on the population size, the costs of methylation or microRNA expression can be high. Moreover, they can be caused by similar xenobiotics, as in the Linqing et al. (2016) study, where the changes identified in the methylation patterns are not specific to chromium exposure.

Proteomics can be more accurate than gene expression since, as seen above, regulator mechanisms can occur between gene expression and gene translation. Target proteins can be found in high quantities in biological fluids, and high-throughput data can be obtained. Through the new techniques, low and high molecular weight proteins can be detected, but they can be expensive depending on the number of samples analysed. Proteomics became a high throughput field of research that can be used with biological samples that are easily collected (though some with invasive techniques). Thus, a proteomic approach with the improved accuracy of new technologies and bioinformatics tools might be an important tool to associate xenobiotics and health outcomes. Within this literature search, an article that uses proteomics in order to associate mis-regulated proteins with chromium exposure was found (Hu et al. 2017). The authors recruited workers from a chromate production plant and found that the exposure group had higher levels of

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Cr in blood. In addition, among many proteins they found deregulated, they show a significant negative correlation between C reactive protein (CRP) and chromium levels in blood, and a significant positive correlation between sonic hedgehog protein (SHH) and chromium levels in blood. However, like in gene expression studies, the alterations in protein expression are not specific for chromium exposure. More important than a specific protein found through the proteomic approach, a signature of proteins detected as deregulated (up- or/and down-regulated) could work as an effect biomarker for chromium exposure.

Another possible effect biomarker is circulating-free DNA. Cell-free DNA in high amounts might suggest a high number of dying cells and transformed cells, thus being a good cancer biomarker. Can be isolated from blood, thus a follow-up of a health outcome can be easily monitored through time. However, the techniques available are still expensive. Since cancer is a multifactorial and slow evolving disease, the cell-free-DNA detected is a tumour marker surrogate and might not allow an association with xenobiotics exposure.

Gaps in Knowledge

During this literature search, several articles of chromium exposure were found but only a few of them reported effect biomarkers data. Most of the articles found reported data regarding exposure-only biomarkers or were done using human and non-human models (e.g. human cell lines and mice). There is a lack of studies transposing the data achieved in laboratory-only approaches to HBM approaches. Thus, a lot of putative effect biomarkers need to be studied in HBM to comprehend if they are good future candidate biomarkers for chromium exposure.

Although there is already an AOP associated with hexavalent chromium and intestinal tumours (Interaction with villi (MIE), Villus cytotoxicity (KE1), Crypt hyperplasia (KE2), Spontaneous mutation in crypt stem cells (KE3), Preneoplasia (KE4), Intestinal tumours (AO) (Thompson et al. 2016)), it will be important to develop new AOPs, e.g., for lung cancer to better understand the biological effect of hexavalent chromium and develop specific effect biomarkers.

Conclusions

From 49 articles found in this literature search, approximately 60 effect biomarkers were detected. Among these, some are already being used in HBM, others are used but in a lesser extent and others are putative novel effect biomarkers, thus being experimented for the first time in HBM studies and, particularly, in HBM studies regarding chromium exposure.

One common characteristic to all classical effect biomarkers is the fact that they are not specific for chromium exposures. They can also be altered due to exposures to other heavy metals or other compounds that frequently are present in mixture with chromium. Thus, although the novel effect biomarkers here described could be a new good tool for chromium exposure assessment, it is important to proceed with laboratory research in an attempt to find possible specific effect biomarker for chromium exposure, e.g., based on gene or protein patterns. This would still need validation before they could be applied in Human Biomonitoring studies.

Summarising, we believe that the potential novel effect biomarkers referred, i.e., gene expression of genes involved in detoxification and DNA repair pathways and proteomic analysis of urine and/or blood samples, could be further studied as cost-effective effect biomarkers related to Cr(VI) exposure.

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5 Executive summary

This deliverable presented results from the literature searches conducted to identify the most relevant effect biomarkers for the 2nd set of prioritised substances: Acrylamide, Arsenic, Lead, Mercury, Mycotoxins, Pesticides, UV-filters, as well as Hexavalent Chromium (belonging to the 1st set of substances, but not covered in D14.2).

Given the enormous amount of data collected, and the large and heterogeneous number of biological targets discussed at different levels of biological organisation (genes, epigenetic, proteins, metabolites, etc.), it has not been possible to provide a summary table. Instead we provide an executive summary with the most important points covered in this deliverable. Future works will refine and discuss the best effect biomarkers to be studied taking into account specific compounds, specific health endpoints and specific developmental periods, all of this in the light of available mechanistic evidence.

Acrylamide is a potential carcinogen and neurotoxic compound, that more recently has been suspected of also interfering with reproductive function. There is scarce information regarding useful effect biomarkers previously implemented in epidemiologic studies. For women reproductive effects, it seems that sex hormones in women and birth outcomes such as birth weight and head circumference could be sensitive endpoints. In men, acrylamide exposure should be investigated in relation to sperm quality and sperm DNA damage markers.

Arsenic was investigated in relation to cancer, metabolic syndrome, type 2 diabetes, cardiovascular disease and neurobehavioral health. No molecular or biochemical effect biomarkers were found for cancer endpoints. Blood glucose levels, serum lipids, abdominal obesity, blood pressure and adipokines (adiponectin, leptin, etc.), HbA1c and HOMA-IR are classical effect biomarkers useful for assessing Arsenic's cardiometabolic effects. Several experimental studies suggest that diabetogenic effects of As are mediated by oxidative stress. Both epidemiological and experimental studies reported either reduction of insulin secretion (caused by disrupted pancreatic β -cell function due to oxidative stress, cytotoxicity, dysfunction of mitochondria and/or insulin transport vesicles, apoptosis, autophagy, inflammation, or pyroptosis) or reduction of insulin sensitivity as primary effect of As. Many studies related Arsenic exposure with increased blood pressure and cIMT. Heart Rate Reserve (HRR) is lower when exposed to As, showing cardiac autonomic dysregulation. Regarding ECG measures, Q-Tc interval prolongation is the most cited effect of As exposure while the influence on other parameters remains unclear. Few effect biomarkers of Arsenic-related neurological effects were found, including plasma cholinesterase activity and serum pigment epithelium-derived factor (PEDF).

Lead is a paradigmatic neurotoxic agent for which a no-effect dose level in human populations has not been demonstrated. Apart from neuropsychological tests, brain derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) has been identified as an important target. Additionally, some epigenetic markers such as LINE-1-methylation, p16, CLC11A, DNHD1, could represent relevant markers. Additionally, the interaction of iron and lead levels is well-established. It is based on both animal and human studies confirming that iron deficiency increases intestinal lead absorption and lead body burden (Baker and Greer 2010). Therefore, assessing markers of iron status (Hb, Hct, sTFR - serum transferrin receptor and serum ferritin), would be preferable. It is well documented that lead (Pb^{2+}) blocks the N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor (NMDA) (Bal-Price and Meek 2017). According to AOP12 (*Chronic binding of antagonist to NMDARs during brain development leads to neurodegeneration with impairment in learning and memory in aging*) and AOP13 (*Chronic binding of antagonist to NMDARs during brain development induces impairment of learning and memory abilities*) decreased calcium influx and reduced levels of Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) are

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cellular key events. Therefore, BDNF (*BDNF* methylation, gene expression and/or blood BDNF levels) should be included in the set of biomarkers.

Mercury, another known neurotoxic compound, was studied also in relation to metabolic, immune and multiple health endpoints. BDNF, oxidative stress and many epigenetic and gene expression markers were found to be correlated with higher exposure to mercury in human studies. Given the wide amount of specifically deregulated genes and epigenetic effects identified, future efforts should prioritise the most interesting molecular targets based on mechanistic and AOP information.

Mycotoxins are secondary fungal metabolites often found as natural contaminants in food (e.g., cereals and cereal-based food, dried fruits, coffee and fruit-based beverages), which is the major route of mycotoxin exposure. In relation to fumonisins, that can cause hepatotoxicity, the activity of liver enzymes ALT, AST and ALP, as well as creatinine appear as very unspecific effect biomarkers associated with hepatotoxicity and nephrotoxicity, respectively. Since FB1 has been recognised as an inhibitor of ceramide synthase, involved in lipid metabolism, the sphingolipid metabolism (evaluated through urinary or blood sphinganine, sphingosine and their ratio) appears as the most reliable and specific effect biomarker to use. However, further epidemiological research is necessary to prove the association between fumonisin exposure and altered sphinganine to sphingosine ratio, as well as the predictive potential of these biomarkers for a given health endpoint such as hepatotoxicity and hepatocellular carcinoma.

Even though the number of Human Biomonitoring studies about human exposure to mycotoxins, including fumonisin B1 (FB1) and deoxynivalenol (DON) has increased in the last decade, only very few of them have included the analysis of effect biomarkers. Concerning FB1, the only specific effect biomarker that has been reported to date is the measurement of sphingolipids in blood or urine, relying on the recognised mechanism of toxicity of this substance. Nonetheless, the sensitivity of this biomarker is still a matter of debate. On the other hand, diverse *in vitro* and a few *in vivo* studies have been better characterising the cellular and molecular mechanism of action of FB1, particularly, its genotoxicity and tumor promoting activity. These works have pointed to some endpoints and methodological approaches, e.g., gene expression or gene methylation analyses, that deserve to be further explored in an attempt to discover novel effect biomarkers. Regarding DON, a single study referring the use of effect biomarkers related to its immunotoxicity and autism was retrieved.

Pesticides

Overall, several biomarkers were identified covering a wide spectrum of target organs toxicity, but only a small number of studies assessed them. Hence, the issue of reproducibility and validity represents an important limitation for their predictive value or initial chemical safety screening. The nervous system is one the most concerning target of pesticide exposure in general. In addition to neuropsychological tests, molecular biomarkers and functional neuroimaging will provide a better understanding of potential adverse effects. Immunoregulatory molecules also appear to be promising biomarkers, not only for immune diseases but also for neurotoxicity due to the cross-talk between the immune and the nervous system. Thyroid hormone and reproductive effects are also a concern. Notably, there are many studies addressing non-organ specific toxicity biomarkers, as is the case of genotoxicity and oxidative stress. Most of them are traditional biomarkers and rather extensively studied, although under different conditions (exposures, cells, populations, methodology...), which might account partially for the lack of reproducibility as sometimes these biomarkers behave differently showing either increased or decreased levels. The consideration of "novel biomarkers" for a few of them depends more on their recent use than on their novelty itself. Another group is represented by biomarkers of susceptibility, which consist mainly of genetic polymorphisms coding for xenobiotic detoxification enzymes and DNA repair enzymes.

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Chlorpyrifos is an organophosphate pesticide that inhibits the acetylcholinesterase, thus causing poisoning through a collapse of the central nervous system of the insect. The World Health Organization (WHO) considers this pesticide moderately hazardous to humans. Based on its acute toxicity and its chronic exposure, chlorpyrifos has been associated with neurological effects and developmental and autoimmune disorders. Diverse epidemiological studies have found a significant negative association between the levels of CPS, concretely 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol and a downregulation of the butyrylcholinesterase and acetylcholinesterase. Additionally, children exposed in utero had an enlargement of some regions of the brain, with an increase of the glia or white matter and, in girls, a reduction of the parietal lobe. Neurodevelopmental and immune markers should be investigated in HBM studies.

Dimethoate is a widely used organophosphate (OP) insecticide and acaricide on several agricultural crops, tree crops, and ornamentals. Like other OPs, dimethoate is an acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibitor, leading to acetylcholine accumulation, hyperstimulation of nicotinic and muscarinic receptors, and disrupted neurotransmission. Very scarce data is available on human effect biomarkers.

Fipronil is a broad-spectrum insecticide and acaricide of the phenylpyrazole family. It is widely used in crop protection due to its systemic nature, in urban areas for insect control and in veterinary practice. Its neurotoxicity arises from non-competitive blocking of gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA)-gated chloride channels resulting in excessive neuronal stimulation and death. Its specificity for target organisms derives from its higher affinity for invertebrate GABA-A and GABA-C receptors than those of mammals. Fipronil is metabolised by CYP3A4 to Fipronil-sulfone which is relatively more biologically active and considerably more toxic, persistent, bioaccumulative and less selective than the parent compound. The effects of fipronil on the Hypothalamus-Pituitary-Thyroid axis are substantiated by in vivo and in vitro evidence. HBM studies should investigate thyroid hormones in relation to fipronil exposure.

Glyphosate

Premature mortality from Parkinson's disease and the occurrence of autism spectrum disorder were associated with glyphosate exposure in humans. In rats, oxidative stress and apoptosis were observed in the brain. In vivo studies showed effects of glyphosate on locomotor activity, anxiety, memory, and depressive-like behavior. Deregulation of the dopaminergic, glutamatergic and/or cholinergic systems and oxidative stress may be involved. Glyphosate was reported to inhibit acetylcholinesterase in several experimental studies. The study of acetylcholinesterase and thyroid hormones would be interesting in epidemiologic studies. Novel molecular or biochemical effect biomarkers were not reported in epidemiological studies, except for serum S100B as a predictor of neurologic complications in patients with acute glyphosate poisoning.

Pyrethroids

Many references were found related to pyrethroid exposure. Sperm related chromosomal abnormalities observed following pesticide exposure could serve as novel biomarkers. Two epidemiological studies have reported sex chromosome disomy and disomy of chromosomes 18 and 21 in men with increased levels of a permethrin pyrethroid metabolite, cis-3-(2,2-Dichlorovinyl)-1-methylcyclopropane-1,2-dicarboxylic acid (CCDA). Two studies showed that exposure to pyrethroids and other pesticides significantly reduced or inhibited acetylcholinesterase and butyryl cholinesterase activities in the blood of pesticide applicators, and many others reported neurobehavioral alterations at a population level. One study identified that pyrethroid metabolites significantly increase the risk for coronary heart diseases. Significant changes in antioxidant enzymes like superoxide dismutase, catalase and glutathione and increased malondialdehyde

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levels were reported in pesticide workers in 4 studies. Two studies identified an increased prevalence of abnormal glucose regulation in pesticide users. Two studies have reported changes in interleukin levels following exposure to pesticides. Changes in interferon- γ , IL-2, IL-8 and IL-22 were reported. The specificity of interferons for pesticide exposure needs to be confirmed.

UV-filters

Exposure to benzophenone-3 (BP-3), one of the most widely used UV-filters, may alter the androgen/estrogen balance based on experimental findings and urinary exposure to BP-3 was associated with decreased serum TT levels in adolescent males in the NHANES. Therefore, this potential association in adolescents should be further studied.

Our search also showed that exposure to BP-3 is associated with altered thyroid hormone levels in several studies, including both pregnant women and adults. Experimental studies support that benzophenones may alter thyroid hormone balance by influencing their central regulation and metabolism, and inhibition of thyroid peroxidase (TPO) appears as a potential mechanism. Moreover, effects may be more pronounced in a context of low iodide availability, still prevalent in many parts of the world. Therefore, thyroid hormones should also be investigated in HBM studies. No novel effect biomarkers for BP-3 were observed.

Hexavalent Chromium

All classical effect biomarkers found are not specific for chromium exposures. They can also be altered due to exposures to other heavy metals or other compounds that frequently are present in mixture with chromium. Thus, although the potential biomarkers described here could be a new good tool for chromium exposure assessment, it is important to proceed with laboratory research in an attempt to find possible specific effect biomarker for chromium exposure, e.g., based on gene or protein patterns. This would still need validation before they could be applied in Human Biomonitoring studies. Summarising, among these effect biomarkers referred, i.e., gene expression of genes involved in detoxification and DNA repair pathways and proteomic analysis of urine and/or blood samples, could be good effect biomarkers of Cr(VI).

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6 General conclusions and future steps

This work has been able to gather the most relevant effect biomarkers implemented in epidemiologic studies for the 2nd list of prioritised substances, and mechanistic insight and AOP information has been briefly discussed in the case of the most interesting biomarkers. The gathered information, when more refined and in conjunction with mechanistic knowledge, should be the basis for a potential future selection of effect biomarkers to be implemented in the HBM4EU aligned studies in relation to the 2nd of prioritised compounds. Additionally, in those cases in which no or very few effect biomarkers have been explored in human populations, experimental information has been retrieved and analysed, opening the possibility for the development of novel biomarkers and the advancement of gaps in knowledge (i.e. the scarce availability of neurological biomarkers).

As done with biomarkers obtained for the 1st list of prioritised substances, specific working groups from both WP13 (Adverse Outcomes Pathways-AOPs) and WP14 (Effect biomarkers) should discuss and propose a final list of effect biomarkers that could be implemented in HBM4EU aligned studies, following the protocol presented in AD14.3. This protocol takes into account experimental studies and AOPs, the adverse outcomes of highest concern for each chemical family, the critical period of development in which exposure is assessed in the aligned studies (children, adolescents and/or adults), the biological matrix available (urine or serum), the validity of each particular effect biomarker, as well as logistic and technical issues.

In a similar way to the work presented in D14.2, the results of these literature searches (D14.5/D14.6) will be refined, complemented with experimental information and published in peer-review journals during the coming years to create a corpus of knowledge that may help to approach the field of effect biomarkers in a more systematic way.